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D.5.5 Report on the development of monitoring for safe analysis at IPERION HS facilities and Definition of the standard Irradiation Passport

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Abstract

The development of particle-based techniques for the last 20 years has tremendously impacted the knowledge of materials from cultural heritage archaeology and paleontology. The development and use of particle accelerators and laser-based approaches have significantly enrichment the capacity to characterize heterogeneous and complex materials that hold information on our past. Moreover, the increasing brightness or fluence of modern accelerator-based sources provides critical benefit for the study of traces or diluted species in complex media as found in heritage samples. Such developments have also gradually triggered the attention of the impact of irradiation on materials properties and an increasing awareness has started to be paid to defect formation that can lead for instance to color change, mechanical fragility, or misinterpretation of collected analytical data.

Based on the pioneer research programs implemented in the framework of the IPERION-CH European Commission research projects and of the activities organized under the umbrella of the International Atomic Energy Agency and in the framework of European actions (IAEA), The task „*Monitoring strategies for safe analysis of heritage artefacts*“ has focused on the implementation of state-of-the-art monitoring strategies to detect, follow and interpret irradiation-induced changes **on ancient and irradiation materials. The implementation of the work has strongly relied on the expertise of the research groups involved in the field, and on the importance of monitoring changes at different time scale, from during the time of irradiation and at longer term.**

The task has been organized according to three research axes: (1) New methods for real-time detection of physical and chemical changes induced by laser radiation, by X-ray and by ion beams. Imaging-based strategies will be used as an in-situ probe to dynamically survey colorimetric change and luminescence contrasts. Statistical data processing methods will be used to design data collection protocols, optimizing the signal-to-noise ratio according to the dose and to the size of the spectral maps collected. (2) Post-irradiation survey protocols for objects, using FIXLAB and MOLAB. We will evaluate the slow kinetics of physical and chemical changes after irradiation to optimize storage conditions and hinder or slow down changes. (3) the development of an “**Irradiation Passport**”, defined by teams associating curators, paleontologists, archaeologists, conservation scientists and engineers in order to generate a standardized document attached to each object, specimen or sample, archiving its “irradiation history” to enrich the data accessible in ARCHLAB and in the future E-RHIS DIGILAB in collaboration will be developed with the IAEA Expert Group on “Safe Analysis of Cultural and Natural Heritage Objects and Materials”.

The consortium's work has focused on the development of monitoring strategies, encompassing the detection of changes during and after the irradiation, based on the study of specific materials including, for example, paint layers, ancient lead glasses, parchments and fossil specimens. The variety of probes and observable used to study evolution of materials under irradiation triggered exchanges about the definition of what is a change and does it impact the visual perception and the preservation of the chemical and mechanical integrity of materials at longer term. The work developed within the task has provided practical monitoring protocols optimized to study specific materials reactivity under particles irradiation in order to set mitigation strategies and provide a robust base for further application to a larger panel of cultural heritage materials. The exchanges triggers with the consortium have also allowed to set new paths of further development of a standardized irradiation passport.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
ATR-FTIR	Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy
BO	bonding oxygen
CPVC	Critical Pigment Volume Concentration
CW	Continuous wave
DR-FTIR	Diffuse Reflectance FTIR spectroscopy
FORS	Fiber Optic Reflectance Spectroscopy
FoV	field of view
FWHM	Full width at half maximum
GENS-LIBS	Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy of gas enhanced by solid initiator
GUI	graphic user interface
ICP-OEM	Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometry
IBA	Ion Beam Analysis
IR	infrared
LIBS	Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
LIF	using laser induced fluorescence
MPEF	multiphoton excitation fluorescence
MSC	Multiplicative scatter Correction
μ -RS	Micro-Raman spectroscopy
μ XAS	Micro X-ray absorption spectroscopy
NAA	<i>Neutron activation analysis</i>
NLOM	nonlinear optical microscopy
NRA	Nuclear Reaction Analysis
OA	oil absorption
ODC	oxygen deficiency centres
OM	Optical microscopy
<i>PGAA</i>	Prompt-gamma neutron activation analysis
PIGE	Particle Induced gamma-ray Emission
PIXE	Particle Induced X-ray Emission
PVC	pigment volume concentration
RBS	Rutherford Backscattering Spectrometry
SANS	small angle neutron scattering
SDD	silicon drift detector
SDS-PAGE	Sodium dodecyl-sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis
SEM-EDX	Scanning Electron Microscopy Energy Dispersive X-Ray
SNV	Standard Normal Variate
UHR-SEM	Ultra high resolution Scanning Electron Microscopy
VIS-NIR	Visible – near infrared
VOC	Volatile organic compound
XANES	X-ray absorption near-edge

XEOL	X-ray excited optical luminescence
XRF	X-ray fluorescence

Context and narrative

State-of-the-art

For the over 10 years, research on the impact of photonic and particles analyses on ancient and cultural heritage materials has gained some interest along the development of increasing brightness or fluence of modern accelerator-based sources and the development of laser-based techniques, which provides valuable benefit when studying altered and heterogeneous materials, to detect and characterize traces or diluted species in complex media as found in heritage samples.

In particular, beginning in 2011, through the support of the International Atomic Energy Agency and in the framework of European actions (IAEA), such as the IPERION-CH project, a number of initiatives have focused on organising the investigation about the behaviour of ancient and cultural materials under particles. Consultancy meetings were organised in 2013 and 2022 (Vienna, Austria) and two technical meetings in 2015 in Paris, France and in 2017 in Amsterdam, Netherlands under the umbrella of the IAEA. In parallel, a specific task untitled „Safe boundaries for analysis of heritage materials under intense radiation sources” of the IPERION-CH European Commission funded project has also fostered this topic.

The task „*Monitoring strategies for safe analysis of heritage artefacts*” is a continuation of the previous initiatives and aimed to develop new strategies to detect and monitor irradiation-induced changes. The primary objective of this work was to foster and develop the implementation of applicable real-time approaches at FIXLAB and MOLAB to document the status of artefacts during characterization and to develop post-irradiation survey methodologies. This involves leveraging the consortium's expertise in understanding the behaviour of materials and in adapting new protocols to optimize the detection of changes. This work has also aimed to contribute to the development of a numerical tool allowing to record and archive the history of irradiation of materials, throughout the concept defined in 2017 of an irradiation-passport.

Structure of deliverable

The task 5.3 was organized into three sub-tasks that aimed at covering the critical time frames at which monitoring irradiation-induced modifications at cortical.

The first sub-task was dedicated to the development of new methods for real-time detection of physical and chemical changes induced by laser radiation, by X-ray and by ion beams. The aim was here to implement dedicated solutions to evaluate their sensitivity to probe in situ and dynamically changes using a variety of probes coupled to dedicated statistical data processing methods.

The second sub-task aimed to develop protocols to monitor changes after irradiation, using techniques used in FIXLAB and MOLAB. Slow kinetics of physical and chemical changes on specific cases studies were probed after irradiation to better understand materials behaviors and provide enhanced knowledge to optimize storage conditions and hinder or slow down changes.

The last sub-task focused on key concepts and parameters that need to be taken into accounts in the structuration and the future implementation of digital folder that would gather all the information associated with the irradiation undertaken of an object or a sample and that would follow it all its life. Such an irradiation passport would also be extremely useful no to enrich the knowledge about history of irradiation and the its impact on the preservation of materials It would also enrich all the data accessible in ARCHLAB and in the future E-RHIS DIGILAB. Collaboration has been triggered the IAEA Expert Group on “Safe Analysis of Cultural and Natural Heritage Objects and Materials.

Structure of the three sub-tasks

During the implementation of the task, and based on the various expertise of the members of the consortium, the choice was made to select a restricted list of materials which are known to be reactive under irradiation and which were good representatives of the challenges of implementing efficient monitoring strategies at different facilities, from portable laser based systems up to particle accelerators. Moreover, among the various case studies developed here, the specificity of ancient systems were particularly at stake when implementing monitoring strategies, such as the heterogeneity of materials, the effect of the environment of the materials studied in its broadest meaning were particularly studied on their reactivity under irradiations. binder, the heterogeneity and the analysis environment on the typologies and modification kinetics generated.

The work has also focused on the impact of techniques that are widely used in the field of cultural heritage and ancient materials and that are also used with the context of MOLAB and FIXLAB facilities, and for which materials modification has been observed, such as for example, Raman spectroscopy, proton and ion beam analyses. In that context, the different research topics at covering the question of the spatial scale at which changes are induced and detected with respect of the of the size of the irradiated area and its evolution through time.

A last part of the deliverable is dedicated to the work dedicated to the irradiation passport. In context of the development of such tool, the question of technical vocabulary used to describe the methodology of irradiation (unit of doses, metadata of the data collected, description of the

modifications observed) has been tackled. Aggregating information about practices of reporting analytical conditions and parameters was a first step to structure the development of “irradiation passport” and to establish the procedures in connection with the work of task 5.5.

Overview project partners

Abbreviation	Institute	Country
CNR-IFAC	Istituto di Fisica Applicata “N. Carrara”, CNR	Italy
CNR-ISPC	Institute of Heritage Science, CNR	Italy
CNRS-PANEMA	European Photonics Institute for the non invasive analyses of ancient materials	France
IRCP	Chimie ParisTech, PSL University, CNRS, Institut de Recherche de Chimie Paris	France
CNRS/Synchrotron SOLEIL	Synchrotron SOLEIL	France
C2RMF	Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées de France	France
FR New AGLAE / UAR3506 CNRS Lab-BC	New AGLAE/ Laboratoire de développement instrumental et de méthodologies innovantes pour les Biens Culturels (Lab-BC)	France
EK	HUN-REN Centre for Energy Research	Hungary
HSL	Heritage Science Laboratory, University of Ljubljana	Slovenia
IQF-CSIC	Instituto de Química Física Blas Cabrera - CSIC	Spain
ICV-CSIC	Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio,	Spain
IEM-CSIC	Instituto de Estructura de la Materia	Spain
	Imperial College, London	United Kingdom
MTA Atomki	Magyar Tudományos Akadémia Atommagkutató Intézet	Hungary
NCU	Uniwersytet Mikołaja Kopernika Toruń	Poland
NG	The National Gallery, London	United Kingdom
NTU-ISAAC	Imaging and Sensing for Archaeology, Art history and Conservation, Nottingham Trent University	United Kingdom
	Laboratoire de photophysique et photochimie supramoléculaires et macromoléculaire	France
RCE	Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands	The Netherlands

SATIE	Systèmes et Applications des Technologies de l'Information et de l'Energie, Cergy-Paris Université	France
UCL	UCL Institute for Sustainable Heritage	United Kingdom
UCL	Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering	United Kingdom
ZVKDS	Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia, Ljubljana	Slovenia

1. Research projects

1.1 Exposure limits of Raman spectroscopy to plastics

1.1.1 Context and concept:

This project focused on the investigation of the possible damage that may occur when heritage plastics are examined using Raman spectroscopy. Cellulose Acetate, Polypropylene, and Polylactic Acid and three pigments were analysed. A dedicated sample shape was designed and built to study the effect of laser illumination from Raman spectroscopy under different laser wavelengths, powers and exposure times. Evidence suggests that Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy was unable to detect reliable and reproducible changes in the samples, suggesting that Raman spectroscopy can be considered to be safe. However, the analysis to date does not exclude the possibility of specific chemical shifts which might be detected as the analysis is further optimised.

Plastics make up a wide range of modern cultural heritage objects that are now of historic and cultural interest, but that degrade rapidly, unpredictably and in different ways compared to more traditionally curated materials. The nature of plastic degradation is complex and an understanding of how chemical and physical properties vary within a three-dimensional plastic object would help in the development of conservation strategies and could be provided with imaging. However, we have anecdotal evidence that the development of imaging techniques for plastics is inhibited due to concern among conservators about the potential damage caused to plastics by the radiation involved in such techniques.

Various optical analysis techniques have been used to characterize plastics] based on the fact that different polymers present a specific spectral fingerprint in the IR and NIR range (Analytical Methods Committee, 2018). For example, NIR imaging has been used to characterize and quantify the components of historic plastic materials]. Furthermore, although it is well established that ultraviolet and x-ray radiation, at high dose levels, will cause damage to plastics (McKeen, 2019; Simon, 1993; Stephenson et al., 1961), most of these results were obtained from high irradiation levels encountered in industry and that are not relevant in the heritage environment.

The purpose of this proposed work is to establish safe exposure levels for Raman spectroscopy, which is a commonly used analysis method applied to plastics. The aim is to determine safe limits for Raman spectroscopy applied to certain plastics of historic significance. This will inform scientists and conservators who are interested in applying Raman spectroscopy to plastics and will act as a pilot study for future grant applications aimed at extending the work to a broader range of analysis methods and plastics.

1.1.2 Monitoring protocol

Project plan

Three types of plastics were analysed for damage, Cellulose Acetate, Polypropylene and Polylactic Acid (PLA). These three plastics are common, historically interesting and represent three major classes of plastics (cellulose-based, polyolefin and condensation polymers, respectively).

Some samples were coloured using PG8 (green) and PR48 (red) pigments and others left unpigmented. Green, red and clear samples of polypropylene were purchased, but the pigments used in their manufacture was not disclosed.

Polymer Type	Plasticiser	Pigment	Colour
Cellulose Acetate	Diethyl phthalate (22%)	PR48:2 (15865)	Red
		PG8 (10006)	Green
		None	Clear
Polypropylene	None		Red
			Green
		None	White/Clear
Polylactic Acid	None	PR48:2 (15865)	Red
		PG8 (10006)	Green
		None	Clear

Table 1: Combinations of polymers, plasticisers and pigments used in this work

Test targets, made with the different combinations of polymer, plasticiser and pigments shown in Table 1, were made. Each target had 12 points identified. Seven were illuminated at different power levels with four different wavelengths using Raman spectroscopy systems. Three were left as controls and two as spare points.

In total, there were 756 irradiations, made up of 3 x plastics, 3 x pigments, 3 x repeated measurements, with/without plasticiser, 4 x Raman wavelengths and 7 x power levels. These were then assessed for damage with about 7000 measurements, with each of the irradiated points measured (with the addition on unirradiated control points) three times, each before and after irradiation.

1.1.2.1 Sample Preparation

The cellulose acetate was made in-house using a solvent casting method (Da Ros et al., 2021). Plasticiser diethyl phthalate (DEP) (Sigma Aldrich, UK) was dissolved in acetone, then commercial cellulose acetate (Sigma Aldrich UK) was added together with any pigments, and more acetone. The mixture was then kept under reflux for 4.5 hours and allowed to cool for an hour, while being stirred continuously to ensure homogeneity. The solution was poured over a flat glass tray and allowed to evaporate for 1 week under a glass lid at room temperature.

PLA granules (3devo, NL) were heated to 180-240°C inside a fume hood using a laboratory hotplate at which point they became semi-solid. Pigments and plasticisers were added and while being stirred continuously to ensure homogeneity. The solution was poured over a PTFE evaporating dish and allowed it to evaporate for 3 days under a glass lid at room temperature.

Polypropylene was purchased as 1 mm thick sheets from Kitronik Ltd (UK).

Sample targets were laser cut from the prepared sheets following the design shown in Figure 1. 12 points were outlined using a circular punch using a laser cut guide. The points were far away enough from the edges to avoid any damaged areas caused by laser cutting. The guide ensured that the indentations were in similarly located on each sample. The sample was always orientated so the cut off corner was in the top left-hand corner. Points 1, 2 and 3 are on the top row and were used as unilluminated controls. The next seven points were irradiated and the last two were left as spare points. The prepared samples were then retained for irradiation and analysis (Figure 2)

Figure 1: Design of sample targets

Figure 2: Samples prepared and ready for examination.

Illumination

The samples were illuminated using Raman spectroscopy systems at four wavelengths. Ultraviolet and green illumination (533 nm and 325 nm) were carried out in the Department of Chemistry, UCL, UK using an inVia Raman microscope (Renishaw plc, UK), and red and near infrared illumination (785 nm and 1064 nm) at the Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia, Slovenia, using Bruker SENTERRA II Dispersive Raman Microscope and FT-Raman microscope RamanScope III systems (Bruker, Germany).

These wavelengths were selected to cover the widest range of wavelengths, to understand the differences between thermal degradation likely to occur at longer wavelengths chemical degradations likely to occur at short wavelengths.

Power and exposure duration settings were chosen to give the full range of likely illumination conditions for each wavelength.

A supercontinuum white light (450-2000 nm) laser (WhiteLase, Fianium UK) with a full spectrum power of 200 mW was used on a small number of additional samples to create significant visible damage, which was useful for testing the analytical techniques.

Analysis with ATR-FTIR

Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) measurements were carried out using a Nicolet iN10MX FTIR microscope (Thermo Fisher Scientific USA). An aperture of 300 x 300 μm was used together with the SlideOn MicroTip Ge ATR crystal attachment. At each of the 12 punched locations, 128 scans were collected to improve the signal to noise ratio. A consistent pressure of 40% was applied to the sample. All 12 points were analysed before and after Raman irradiation, with 3 repeats done at each point.

Analysis with microscopy

A Keyence digital microscope (Keyence UK) gave useful insight into mechanisms of damage but was not used for quantitative analysis.

Analysis with FTIR mapping

The Nicolet iN10MX FTIR microscope (Thermo Fisher Scientific USA) was used in reflectance mode to generate maps of the surface of the plastic samples. These images were used to determine the extent and location of any damage

1.1.3 Results

Analysis with ATR-FTIR

Three example sets of spectra are shown in Figures 3-5, showing ATR-FTIR spectra for cellulose acetate with no pigment, irradiated at 325 nm, polypropylene with red pigment, irradiated at 533 nm and PLA with green pigment, irradiated at 785 nm. Other combinations of plastic, pigment and irradiation wavelength have also been analysed. Each spectrum is baseline corrected and normalised. Points 4-10 show increasing power densities. The average control is shown in black, with a band denoting +/- 2 standard deviations in grey.

Figure 3: FTIR spectra of cellulose acetate with no pigment, irradiated at 325 nm

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of polypropylene with red pigment, irradiated at 533 nm

Figure 5: FTIR spectra of PLA with green pigment, irradiated at 785 nm

This complex data set requires further processing. The optimal settings for baseline correction, normalisation and the most appropriate peaks for analysis are to some extent subjective, with different researchers using different analysis schemes.

On the whole, we do not see convincing and reproducible evidence of damage on these samples.

Analysis with microscopy

Microscopy was done on the three green samples that were exposed to the white laser, as well as a couple of samples that had been exposed to Raman spectroscopy to explore the visual differences.

With the naked eye, only the three green samples exposed to the white laser showed any signs of damage. None of the samples exposed to Raman spectroscopy showed signs of damage. Figure 6 is a microscope image showing that the areas of damage following white laser irradiation were raised compared to the rest of the surface. The laser damaged surface showed a different morphology to the other areas of the same piece of plastic.

Figure 6: Microscopy images showing surface damage due to white laser irradiation

Analysis with FTIR mapping

Having seen no convincing evidence of damage using ATR-FTIR, we wanted to investigate whether there might be damage that the ATR-FTIR analysis was not detecting. This might, for example, be due to the illumination point and the detection point not coinciding, perhaps due to an optical misalignment.

We therefore carried out FTIR mapping to visualise the extended irradiated area. Figure 7 is an example, showing (left) the FTIR map and (right) a microscope image showing the circular indent marking the target area. There is no asymmetry in the FTIR image, and no points of increased intensity, suggesting that the lack of damage was genuine.

Figure 7: FTIR map of an irradiated area (left) and corresponding microscope image (right)

1.1.4 Interpretation of results

The analysis to date suggests that any damage caused by Raman irradiation of plastics is below the detection limit of ATR-FTIR spectroscopy.

However, it is possible that the irradiation and analysis do not coincide. More FTIR microscopy is necessary to exclude this possibility.

ATR-FTIR is very sensitive to surface contact. Analysis of the plastic damaged by the white light laser suggest that the damage predominantly appears as physical damage to the surface due to melting and cooling. We need to carry out more analysis of specific spectral peaks to demonstrate that any effects are genuinely due to chemical changes and not surface contact. We note the potential for pressure from ATR-FTIR tip to cause further damage

The complex spectra require careful normalisation and baseline correction, the details of which depend on the specific spectral properties and need to be further optimised for each plastic type. Any subtle spectral shifts due to chemical changes could have been missed by the full-spectral analysis we have carried out to date, and we intend to carry out more detailed analysis of specific peaks.

We aim to convert the power and exposure time settings from the Raman instruments to total energy density by calculating spot sizes, to allow different systems to be compared directly.

Once analysis is complete, the data will be released as an open source dataset suitable for teaching and research.

1.2 Novel probe for thermally controlled Raman spectroscopy using online IR sensing and emissivity measurements

1.2.1 Context and concept:

Although Raman spectroscopy is generally considered a non-destructive technique, laser heating represents a crucial issue for materials with high optical absorption at the excitation wavelength and low critical temperatures. Laser heating may produce band broadening and shifting, background increase, and even sample damage. Phase transitions, discolorations, or photo-degradation of the samples can be induced by laser irradiation at the typical intensities and total radiant exposure of Raman spectroscopy. The measurement and control of the laser induced temperature rise can allow avoiding data misinterpretation and undesired alterations.

It is well known that temperature affects the distribution of the population of the ground and excited vibrational states, so it can be found out from the ratio of Stokes and anti-Stokes lines intensities. However, the anti-Stokes bands for many materials are very weak so it is not trivial to achieve reliable temperature using their intensities. Moreover, this method is expensive because it requires the use of a Super-Notch filter and it is not suitable for in situ measurements.

We introduce a novel, non-contact temperature monitoring and then control method based on the measurement of the surface emissivity and its infrared (IR) emission. Emissivity (ε) is defined as the ratio of the radiant emittance of the sample and that of the black body, as recorded at the same temperature. It is a dimensionless number and it varies from zero (perfect reflector) to one (black body). This parameter, which represents the efficiency with which a material radiates the absorbed energy, must be known or preliminarily determined whenever approaching non-contact temperature measurements based on IR sensors.

Various setups and instruments have been developed and demonstrated, which allow measuring the emissivity. The main experimental techniques used are based on calorimetry, radiometry, or thermography, as direct approaches, and on the measurement of spectral reflectance, as an indirect method. The latter is straightly derived from the energy balance for a diffusing sample under irradiation: $E_i = E_a + E_R + E_T$. Since the absorbed energy, E_a , equals the emitted energy, E_e , (E_T and E_R do not contribute to the latter), the energy balance can be rewritten as $E_i = E_e + E_R + E_T$ or also as $1 = e + R + T$, where R and T are the reflectance and transmittance, respectively. Furthermore, T is negligible in the IR region for most solid samples, thus usually: $1 = e + R$, which corresponds to the complementarity between e and R (emissivity increases when the reflectance decreases).

In this work, we report an innovative IR sensing setup allowing for carefully mapping the emissivity of a material surface, as derived from reflectance measurements, and then to monitor and control the temperature rise during compositional mapping using Raman spectroscopy. The setup included an integrating sphere with four radiation channels for the measurement of the total reflectance by means of IR radiation source and sensor channels, of the thermal radiation from the laser excited area, and of the Raman spectrum, respectively. The demonstration of its effectiveness and reliability along with the small sizes of its components make the thermal control channels here developed suitable for integration with a variety of portable as well as laboratory Raman instruments. Furthermore, such an approach to the measurement of the CW laser induced heating could also be useful in laser material processing and other.

1.2.2 Monitoring protocol

Emissivity measurement

Different materials of known emissivity (e) ranges were selected, according to the literature data, in order to cover the whole interval between 0-1 through suitable sample preparation phases. The set of materials included metals (Al, Cu, Pb, Fe, and steel with different surface textures), plywood, gypsum, glass, marble, paper, PVC tape, and limestone.

The respective values of e , which depends on the specific surface features, were directly measured using a setup including Peltier cell, digital contact-thermometer equipped with K type thermocouple (Fluke, USA), and indirectly derived through an IR sensor based on a thermopile (TP_R) with detection range 6-14 μm (Phidgets Inc., CAN). The latter is provided with a blackbody calibration ($e=1$), digital reader, and app allowing to set any emissivity value between 0-1 and to plot the temperature time evolution.

Each sample was then placed on a small aluminum slab in strict thermal contact with the heated face (76 °C) of the Peltier cell and a thermocouple, which measured its temperature. When the sample reached the thermal equilibrium its temperature was registered and, simultaneously, the corresponding IR emission was detected by the TP_T sensor (a thermopile similar to TP_R). Thus, the emissivity of the sample surface was derived by suitably setting its value in the app of the sensor in order to achieve the same temperature as that directly measured by the thermocouple.

Following several preliminary tests, a probe terminated by an integrating sphere equipped with four radiation channels and allowing for indirect emissivity and temperature measurements along with Raman spectroscopy was developed (Figure 1). The internal surface of the sphere was coated with a reflecting aluminum film providing a homogeneous distribution of the IR radiation within the sphere itself during the measurement of the reflectance, R , of the samples under investigation. The latter was carried out using a partially collimated IR source (EOT, ITA) focused onto the sample surface through a ZnSe lens L_1 ($f_1=15$ mm) and the thermopile sensor, TP_R .

The IR emission produced by the laser heating of the sample during Raman excitation was collected in a confocal configuration and imaged onto the active area of the thermopile, TP_T (same specs as those of TP_R) using a ZnSe lens L_2 ($f_2=15$ mm, magnification factor=3).

Figure 1. Schematic setup of the thermally controlled Raman probe including emissivity and temperature measurements channels (see the text). The four radiation channels were housed in the integrating sphere shown in the inset.

A LabVIEW™ virtual machine was developed for controlling the IR source and the thermopile sensors, deriving the reflectance and emissivity values, and performing Raman spectroscopy through a dedicated graphic user interface (GUI). To derive the total reflectance, R , the IR radiation scattered by the sample was compared with that scattered by a Cu sample, as derived through the contact thermal measurement described above: $R_{Cu}=1-e_{Cu}$. The sample temperature was detected in both IR source ON (T) and OFF (T_0) conditions for removing the room temperature background. Moreover, the thermal contribution of the sphere, as measured with the IR source switched ON without the target (background component due to the radiation scattering of the entrance and exit apertures) was subtracted (T_{sp}). R was hence calculated according to the following formula:

$$R = \frac{T^4 - (T_0^4 + T_{sp}^4)}{T_{Cu}^4 - (T_0^4 + T_{sp}^4)} R_{Cu}, \quad (1)$$

where the fourth powers of the temperatures come from the relation between the emittance and the temperature given by the Stefan-Boltzmann law. Equation 1 allowed to indirectly derive the emissivity as $e_{\square}=1-R$.

Temperature control

The Raman system was a commercial fiber coupled portable spectrometer (i-Raman, B&W Tek, USA) extensively used in archaeometry and conservation. Its laser excitation beam (785 nm) was focused onto the sample at an angle of 30° (with respect to the normal) through a plano-convex lens L_3 (Figure 1) with a focal length $f_3=20$ mm. The scattered light was collected through the same lens and sent to a spectrometer providing a spectral resolution of about 8 cm^{-1} .

The sizes of the focal spot were measured using a digital microscope (Dino-Lite, AnMo Electronics Co., TW) at high magnification ($500\times$). The laser spot showed an elliptical shape (Figure 2a) with enough regular transverse (blue) and longitudinal (black) profiles (Figure 2b), respectively.

Figure 2. a) Image of the focal spot of the laser excitation beam ($500\times$). a) Transverse (blue line) and longitudinal (black line) section of the focal spot and corresponding best fit (orange and red line) using super-Gaussian functions.

The best fit of the curve was achieved through a super-Gaussian function with index 1.2 (Figure 2b). The semi-major and semi-minor axis corresponding to 77% of the total area were about 215 and 168 mm, respectively. Thus, the mean diameter of the focal spot was about 383 mm.

The temperature was calculated using the following formula derived from Stefan-Boltzmann black body law (see for example) by taking into account the environmental contribution and the fact that the laser spot covered only a part of the field of view (FoV) area [6]:

$$T = \sqrt[4]{\frac{T_s^4 - (1-\varepsilon) \cdot R_A \cdot T_0^4 \cdot \theta - (1-R_A) \cdot T_0^4}{\varepsilon \cdot R_A \cdot \theta}}, \quad (2)$$

where T_s is the apparent blackbody temperature ($e = 1$) provided by the thermopile sensor TP_T , R_A =laser spot area/FoV area, and θ the lens transmissivity (0.95 in the present setup).

Figure 3. Temperature spatial profiles, as detected by the TP_T sensor during Y scan of a hot wire in the focal plane with laser OFF (black) and ON (green), and along X scan with laser OFF (blue) and ON (red).

Equation 2 represents the recalibration of the thermal sensor according to the specific setup and material under study, whose emissivity, e , was measured as described above. The areal ratio R_A in eq. 2 was experimentally determined by moving a thin metallic wire across the laser spot, along the Y and X axis, respectively. The wire was heated at a constant temperature ($70\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) with a suitable electric current and for each position, two temperatures were measured: with the laser switched OFF and ON, respectively. The detected temperature rises $DT(X)$ and $DT(Y)$ with the laser OFF shown in Figure 3 (blue and black lines, respectively) provided the FoV of the sensor TP_T . The same scans with the laser ON (red and green lines, respectively) provided an estimation of the diameter of the wire (180 mm) and an alternative measurement of the diameter of the laser focal spot (about 380 mm). Furthermore, the measurement also allowed to verify the good alignment of the sensor TP_T .

By considering the area of the laser spot, as measured using the beam analyser (Figure 2), and the FoV area, as derived from FWHMs of the curves of Figure 3, the areal ratio to be used in equation 2 was $R_A=0.14$.

1.2.3 Results and interpretation

As mentioned above, various material samples were formerly investigated. The measurement of their emissivity according to the direct (e_T) and indirect (e_R) method, respectively are listed in Table 1, along with some related literature data (e_{ref}).

Material	e_T	$e_{\square}=I-R$	e_{ref}
Al, polished	0.04	0.04	0.04-0.06 [23]
Cu, burnished	0.05	0.05	0.07 [23]
Pb, shiny	0.07	0.13	0.08 [23]
Fe, unoxidized	0.1	0.05	0.05 [24]
AISI 316	0.17	0.16	0.14 [25]
Pb, rough	0.51	0.49	0.43 [24]
Cu, oxidized	0.71	0.70	0.60-0.70 [23]
Plywood	0.76	0.88	0.83 [26]
Gypsum	0.87	0.92	0.80-0.90 [23]
Glass, smooth	0.88	0.89	0.92-0.94 [24]
White marble	0.89	0.93	0.95 [24]
White paper	0.90	0.91	0.70-0.90 [23]
Black tape	0.92	0.93	0.90 [27]
Limestone	0.97	0.97	0.88-0.95 [24]

Table 1. Emissivity of various material samples, as measured according to the direct (e_T) and indirect (e_R) method, respectively, and corresponding literature data (e_{ref}).

As shown, an overall satisfactory agreement was achieved, which evidenced, in particular, the reliability of the indirect method using the integrating sphere shown in the inset of Figure 1. This is also clearly evidenced in Figure 4, showing the congruence with the physical relation between reflectance and emissivity in the approximation of opaque materials. Thus, such a comparison demonstrated the functionality and reliability of the setup of Figure 1 and of the associated reflectance method for the samples listed in Table 1.

As mentioned above, one of the main potential applications of the present innovative thermally controlled Raman probe concerns the field of archaeometry and conservation of cultural heritage. Thus, following the assessment of the effectiveness of the present thermal monitoring approach, the novel probe (Figure 1) was tested on a set of pigments in linseed oil binder applied on glass slides. The samples and the corresponding emissivity values, as measured using the direct thermal method (e_T) and with the new setup (e_{\square}), are reported in Table 2.

Figure 4. Plot comparing the (R , e_T) data of Table 1 and the expected linear dependence $R=1-e$.

Pigment	e_T	$e_R=1-R$
Cinnabar	0.55	0.69
Massicot	0.63	0.53
Pb red	0.67	0.76
Cd yellow	0.79	0.90
Co blue	0.80	0.83
Cr green	0.84	0.86
Ti white	0.87	0.90
Zn white	0.84	0.88
Paint layer		
Linseed oil	0.88	0.96
Cinnabar	0.85	0.83
Pb red	0.93	0.93
Cd yellow	0.87	0.91
Co blue	0.92	0.97
Cr green	0.90	0.96
Ti white	0.90	0.96
Zn white	0.89	0.95

Table 2. Emissivity of pigments (powder) and paint layers with linseed oil binder using the direct (e_T) and indirect ($e_R=1-R$) method, respectively.

The comparison confirmed the congruence between the two independent methods, with maximum differences of about 0.1 for pigment and a bit less for paint layers. The emissivity of the painted samples was generally higher than that of the corresponding pigment because of the higher emissivity of the linseed oil matrix. The pigment: binder ratio was 65wt%:35wt%, which corresponds to a pigment volume concentration fraction of 17-30% for the actual pigments. Thus a certain variation is expected in practical cases of interest, due to the different ratio between pigment and binder, as well as to the presence of two or more pigments in the paint mix.

The emissivity measured for the various samples was used to recalibrate the temperature sensor TP_T and implement the temperature control during Raman spectroscopy. As an example, in Figure 5, we report the case of cinnabar, a red pigment with high photothermal instability. Figure 5a displays the Raman spectra achieved at eight different laser powers with an integration time of 12 s and Figure 5b shows the respective temperature profiles.

Figure 5. Raman spectra (a) obtained for cinnabar powder at different laser power and corresponding temperature temporal profiles (b). In the inset, the trend of temperature measured at 11.6 s as function of the laser power.

The Raman signal gradually increased up to 86 mW (yellow line), whereas above this power, drastically decreased (dark yellow line). Besides the previous spectral feature, even a significant variation in the temperature temporal profile was observed at laser power higher than 86 mW. In particular, at 88 mW, the slope of the temperature profile changed drastically at 11 s, and 1 s later it increased from about 200 °C to about 325 °C. In the inset of Figure 5b, the temperature recorded at 11.6 s as a function of the laser power is reported. As shown, the linear increasing trend had an abrupt change of slope at 86 mW (160 °C). This variation was associated with the darkening of the irradiated area. According to the literature, such a darkening effect and associated metallic appearance were attributed to a photothermal reduction effect occurring at the vaporization of mercury (357 °C). The corresponding experimental critical temperature was lower than the nominal one likely because of the fast rise, which cannot be detected by the sensor (response time of 1.3 s) and of the associated material removal, which produce a cooling effect. Nevertheless, the present thermal sensing line allowed to determine quite precisely the alteration threshold, as well as to foresee the damage through the lack of saturation of the temperature profile. Thus, in all the cases the maximum temperature of the irradiated sample surface along with a maximum slope of the temperature temporal profile, after its former leading edge, can represent two control parameters that can be suitably set through the dedicated GUI in order to optimize the signal detection and prevent possible alterations.

As highlighted in the literature, the alteration intensity strongly depends on the laser spot diameter. For example, we previously found about 600 W/cm² for a spot size of 105 mm, against the present 76 W/cm² for about 380 mm spot diameter. This general behavior should be taken into account along with other features of the laser damage nucleation, which extends beyond the subject of this paper.

Critical temperature and alteration intensities of a paint layer are expected to be significantly lower than those of the inorganic pigments that it contains, because of the thermal sensitivity of the organic components (binder, dye), but the conceptual approach of the thermal control described above remains the same: suitable constrains to the thermal temporal profile can prevent sample alteration.

Figure 6a shows the spectra achieved at different laser emission power on a 10-years aged paint sample prepared with cinnabar in linseed oil on gypsum primed wooden panel. Raman spectra were achieved with an integration time of 12 s (100 ms, 120 averages). In Figure 6b the respective temperature profiles are reported. The temperature rise induced by the laser

irradiation increased linearly with the laser power (see the inset) and the sample didn't show any alteration. This can be attributed to the higher optical penetration depth of the paint film with respect to the pure pigment.

Figure 6. Cinnabar in linseed oil paint layer: a) Raman spectra (exc. wav. 785nm) achieved with 12 s integration time at different laser power; b) corresponding temperature profiles and temperature dependence on power at 11.6 s (inset).

A further application of the present innovative probe was carried out on Prussian blue, which is another known photothermally sensitive pigment. It is an iron (III) hexacyanoferrate (II) complex and its colour is correlated with the iron (II) and iron (III) charge transfer via a cyano group.

Figure 7. Prussian blue in linseed oil paint film: a) smoothed Raman spectra collected with a single scan and integration time of 65 s; b) associated temperature profiles. The emissivity value measured in situ was 0.97.

Figure 7 shows the dependence of the Raman spectrum (integration time of 65 s) and associated temperature profile on laser power of Prussian blue in linseed oil paint film. No any alteration was observed over the indicated power range (27-103 mW). Besides band and background amplitude variations increasing red shift of the CN stretching band ($\approx 2150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was observed at increasing laser power. This is clearly observable in the detail of Figure 8a showing the baseline subtracted spectra between $2105\text{-}2180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. A Gaussian fit of the mentioned band was executed in order to extract its central wavenumber for each spectrum. A red shifts of 4 cm^{-1} was observed when changing the irradiation power from 27 mW to 103

mW laser power. Such an effect was previously reported and it was attributed to the reduction of Fe (III) to Fe (II) in absence of charge transfer process. Here, we correlate it to the laser induced temperature rise (Figure 8b).

Figure 8. a) Spectral detail of the CN stretching band ($\approx 2150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at increasing power. b) Corresponding variation of the central wavenumber and temperature after 60 s laser irradiation.

In order to validate the novel probe in real operative conditions tests were carried out on a modern oil painting on canvas. It was a female portrait by anonymous, which was overpainted and partially uncovered in the past at its bottom part (Figure 9). The original painting (below the dotted line) was extensively overpainted using green, yellow, and brown hue paint. This artwork was previously analyzed using optical and SEM-EDX microscopy and uncovering laser ablation tests were carried out.

Figure 9. Overpainted modern oil painting by anonymous.

For the present purposes, the Raman spectra along with emissivity and temperature measurements were achieved on the reddish dress (sites A and B) and the green overpaint (site C). After some preliminary tests, the laser power was set at 47 mW and the integration time at 25s (500ms, 50 averages) for the site A (Figure 10a) and 22 mW and 80s (200ms, 400 averages) for site B (Figure 10b). The intensity of the latter measurement was reduced since the temperature induced by the former has to be considered too high for safeguarding the oil binder. The emissivity was measured in situ and resulted to be 0.91 for site A and 0.87 for site B. Site A (orange zone) shows the red lead characteristic peaks ($222, 306, 386, \text{ and } 541 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and in

site B (red zone) besides these the Raman bands of the quinacridone (1273, 1356, 1382, 1486, and 1576 cm^{-1}) were also detected.

Figure 10. Raman spectra (exc. wav. 785nm) of light red (a, orange line) and red (b, wine line) shaded zones (sites A and B, respectively) using 47 mW (a) and 22 mW (b), respectively. Blue wavenumbers correspond to red lead bands while black wavenumbers highlight the quinacridone bands. The insets show the corresponding temperature profiles, based on measured emissivity of 0.91 (a) and 0.87 (b), respectively.

The spectra and temperature rise of the green overpaint (site C) were finally measured using a laser power of 22 mW (Figure 11) and an integration time of 40s (800 ms, 50 averages). The Raman characteristic bands of the green phthalocyanine were recognized (680, 738, 1208, 1286, and 1532 cm^{-1}). The Signal/Noise level of this spectrum could be raised up using higher laser power, although the induced temperature rises could not be compatible with such a fully organic site (organic pigment and binder).

Figure 11. a) Figure shows phthalocyanine Raman spectrum collected from the site C using 22 mW. b) Temperature profile based on a measured emissivity of 0.92.

These examples show the monitoring of the temperature allowed to evaluate and then control the level of risk of the measurement. In particular, literature data report the evaporation of VOCs contained in oil matrix represent the early alteration of oil paint, which starts to occur over a large temperature range around 100 °C, according to the specific features. Thus, if this temperature has to be reached in order to get a good spectrum, the time exposure should be limited. The measurements carried out on the painting of Figure 9 involved maximum temperature rises between 75-90 °C, which did not evidence any anomalous behavior, although it would be safer to further limit the heating.

1.2.4 Conclusions and perspectives

Here, we extended the technology and method of the remote temperature control during Raman spectroscopy previously introduced. A novel portable probe was developed allowing to derive the emissivity from reflectance measurement and then to use this parameter to monitor the temperature of the irradiated sample surface during Raman spectroscopy. The effectiveness and reliability of the indirect measurement of the emissivity based on IR reflectance measurement was formerly demonstrated on a variety of material samples including metals, stones, and other, the work focused on pigments and paint layers. The latter were selected as an example application, where the thermal control during Raman spectroscopy can represent the solution of a practical need because of the high photothermal sensitivity of most of the pigments and binders typically encountered in artwork material characterizations. These material systems easily undergo alteration during Raman spectroscopy, which can be prevented by implementing an online temperature control. At the same time, it is evident that the present approach can also be exploited in other fields of application, whenever the knowledge of the temperature during CW laser irradiation can be of interest. One case of particular interest is the study of the dependence of the Raman spectral features on the temperature, such as for example the red shift of Prussian blue discussed above, where the contribution of the laser irradiation should be carefully taken into account and measured.

1.3 Temperature sensing during Raman spectroscopy of lead white films in different purity grades and boundary conditions.

1.3.1 Context and concept

Lead White (LW) is one of the most used pigments in art and cosmetics since ancient times. Due to its popularity several manufacturing methods and products have been crafted along the past in order to meet various needs. In all the cases, the purification can be certainly considered a crucial phase of the pigment preparation, necessary to achieve high-quality products with specific properties, like whiteness, hardness, stability and hiding power.

High-grade (analyte) and low-grade (art pigment) LWs were selected for the present study to investigate the influence of impurities on the photothermal behavior. Furthermore, high-grade lead carbonate (PbCO_3) which can be found in LW in different amounts depending on the production method and lead sulfate (PbSO_4), possibly present as degradation product, were investigated. Formulated paints were applied on glass slides and primed canvas to study the influence of the substrate on the photothermal behavior. Moreover, LW paint film alone devoid of substrate was also investigated.

Thorough optical, compositional, and microstructural characterizations of the samples were carried out. Optical penetration depths were measured in order to quantify the energy coupling to the paint films, which determines the intensity of the Raman signal. Trace elements of low-grade samples were quantified using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OEM) while pigment morphology (particle size and shape), presence of inclusions and layer structures were examined using Scanning Electron Microscopy-Energy Dispersive X-Ray spectrometry (SEM-EDX). Material properties achieved provided the interpretative basis for explaining the significant differences among the photothermal behaviors of the different samples upon CW Nd:YAG(1064nm) laser irradiation.

A high-efficiency Raman system equipped with a thermal control line was used for measuring laser induced heating and detecting associated changes of the molecular spectra. The parameterization of the observed phenomena allowed understanding the origin of the different photothermal coupling and to achieve clear relations between the latter and the measured spectra, which can be exploited in Raman spectroscopy of LW-based paint films in order to prevent alterations and derive additional compositional information.

1.3.2 Monitoring protocol

Paint film preparation

Film-forming solutions were prepared using certified analytes (high-grade of purity) and commercial pigment powders (low grade of purity) listed in Table 1. Analytes refer to high-purity products, which meet or exceed stringent ACS specifications. For completeness, trace metal analyses of analytes as indicated by the product supplier are reported.

Sample	Compound	Producer	Company product Specifications
High-Grades			

LCB ₁	Lead(II) Carbonate, Basic	Alfa-Aesar	Insoluble matter $\leq 0.02\%$, Cl 0.002%, Nitrate and nitrite (limit about 0.005%), K 0.02%, Na 0.05%, Cd 0.002%, Ca 0.01%, Fe 0.005%, Zn 0.003%
LCB ₂		Fluka	Pb content $> 77\%$, in water soluble matter mx. 0.5 %, Fe 0.005%, Cu 0.005%, Zn 0.005%, Cl 0.003%
LCB ₃		Carlo Erba	Pb content $> 77\%$, in water soluble matter mx. 0.5 %, Fe 0.005%, Cu 0.005%, Zn 0.005%, Cl 0.003%
LC	Lead(II) Carbonate	Acros Organics	Insoluble matter $\leq 0.02\%$, Cl 0.002%, Cd 0.002 %, Ca 0.01%, Fe 0.005%, K 0.02%, Na 0.05%, Zn 0.003%
LS	Lead(II) Sulfate	Acros Organics	crystalline powder conformed $> 98.5\%$
Sample	Compound	Producer	Results of ICP-OES analysis
Low-Grades			
LW ₁	Lead(II) Carbonate, Basic	Bizzarri	Cd $< 0.002\%$, Cu 0.002%, Fe 0.025%, K 0.015%, Na 0.03%, Zn 0.003%
LW ₂		Zecchi	Cd $< 0.002\%$, Cu 0.004%, Fe 0.015%, K 0.006%, Na 0.025%, Zn 0.01%

Table 1 List of analytes (High-Grade of purity)/commercial (Low-Grade of purity) Pb-based powders used for film preparation and corresponding product specs and ICP-OES results.

LW₁ and LW₂, were commercial pigments mostly composed of basic lead carbonate and produced according to ancient recipes. They exhibit higher contents of trace metals than the analytes, as assessed using ICP-OES (Optima 2000 DV, PerkinElmer) (Table 1). In particular, it is worth noting that concentrations of Fe were 3-5 times higher than those recommended by ACS specs.

To prepare film-forming solutions, each Pb powder was dispersed in a medium molecular weight (M.W. 57,000-66,000) Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) supplied by Alfa Aesar. This polymeric matrix was chosen for its high thermal stability (T_g 75-80°C, T_m ~218 °C) and transparency in the spectral region of interest. The PVA solution was prepared by dispersing 10 % w/v of the polymer in distilled water under continuous stirring for 1 h at 90°C. After completing the solubilization, PVA solution was left cooling down at room temperature, sonicated for 15 min. to remove air bubbles and then poured into a glass vial. Afterwards, each Pb-based powder was manually ground and blended to the PVA solution in a 75/25 w/w pigment to binder ratio, which corresponds to a pigment volume concentration of approximately 30%. The PVA blends were applied on three different substrates: glass slides, silicone rubber molds and a commercial pre-primed canvas. Silicone rubber molds were used as hydrophobic surface to prepare free standing (no-substrate) PVA blend films as the latter once dried could be easily peeled off. The ground layer of the canvas was an ad-mixture of chalk (calcium carbonate, CaCO₃) and gypsum (calcium sulfate, CaSO₄) in a proteinaceous binder. Comparable film thicknesses were obtained using a manual film applicator. The actual film thickness was measured in cross-section by averaging ten readings under OM. The relative error was of the order of 10%. Once applied on the different substrates PVA blend films were left to dry in a ventilated oven overnight at 50 °C and then stored to lab conditions. For the sake of comparison, the same lead powders listed in Table 1 were gently flattened using a spatula.

Thermally-controlled NIR Raman spectroscopy

The Raman probe used consists of an ultra-narrow linewidth diode pumped CW Nd:YAG (1064 nm) laser excitation and optical set-up including a long-pass filter, off-axis parabolic

mirrors and a notch filter. It offers higher sensitivity and lower backgrounds than other typical optical configurations. A high-throughput spectrometer with a deep-cooled (-55°C) InGaAs array detector and a monochromator covering spectral range between $165\text{-}1825\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a spectral resolution $8\text{-}10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (SuperGamut by BaySpec) were used for Raman signal detection. More detailed technical information about instrument can be found elsewhere.^{15,31}

Experiments were performed in air at room temperature and the measuring parameters were 330 mW laser excitation power, $450\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ spot size, 25 s integration time. The corresponding total radiant exposure released to the target was around 5.2 kJ/cm^2 (irradiance: 207 W/cm^2). To account for inhomogeneity three measurements at different points of the sample surface were recorded. Precision in focusing and reproducibility were provided by automated positioning of the Raman probe over each sample.³³ In the following, spectra are shown without smoothing or baseline fitting.

Temperature during Raman acquisition was measured using a thermopile ($5\text{-}13\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) with an active area of about $750 \times 750\text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$, angle of view of about 10° , 25 ms sampling period and absolute accuracy at 25°C of 0.5°C . To convert the IR signal detected to temperature the emissivity was set to 0.9, as measured for lead carbonate at 52°C .³⁴ Custom-designed LabVIEW software was used for controlling hardware components and performing data processing, which also provide real time temperature rise, $\Delta T(t)$, measurements.

1.3.3 Results and interpretation

Optical and microstructural characterization

Optical properties measured on freestanding PVA films are listed in Table 3. Basically, the latter were highly diffusive as μ_s values were orders of magnitude larger than μ_a . Among pure lead basic carbonates, PVA-LCB₂ figured out the highest μ_s values (1500 cm^{-1}), with a surface reflectivity over 95%, whereas PVA-LC around 1100 cm^{-1} . Diversely, $\mu_s = 630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was derived for PVA-LS. The angular distribution of scattered laser intensity fitted very well with the cosine law of a Lambertian diffuser and no specular reflection components were observed. As shown in Table 3, μ_s of low-purity grade PVA-LW films were lower than those of high-purity grade PVA-LCB films, while μ_a was about five times greater. Thus, the differences in the measured δ was certainly ascribable to the concentration of Fe impurities (see Table 2), as evidenced by ICP-OES analysis.

PVA film	Diffuse reflectance, $R(\%)$	Diffuse transmittance, $T(\%)$	Film thickness ^a , $l\text{ }(\mu\text{m})$	Absorption coefficient, $\mu_a\text{ }(\text{cm}^{-1})$	Scattering coefficient, $\mu_s\text{ }(\text{cm}^{-1})$	Effective optical penetration depth, $\delta_{\text{eff}}\text{ }(\mu\text{m})$
High-purity grade						
PVA-LCB ₁	90.5 ± 1.6	8.8 ± 0.3	150	0.23	900	395
PVA-LCB ₂	95.5 ± 1.3	3.8 ± 0.3	200	0.18	1500	340
PVA-LCB ₃	92.2 ± 2.5	7.2 ± 0.2	150	0.20	1100	385
PVA-LC	89.1 ± 1.7	10.5 ± 1.1	100	0.20	1120	384
PVA-LS	87.4 ± 2.2	12.2 ± 0.4	150	0.20	630	510
Low-purity grade						

PVA-LW ₁	88.2 ±1.4	8.0 ±0.5	200	1.09	640	225
PVA-LW ₂	87.3 ±1.5	8.2 ±0.5	250	1.06	500	250

Table 2. 1064 nm-optical properties of prepared PVA films.

^aUncertainty of film thickness are within 10%.

Powder morphology (size and shape), which can influence laser-material interaction (e.g. scattering, absorption, laser-induced heating and Raman signal intensity) was assessed by UHR-SEM. Microstructures and PSDs of one sample for each category of Pb-compounds listed in Table 1 are displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1 UHR-SE-SEM images and PSD analysis of the four main categories of PVA-pigment blends formulated; PVA-LCB₃ a), PVA-LW₁ b), PVA-LC c), and PVA-LS d).

From this analysis it resulted that the average particle size of all the powders used in this study ranged between 0.5 μm of the finest up to 2.5 μm of the coarsest, though the full width at half maximum (FWHM) varied appreciably among different compounds. From the optical standpoint, it was observed that diffuse reflectance, R , of pigmented layers with larger PSD ($0.8 < x_c < 5 \mu\text{m}$), reached saturation values at paint layer thicknesses of about 150 μm, whereas for lower PSD ($0.25 < x_c < 0.75 \mu\text{m}$) reflectance saturated at sample thicknesses less than 100 μm.

Concerning particle shape, high- and low-purity grades of LCB, which are represented in Figure 1 by PVA-LCB₃ and PVA-LW₁ films, were mainly constituted of roundish and hexagonal platelets with sizes lower than 1 μm.^{35,36} Looking at PSDs of Figs. 1a and 1b it is easily appreciable that basic lead carbonate compounds differed strongly each other, suggesting different synthesis conditions and post-synthesis processes for their production. Among lead basic carbonates, PVA-LCB₃ with an average particle diameter of $2.4 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ was the coarsest powder followed by PVA-LCB₂, PVA-LCB₁ and PVA-LW₁. As shown by PSD of Figure 1b, the average particle size of the latter was estimated as $0.955 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{m}$. PVA-LC revealed to be the most finely distributed with average particle size of $0.5 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{m}$. LC was formed by elongated

acicular-shaped particles and small platelets. Last, PVA-LS film (Figure1d) was made of coarsely-sized crystallites of lead(II) sulfate, orthorhombic, with an average particle size of $2.27 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{m}$.

Impurities in low-purity grade LWs films were characterized through OM and BSE-EDX analysis. This required major efforts due to a limited capacity of probing the depths in high-Z materials (i.e. few microns) as well as the presence of trace elements percentages lower than the detection limit of BSE-EDX analysis. Therefore, impurities were first observed under OM, selected and then analyzed by SEM. Figure 2 shows localized inclusions in PVA-LW₁ films and the results of BSE-EDX mapping analysis. From the OM transverse section red colored spots were clearly visible.

In general, the inclusions were variably sized ranging from sub-micron size particles up to agglomerates with maximum sizes of $30 \mu\text{m}$, thus ascribable to contaminants. BSE-EDX elemental mapping revealed the nature of such inclusions which resulted Fe_xO_x , most likely hematite. Furthermore, as regards pigment powders (LW₁ and LW₂) BSE-EDX analysis confirmed a Pb content of about 70 wt % and the presence of other minor impurities of Cu, Zn and Sn.

Figure 2. OM Cross-section showing red-colored inclusions in $100 \mu\text{m}$ thick PVA-LW₁ film. Smaller images refer to: a) OM detail of a red inclusion, b) BSE-SEM image; c-d-e-f-g) BSE-EDX maps show the elemental distribution of Pb, O, Fe, C and Cu, respectively. BSE image scale bar is $10 \mu\text{m}$.

Raman characterizations

Freely suspended paint films: the effect of pigment purity grade

Raman spectra of no-substrate LW-containing PVA films are displayed in Figure 3. Bands were assigned on the basis of the literature. Comparing the spectra of paint films with those of the powders alone (see Figure S1), neither Raman bands of the PVA matrix nor newly-generated peaks from pigment-PVA interactions were detected. Spectra of samples with high-purity grade analytes (LCB₁, LCB₂, LCB₃, LC and LS) were characterized by low and flat baselines. The ν_1 symmetric stretching modes were observed at 1053 cm^{-1} for basic lead carbonate, at 1056 cm^{-1} for lead carbonate, and at 980 cm^{-1} for lead sulfate (see Figure 6c).

Among LCB samples (Figure 3a-c), the most relevant spectral differences were observed in the bands between 1300 and 1500 cm^{-1} ascribable to ν_3 (*ca.* 1370 cm^{-1}) and B_{2g} (*ca.* 1475 cm^{-1}) modes. In contrast to PVA-LCB₂ and PVA-LCB₃, showing a unique band peaked at *ca.* 1370 cm^{-1} with very weak shoulders at 1414 and 1476 cm^{-1} , PVA-LCB₁ sample featured well discernable peaks at 1370 and 1476 cm^{-1} .³⁹ The latter along with those at *ca.* 218 and 840 cm^{-1} , which were missing or almost negligible in PVA-LCB₂ and PVA-LCB₃, allowed discriminating between hydrocerussite and cerussite phases, especially comparing with the spectrum of PVA-LC (Figure 3d). The very weak band at 838 cm^{-1} was assigned to ν_2 carbonate vibration in cerussite. Moreover, PVA-LCB samples showed a weak and broad band at 415-420 cm^{-1} , which was absent in the PVA-LC spectrum and was attributed to Pb-O modes.

Figure 3 Raman spectra of freely suspended (no-substrate) paint films containing high-purity grade (a-d) and low-purity grade (e-f) LWs. Spectra were recorded at 207 W/cm^2 laser intensity (25 s integration time).

Raman spectra of low-purity grade PVA-LW₁ and PVA-LW₂ showed relevant differences with respect to high-purity grade films. The most prominent were a noticeable increase of background levels associated with a marked decrease in spectral intensity. The slightly lower background and intensity of PVA-LW₂ with respect to PVA-LW₁ was likely due to different amounts of trace elements and Fe inclusions. ICP-OES analysis revealed about 0.025% and 0.015% of Fe ions in LW₁ and LW₂ pigment powders, respectively. However, the high SNR (signal-to-noise ratio) allowed detecting all the fundamental vibration modes of basic lead carbonate and related minor features. It is worth noting that the ν_3 mode at *ca.* 1370 cm^{-1} in

PVA-LW₁ and PVA-LW₂ was rather similar to that of PVA-LCB₂ and PVA-LCB₃, thus corroborating what above described and suggesting a low content of cerussite phases.

Figure 4. Temperature temporal profiles (ΔT) during Raman measurements showing laser-induced heating (207 W/cm^2 , 25 s integration time) of no-substrate LW-containing PVA films. High- versus low-purity grades (a) and detail of measured temperatures for high-purity grades (b).

As regard laser-induced heating, temperature profiles during Raman measurements of Figure 3 are displayed in Figure 4. Despite these temporal behaviors recall in mind the well-known root square dependence of the surface temperature of one-dimensional approximation of the heat equation with a top hat energy release, it should be taken into account that the present dissipation process cannot be easily modelled. It includes the initial heating of the absorption volume, thermal conduction within the film, and air convective motions at the film-air interfaces, which determine the cooling regime and the maximum temperature rise.

Here, ΔT rises of 80°C and 76°C were measured for PVA-LW₁ and PVA-LW₂, respectively. In contrast, high-purity grade paint films showed significantly lower ΔT rises, which were similar among each other (Figure 4b). In fact, temperature variations ranged between 14 and 18 °C, without exhibiting a dependence on the on PSD, since the sample thicknesses were larger than 150 μm , which produced the saturation of the reflectance. Conversely, the small heating differences observed in Figure 4b are ascribable to the specific lead compounds and film defects (i.e. cratering, air bubbles, cracks, agglomerates, contaminants).^{41–43}

Similar photothermal behaviors as those of Figure 4 were also measured for gently pressed pigment powders although temperature rises were slightly higher (Figure S1).

For low-purity grade LW-based films, the dependence of temperature and Raman scattering on the sample thickness was also investigated. Raman spectra displayed in Figure 5a highlighted a saturating increase of the background levels and spectral intensity with layer thickness. This trend can be better appreciated in Figure 5b showing the intensity of the Raman band ascribable to the $\nu_1(\text{CO}_3)$ mode at 1053 cm^{-1} , which did not exhibit any broadening or shifting effects. The plot in the inset of Figure 5b reports the corresponding Raman counts and ΔT_{max} , as measured by online monitoring (Figure 5c). As shown, signal and temperature saturated around 250 μm , which is congruent with the optical penetration depth measured ($\delta=225 \mu\text{m}$, see Table 3).

Figure 5 Raman spectra (a, b) and sample heating (ΔT) (c) of no-substrate PVA-LW₁ sample. The inset (b) shows also the trend of Raman counts of the band at 1053 cm^{-1} and ΔT as a function of the layer thickness, l .

At the same time, Figure 5c suggests different thermal regimes were associated with the different thicknesses. Thinner samples experienced faster saturation of the temperature rise, which is mainly attributable to the lateral/radial thermal conduction. Conversely, a slower saturation was measured for thicker samples, although the behavior remained faster than the one foreseen for the well-known planar approximation ($\Delta T \propto \sqrt{t}$) because of the mentioned lateral propagation of the thermal wave, while transport phenomena only provide a minimal contribution at the highest temperatures. As a matter of fact, the behavior of the sample with $l=400 \mu\text{m}$ was the closest one to the mentioned approximation.

The experimentation also pointed out that Raman counts of high-purity grade films increased as the surface reflection (i.e. elastic scattering) decreases (higher energy coupling to the target) (see Figure S2). Conversely this was not true for low-purity grade films PVA-LW₁ and PVA-LW₂ whose higher absorbances and absorption coefficients (about five times greater, Table 3) favored the thermal dissipation channel. Such a behavior can be attributed to hematite (Fe_2O_3) impurities (150-250 ppm, Table 1), whose absorption coefficient at 1064 nm is of the order of 10^2 - 10^3 cm^{-1} depending on particle sizes. Thus, considerably higher temperatures (3-5 time higher), weaker Raman bands, and higher background were recorded for no-substrate low-

purity grades films in comparison to high-purity grades. The attenuation of the signal can be interpreted as a consequence of the temperature rise, conversely, the increasing of the continuum spectral component is not attributable to the blackbody emission, which is decidedly negligible within the present wavelength range (*ca.* 1080-1300 nm) and low heating levels. We verified the presence of the high background was strictly associated with the laser irradiation rather than to the material heating, which suggest to interpret the phenomenon as a luminescence effect.

According to the literature, fine-particles of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ produce intense (10 times higher than Raman signal) broad NIR luminescence bands (100-2000 cm^{-1}) when excited at 1064 nm, which was tentatively attributed to the d-d transition ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}$. This interpretation is congruent with assessment tests carried out on $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ analyte with our instrumentation, which pointed out a maximum emission at about 8060 cm^{-1} (Raman shift 1335 cm^{-1}) (see Figure S3), resembling very well the reported luminescence emission band of unannealed hematite particles.⁴⁵ Increasing laser power from 35 to 100 mW produced a corresponding luminescence increase around twenty-five times and the band peak shifted to 7800 cm^{-1} (Raman shift 1600 cm^{-1}), as reported for commercial hematite after annealing at 1000 °C.

Influence of the substrate

Raman spectra and ΔT of standalone paint films were compared with those achieved for the same films applied on glass slides and primed canvas.

Figure 6 Substrate-induced effect on Raman scattering and sample heating (ΔT) of high-purity grade paint films. Thicknesses are below the optical penetration depths.

PVA films on glass slides did not exhibit any relevant Raman or luminescence signal. Conversely, primed canvas evidenced the bands of CaSO_4 at 415, 618, 1004 cm^{-1} and of CaCO_3 at 283, 713, 1087, 1438 cm^{-1}) superimposed to broad luminescence bands (Figure 6a).The

associated temperature rise profile revealed heating above 50 °C, which kept on rising over 25 s integration time.

High-purity grade PVA-LC (Figure 6b), PVA-LS (Figure 6c) and PVA-LCB₁ (Figure 6d) films cast on canvas showed appreciably higher background which reasonably arose from the evidenced luminescence of the underlying primed substrate. It is noteworthy that a very weak peak at 1087 cm⁻¹, ascribable to the underlying CaCO₃ layer, was barely observed (Figure 6b-d). From the thermal standpoint, the mentioned films on primed canvas underwent the highest ΔT , which was reasonably due to laser-induced heating of the latter, then followed by no-substrate and glass-substrate films. The higher thermal conductivity of the latter produced a more effective cooling than in air. In contrast, high-purity grade PVA-LCB₂ (Figure 6e) and PVA-LCB₃ (Figure 6f) did not show neither remarkable spectral changes nor effects from underlying substrates. Accordingly, ΔT variations were less pronounced than those on primed canvas and air suspended.

Local temperatures for PVA-LCB₁ and PVA-LS were slightly higher due to lower surface reflectivity, thus transmitted laser energy produced a moderate heating of the primed canvas substrate. As regards films with higher reflectivity (PVA-LCB₂, R=95% and PVA-LCB₃, R=95%) the influence of the primed canvas on the spectrum became negligible. Likewise, local heating was relatively limited and comparable to that of free boundary films. In any case, at the present irradiance (207 W/cm²) local temperature increases of high-purity grades films remained confined within safe ranges for Raman analysis.

For both low-purity grade paint films (PVA-LW_{1,2}) with thicknesses lower or slightly larger than the optical penetration depth, respectively, the highest temperatures during Raman spectroscopy were induced in the most thermally insulated condition (black curves in Figure 7), whereas canvas and glass substrates significantly limited the temperature rises. According to the dependence showed in Figure 5, laser irradiation heated the thicker sample (Figure 7b) more than the thinner one (Figure 7a). Congruently, no spectral features from the underlying layers were observed, suggesting that photons propagation was mostly confined within the LW paint layer.

Figure 6. Effect of substrate on the Raman spectral features and on sample heating of low-purity grade PVA-LW₁ films for thicknesses (l) of 150 μm (a) and of 250 μm (b).

1.3.4 Conclusion and perspectives

This work demonstrates that Raman spectroscopy of white lead compounds and associated laser heating effects are strictly determined by their purity grade. Surprisingly, a few ppm of iron oxide particles in commercial lead whites pigment produce a significant reduction of Raman signal, temperature rise, and background emission, which are not observed in high-purity grade lead carbonates and sulphate. These pronounced differences are attributable to the high optical absorption of iron oxide inclusions, which subtracts energy to Raman excitation. Absorbed energy is dissipated through the thermal and photoluminescence channels. The data reported provide evidence laser heating and Raman signal of a diffusing paint film depend on its thickness and both maximize when the latter approaches the optical penetration depth. Heating represents an important side effect of Raman spectroscopy and it must be taken carefully into account in order to prevent undesired alterations of the paint film under study, such as photothermal phase change and decomposition of its components. The data also show that detached paint layers represent the most harmful situation since such a thermal insulation condition can easily produce significant overheating phenomena. Finally, attention should be paid whenever investigating paintings on canvas in discriminating spectral contributions and temperature rise associated to the latter.

The present interpretations were made possible by the availability of online temperature measurement, which proved to be an essential tool for supporting correct interpretations of the data and provide objective information on the purity of the pigment. Correlating thermal and spectroscopic information constitutes a precious added-value, which can also be exploited in defining conservation treatments, such as in particular those based on laser ablation.

1.4 Quantitative spectroscopic characterization of laser-induced effects on oil paint films

1.4.1 Context and concept

The present work was aimed to optimize an analytical assessment protocol based on reflectance FTIR and μ -Raman spectroscopies in order to characterize and compare undesired effects of laser treatments (213, 266, and 2940 nm) of oil paintings. The corresponding pros and cons have been thoroughly investigated on a variety of varnish films, whereas little has been reported on the effects of direct laser radiation of unvarnished oil paint layers at the aforementioned lasers wavelengths. This is the first work where laser-induced effects at 213, 266 and 2940 nm of unvarnished oil paint films have been systematically compared according to a qualitative and quantitative analytical assessment. For this purpose, the main objectives were: i) to determine the laser damage thresholds of single-layer unvarnished oil paint films; ii) to evaluate by FTIR and μ -Raman the laser-induced changes; iii) to study the dependence of laser-induced changes on the amount of oil binder in the paint films; iv) to discuss advantages and disadvantages of selected laser treatments in terms of potential harmfulness, irradiation procedure, ablation efficiency, practical applicability and the degree of self-termination.

Material and methods

Samples

Background of paint formulations

A quantitative measure of the level of pigmentation in paint is the pigment volume concentration (PVC):

$$PVC = V_p / (V_p + V_b)$$

where V_p is the volume of the pigment, calculated using the weighted amount and the average pigment density, and V_b is the volume of the non-volatile part of the binder in the system. The pigment manufacturer provided the average pigment densities (see **Table 1**, 3.1.2 section). Given that no solvents were used to prepare samples, but only linseed oil, the volatile part of the binder was considered negligible in the PVC calculation.

Another parameter to be taken into account is the Critical Pigment Volume Concentration (CPVC) corresponding to the maximum pigment packing, which can be calculated from oil absorption (OA) as follow:

$$CPVC = \frac{1}{1 + OA \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_b}}$$

where OA is expressed as grams of oil for 100 grams of pigment, ρ_p is the average density of the pigment, and ρ_b is the density of the linseed oil binder (0.935 g/cm³).

The reduced PVC, $\Lambda = PVC/CPVC$, was used to prepare paint films at identical particle packing levels and hence better comparable in laser testing

Below the CPVC ($\Lambda < 1$), a dry coating film is a continuous coating, a composite consisting of pigment particles randomly embedded in a continuously connected polymer matrix. Above the CPVC ($\Lambda \geq 1$), there are void structures in the film due to insufficient

polymer, but the pigment particles can still be thought of as being continuously connected. In this condition there is insufficient binder to cover the pigment surface and the pigment absorbs a significant amount of the polymer.

Sample preparation

The pigments listed in **Table 1** were selected for paint mock-ups preparation. In particular, lead white, cinnabar and chrome yellow were chosen for their recognized sensitivity to laser radiation. Oil paint formulations were prepared by grinding dry-pigment powders with cold-pressed linseed oil (Zecchi) over a grinding slab. Based on the background presented above, oil paint films corresponding to $\Lambda = 0.5$ or 1 were prepared, henceforth referred to as glossy and matte paints, respectively (see **Table 1**), according to their visual appearance.

Sample ID	Pigment	Chemical compound	Avg. density (g/cm ³)	Avg. OA (wt/100 wt)	CPV C	Glossy (G)		Matte (M)	
						PVC	Λ	PVC	Λ
LWLO	Lead white	Lead (II) Carbonate, Basic	6.8	18	43.31	21.57	0.5	43.31	1
VRLO	Vermillion red	Mercury Sulfide	8.1	13	47.03	23.3	0.5	47.03	1
CYLO	Chrome yellow	Lead(II) chromate	6.3	20	42.60	21.25	0.5	42.60	1
ZWLO	Zinc white	Zinc oxide	5.5	23	42.50	21.25	0.5	42.50	1
PBLO	Prussian blue	Ferric ferrocyanide	1.8	45	53.58	26.78	0.5	53.58	1
UBLO	Ultramarine blue	Sodium Aluminum Sulfosilicate	2.3	35	53.74	26.63	0.5	53.74	1

Table 3. List of pigments used. All of them were purchased from Zecchi artist shop (Florence, IT) with the exception of chrome yellow, which is an ACS grade (98%) compound from Alfa Aesar. Average pigment density, average Oil Absorption, sample CVPCs calculated according to PVCs and related Λ values for Glossy (G) and Matte (M) paints are reported.

The formulated paints were spread out in controlled thickness onto glass substrates using a bar film applicator. The wet thickness for all paints was 100 μm . The dry thickness is expected to be approximately 80-90 μm .

Drying and artificial ageing

Prepared samples were left to dry at a temperature of 20-25 °C and relative humidity (RH) of 45-50% under low exposure levels (below 200 lx) and constant air ventilation for ~2.5 months.

During the drying time, loss of sheen and gloss due to sinking in/oiling out phenomena was observed according to drying time of the oil-pigment mixtures. For ZWLO, VRLO and

UBLO, the aspect of the dried film did not result as sheen and glossy as for LWLO, CYLO and PBLO. The time needed for the former to film formation was so slow to allow the oil to be absorbed. After 1.5 months curing zinc white did not result completely dried to the touch. As far as it is known, zinc white is a slow-drying pigment that takes longer to be dried throughout. Fast-drying pigments like Prussian blue, chrome yellow and lead white did not show this feature. As a result, the specular component of glossy samples was recognizable to the naked eye.

After 2.5 months-curing, all samples were dry to the touch. In order to simulate the complex reactions taking place during indoor exposure of oil paintings in museums, which comprise processes of aging induced by exposure to light and dark, a two-step artificial aging procedure was applied. First, a dry oven treatment was performed to speed up free fatty acid evaporation (i.e., palmitic and stearic acids) and promote thermally induced oxidative reactions that are involved in the initial phase of the drying process of fresh oil paint. The conditions that were applied are: thermal treatment at 60°C and 12% RH in darkness, with air ventilation, for 120 hours in total. According to Lazzari et al., this thermal treatment can accelerate the natural processes of drying and degradation by approximately 40 times. Following 1 month of dark-storage from the thermal treatment samples become yellowed (refer to **Figure 1-SM** of the Supplementary Material). This was particularly noticeable in the case of LW, which displayed much more pronounced yellowing than ZW. Similarly, the glossy series (with lower PVC content) was more yellowish in color compared to the matte series.

Then, to simulate light-induced photochemical and photooxidative processes, heat darkened samples were exposed to 600W LED Flood Light (1000W Halogen Equivalent) with 6000K Daylight White and constant air ventilation. 14 hr light/dark cycles were repeated for 20 days (total exposure 280 hr). Average exposure conditions at the target during light/dark cycles were: temperature of 30°C ±3.7, RH of 39.4% ±7 and a light flux of 5±1.5 klux. As expected, samples started bleaching markedly since the first hours of exposure, and the phenomenon was evident for LWLO and ZWLO samples (**Figure 1-SM**). LWLO took longer times than ZWLO to recover its whiteness. CYLO and VRLO resulted instead slightly darker following LED exposure, remarking their higher photosensitivity.

1.4.2 Monitoring protocol

Laser irradiation tests

The 4th (266 nm) and the 5th (213 nm) harmonics of a Q-Switched (15 ns) Nd:YAG laser, and a Free-Running (160 μs pulses) Er:YAG laser emitting at 2940 nm were used for the experimentation. Single-pulse laser-induced damage threshold (F_{th}) was determined by measuring the minimum incident laser fluence, F , at which the occurrence of damage was observed through Optical Microscopy (OM) according to a well-established procedure [36]. For Er:YAG tests, laser-induced effects included surface discoloration (e.g. yellowing or darkening) and micromorphological changes (e.g. cratering effects). OM was carried out under Darkfield (DF) using a Nikon Eclipse L150 microscope, 10× and 20× objective and a Nikon D80 DSLR camera. For UV tests, the emission onset of gaseous by-products was also monitored using a CCD camera positioned sideways to the irradiation spot. Generally, in the case of ns UV laser irradiation, ejection of gaseous products is an indicator of ablation, whereas at 2940 nm is more associated with slow vaporization and melting of the organic component. The precise determination of the laser-spot size was achieved by measuring the mark imprinted by the pulsed laser onto photosensitive material. Here we used ZAP-IT® Paper, suitable for

recording beam characteristics of pulsed laser sources from UV to IR and recommended for pulse width from 1 ns to 30 ms in a fluence range between 5 mJ/cm² and 20 J/cm².

Once determined single-shot fluence thresholds F_{th} for each laser wavelength, test surface areas of 6×6 mm² were processed using motorized XY scanning and pre-defined fluence ratios, F/F_{th} , of 0.75, 1, and 1.25. Five laser pulses/step were released at each laser spot position. A line-wise scanning mode leading to a pulse overlap (PO) of 50% and a line scan of about 25-30% was adopted. Spectroanalytical evaluations upon 213, 266 and 2940 nm laser treatments were performed on areas treated at $F = 1.25 \cdot F_{th}$.

Surface characterization

Diffuse Reflectance-FTIR spectroscopy

Diffuse Reflectance FTIR spectroscopy (DR-FTIR) is a very surface-sensitive technique and was here exploited for assessing the effects induced by the different laser treatments. DR-FTIR spectra were collected using a Cary 630 FTIR (Agilent, USA) spectrophotometer equipped with a DR accessory for non-invasive measurements, Mercury Cadmium Telluride (MCT) detector and ZnSe optics (spectral range: 5100-650 cm⁻¹). The illuminated spot diameter, as measured with an infrared thermo-camera, was approximately 2 mm. Reflectance spectra, $R(1/l)$, transformed in pseudo-absorbance units, $A' = \log(1/R)$, were acquired as a sum of 200 scans with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, which allowed for an excellent S/N throughout the investigated mid-IR spectral range. For the sake of reproducibility, three spectra in different positions were recorded and averaged. A 4 points moving-average smoothing followed by Standard Normal Variate (SNV) normalization was then applied to suppress noise and compare spectra each other.

As regards data processing and spectral interpretations, it should be considered that the collection optics of the DR accessory is designed to reject specular reflection, R_s , of flat surfaces (normal incidence, 0°/0° geometry) and collect part of the off-axis backscattered light, R_v . However, the total reflectivity ($R = R_v + R_s$) collected by the DR accessory may also contain a specular contribution as a result of surface waviness and optical properties of the sample (index of refraction, n , and the coefficient of absorption, k). Notably, R_v may cause variations of band intensities whereas R_s may cause band distortion exhibiting the typical derivative shaped or, in the case of strong absorptions ($k > 1$), inverted or so-called *reststrahlen* bands. Thus, accounting for the different contributions of R_s and R_v , band shapes and peak positions of untreated spectra were considered as control for monitoring laser-induced modifications.

Micro-Raman spectroscopy

Micro-Raman spectroscopy (μ -RS) was carried out using Horiba XploRA confocal microscope coupled with a cooled Si CCD detector (1024 x 256 pixels) and laser excitation lines at 532, 638 and 785 nm. The latter was selected as the best compromise to maintain good signal detection, even at low excitation powers, and reduce fluorescence or quenching phenomena.

The measuring parameters selected were: 100× objective lens, 1200 l/mm grating, and 50 μ m slit. Single acquisition was preferred to avoid quenching phenomena. Afterwards, we measured in all samples the optimal exposure limit within which to carry out safe μ -RS acquisitions, thus preventing chemical-physical and spectral alterations. The applied protocol consisted in exposing the same test site at increasing power by keeping fixed the number of

accumulations. To get a satisfactory S/N, integration times were optimized for each type of pigment composing the paint film (**Table 2, 4.2.2** results section).

After the determination of optimal exposure conditions, μ -RS acquisitions and statistics of untreated and laser-treated areas using the mapping mode (XY map) were carried out. Maps were 4×4 matrices (16 total data points), 80×60 μm^2 analyzed area with XY steps of 26.7 and 20 μm , respectively. A post-processing treatment of the collected maps was performed to highlight and quantify radiation-induced effects. After selecting specific Raman bands of the pigment (**Table 1-SM**), their peak intensity, I_R , and background, I_B (without any correction), were used to calculate the Raman signal to background ratio, $RBR=(I_R - I_B)/I_B$. The latter, which has previously been used to quantitatively determine the average grain size of calcareous rocks from Raman spectra [37], considers and evaluates both fluctuations in background and Raman signals.

Then, the mean difference $RBR_{before} - RBR_{after} (\pm SD)$ over 16 measurements was calculated to get quantitative information on laser-induced modifications. An increase in this difference, observed after the laser irradiation treatment, may imply an increase in the background (I_B), a decrease in the Raman signal intensity (I_R), or both.

1.4.3 Results and interpretation

4.1 Thresholds and laser processing

F_{th} for each laser wavelength was determined and then used for processing areas at pre-defined fluence ratios. Results showed that single-pulse F_{th} follow the order 213 < 266 < 2940 nm, as summarized in **Table 2** and displayed in **Figure 1**. LWLO, VRLO and CYLO films revealed to be less stable than ZWLO, UBLO and PBLO to laser irradiation, with vermilion paint being one of the most sensitive to all the three tested laser wavelengths. Darkening of the pigment at very low fluences was the main alteration effect of LWLO, VRLO, CYLO, whereas whitening or yellowing of the oil matrix was observed on ZWLO, UBLO and PBLO.

Samples	F_{th} (J/cm ²) @213 nm, 15 ns		F_{th} (J/cm ²) @266 nm, 15 ns		F_{th} (J/cm ²) @2940 nm, 160 μs	
LO	0.108 (s)		0.175 (b+s)		2.3 (b+s)	
Oil paints	Glossy	Matte	Glossy	Matte	Glossy	Matte
LW-LO	0.094 (d+g)	0.0576 (d)	0.232 (d)	0.153 (d)	2.30 (d+b)	1.90 (d+b)
VR-LO	0.130 (d+g)	0.0729 (d)	0.107 (d)	0.070 (d)	1.14 (d+b)	0.92 (d+b)
CY-LO	0.144 (d+g)	0.0785 (d)	0.200 (d)	0.193 (d)	1.90 (b)	1.90 (b)
ZW-LO	0.1248 (g)	0.078 (g)	0.796 (d)	0.397 (d)	1.90 (d+b)	2.30 (d+b)
PB-LO	0.979 (g)	0.0806 (g)	0.325 (d)	0.262 (d)	2.45 (d+b)	2.30 (d+b)
UB-LO	0.1209 (g)	0.01209 (g)	0.309 (d)	0.230 (d)	2.30 (d+b)	2.00 (d+b)

b: bubbling, g: gas emission, d: discoloration (i.e. blackening, yellowing or whitening)

Table 4. Single-shot laser-induced damage thresholds (F_{th}) of glossy (G) and matte (M) oil-paint model samples at 213, 266 and 2940 nm. The threshold fluence of the oil film alone, $F_{th, LO}$, was reported for comparison.

Figure 7. Single-shot discoloration thresholds measured on matte and glossy oil paint models upon 213 nm, 266 nm and 2940 nm laser irradiation. Reported F_{th} values are the average of three measurements carried out in different sample locations. The dotted black line corresponds to the threshold fluence of an unpigmented linseed oil layer, $F_{th, LO}$.

Moreover, in most of the tested model samples, clear differences between F_{th} of matte and glossy paint films were observed. Generally, thanks to the lower PVC, F_{th} of gloss paints resulted appreciably higher than those of matte series. At 213 nm F_{th} of glossy paints were very close to $F_{th, LO}$ due to the high laser light absorption of the oil binding medium at this wavelength. Minimal deviations of F_{th} from the value of $F_{th, LO}$ are correlated to the variability of the sample surface, to the pigment-binder interactions and to uncertainty of the threshold measurements. In contrast, at 266 nm F_{th} values were found to be more strongly dependent on the type of pigment than on oil absorption, which at this wavelength is almost negligible. In this case, darkening of the pigment was easily observed at fluences below or comparable to $F_{th, LO}$ for oil paints containing photothermally sensitive pigments (VR, LW and CY). Instead, more stable pigments (UB, PB and ZW) showed whitening or yellowing effects above $F_{th, LO}$, mostly due to ablation and photothermal decomposition of the oil medium. At 2940 nm and longer pulse duration, laser-induced effects appeared markedly different as compared to ns UV lasers. Measured F_{th} values never exceeded $F_{th, LO}$ both for matte and glossy paints. At 2940 nm, laser-induced modifications (i.e. bubbling, yellowing, charring) were mostly associated with thermal damage of the oil binder. The degree of discoloration (yellowing) was more appreciable in white samples (LWLO and ZWLO) and most important, it was more intense for low PVC films. To appreciate these effects, **Figure 2** displays DF-OM images of matte and glossy paint models processed with fluences of $1.25 \cdot F_{th}$.

Figure 8. DF-OM images showing the transition between untreated (in the left half) and laser processed areas (in the right half) at 213, 266 and 2940 nm with $1.25F_{th}$ (see F_{th} values reported in Table 2), 50% pulse overlap, 5 pulses/spot. Scale bar is 200 μm for all images. Outside of the overall view on the right side, there is a closer examination of the laser-induced modifications in LWLO glossy samples (scale bar: 50 μm).

The temporary discoloration of LWLO is noteworthy. In fact, glossy LWLO showed less discoloration compared to matte LWLO. The former regained its natural color appearance within a few days, whereas the latter required more time (about 1 month). The reconversion of lead white back to its initial state has been linked to an oxidation mechanism, and its duration is influenced by the type of binder and the oxygen levels in the surroundings.

Unlike UV lasers, the oil matrix resulted thermally damaged and permanently yellowed upon 2940 nm laser treatment. Moreover, at the microscopic level, the surface morphology of 2940 nm-irradiated samples, particularly for low PVC, appeared more altered and swollen as compared to UV tests (see details in **Figure 2**). Craters and micro-pits ranging from few micrometers up to 100 μm were easily recognizable under OM.

Surface characterization

Diffuse Reflectance-FTIR spectroscopy

Spectral features and position of band maxima in matte and glossy films were affected, to varying degrees, by both specular (R_s) and diffuse (R_v) reflection depending on the type of

pigment and the PVC of the paint film. Spectra acquired on glossy surfaces were characterized by a higher contribution of R_s with marked band distortions. Diversely, matte paints, being rougher surfaces, showed enhanced combination bands and positive broad peaks due to the higher contribution of R_v .

In **Figure 3** main variations of DR-FTIR spectra in the fingerprint region following laser processing at 213, 266 and 2940 nm with $1.25 \cdot F_{th}$ (see F_{th} in **Table 2**) are shown.

The results are reported in the following sample by sample, whilst variations in peak position are plotted in **Figure 4**.

Lead White in Linseed Oil (LWLO)

Regarding the lead white pigment, no relevant changes were appreciated to the broad 3540 cm^{-1} OH stretching mode of the carbonate group (CO_3^{2-}) and to the $\nu_1 + \nu_3$ and/or $2\nu_2 + \nu_4$ (CO_3^{2-}) combination band at $2410\text{--}2430 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, nor between matte and glossy samples, neither after laser irradiation. Instead, the ν_3 antisymmetric CO_3^{2-} stretching region ($1450\text{--}1400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was characterized by derivative shape, which underwent slight modifications in intensity and in peak position upon laser irradiation (**Figure 3**). The ν_1 carbonate symmetric stretching at around 1000 cm^{-1} , inverted by the *reststrahlen* effect, changed as well. At all three laser wavelengths spectral shifts were more prominent in the glossy samples compared to matte. Consistent with these results were the spectral shifts of the oil component. The aliphatic $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and carbonyl $\nu(\text{C=O})$ derivative-like bands featured appreciable shifts after laser irradiation at 266 nm and 2940 nm (see **Figure 3-4**). Particularly appreciable was the shift toward lower wavenumbers after 2940 nm irradiation, which was, for $\nu(\text{C-H})$ absorption, of 8 and 12 cm^{-1} in matte and glossy samples, respectively. This shift, which was also observed for $\nu(\text{C=O})$, is indicative of changes in surface roughness and was more prominent for the sample with high PVC. Basically, $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C=O})$ spectral features resulted less distorted after irradiation at 2940 nm, with band shapes and peak position almost equal to spectra acquired in transmission or in trans-reflectance mode. Moreover, an increase with the laser wavelength in the intensity of aliphatic compounds ($2750\text{--}3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region) was observed.

Figure 9. Qualitative comparison of DR-FTIR spectra of matte (high PVC) and glossy (low PVC) oil paint films after laser irradiation at 213 (green line), 266 (blue line) and 2940 nm (red line) and 1.25 F_{th} . The black line spectrum refers to the control non-irradiated sample. Grey boxes are indicative of the main stretching modes of the pigment forming the oil paint film. Full range FTIR spectra of reference samples (i.e., non-irradiated) are reported in Figure 3-SM.

Vermillion Red in Linseed Oil (VRLO)

In the studied IR range, the vermilion pigment displays no absorption bands. Therefore, only the absorption bands of the oil binder are observable. Band shape and peak position of reference samples, independently of PVC, were only slightly affected by surface scattering distortions. This could be due to the slow-drying nature of the pigment that did not create an alligator-skin effect on the surface. Relative to the laser treatments, combination bands in the NIR region of $\nu_s(\text{CH}_2)+\delta(\text{CH}_2)$ at 4340 and 4260 cm^{-1} proved to be not informative on laser-induced modifications. Moreover, the $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C=O})$ bands showed no significant peak shifting, as displayed in **Figure 4**, neither significant distortions after the laser treatment at the three investigated wavelengths.

Chrome Yellow in Linseed Oil (CYLO)

In the ν_3 chromate asymmetric stretching region ($930\text{--}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) the strong $\nu_3(\text{CrO}_4^{2-})$ absorption band was affected by the *reststrahlen* effect. Structurally, it is composed of two features at 852 and 830 cm^{-1} which were more resolved in high-PVC paints. However, such bands did not result noticeably shape altered or shifted upon laser irradiation, although the pigment turned visibly black upon laser irradiation, especially with UV lasers (**Figure 2**).

As previously reported, combination bands in the NIR region at 4340 and 4260 cm^{-1} , being associated with volume scattering due to the deeper penetration of IR light in this region, are poorly sensitive to surface changes. Regarding the oil binder, no significant shifts in the $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C=O})$ stretching bands were detected, but only an increase in band intensity in UV-irradiated paints. This enhancement would indicate the formation of a more diffusing and rougher surface texture as a consequence of an ablative effect.

Figure 10. DR-FTIR analysis showing the shifting in the peak position of C-H and C=O stretching of the oil binding medium for matte (high PVC) and glossy (low PVC) oil-paint films upon laser irradiation at 213, 266 and 2940 nm. In the chart, only band shifts exceeding 4 cm^{-1} spectral resolution are reported. Band shifts correspond to the difference between the non-irradiated sample (see control-1 in Table 2 SM) and the laser-irradiated area.

Zinc White in Linseed Oil (ZWLO)

Zinc white in the form of oxide did not show spectral features in the investigated range, therefore the FTIR analysis was limited to the variations of $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C=O})$ of the oil binder. In reference samples, the latter appeared prominently distorted by specular and diffuse surface scattering. Under 213 and 266 nm laser irradiation, no substantial changes in DR-FTIR spectra were observed (**Figure 3**). On the contrary, MIR scattering properties of ZWLO samples irradiated at 2940 nm were severely modified (**Figures 3** and **4**). Basically, the surface roughness increased to such an extent upon the 2940 nm irradiation that $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C=O})$ spectral features passed from derivative-like to positive absorption bands, since the contribution of the first surface scattering was altered by the laser treatment.

Prussian Blue in Linseed Oil (PBLO)

As shown in **Figure 3** the PBLO sample was characterized by an intense derivative band at about 2090 cm^{-1} , which refers to the strong CN asymmetric stretching vibration [41].

Interestingly, the most noticeable change to the CN band was induced by 266 and 2940 nm lasers, both in matte and glossy samples. The transformation in the band shape was less pronounced at 266 nm with respect to 2940 nm.

Regarding the oil binder $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C=O})$ spectral features resulted strongly distorted by surface reflection. The shift of $\nu(\text{C-H})$ band in matte samples was about 18 cm^{-1} at 266 nm and 41 cm^{-1} at 2940 nm, whereas in the glossy sample, was negligible at 266 nm and 26 cm^{-1} at 2940 nm (**Figure 4**). The $\nu(\text{C=O})$ band shifted accordingly, and particularly at 2940 nm, the laser-induced modification produced a strong inversion to an absorbance-like band with the maximum shifting toward a less distorted $\nu(\text{C=O})$ band.

Ultramarine Blue in Linseed Oil (UBLO)

DR-FTIR spectrum of UBLO showed strong *reststrahlen* band of the Si-O antisymmetric stretching at about $900\text{-}1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (**Figure 3**). The *reststrahlen* band of the matte samples was more intense and structured as compared to the glossy samples due to the larger contribution of the diffusively back-reflected radiation. However, no significant changes to the Si-O stretching band were observed. Variations of $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C=O})$ distorted bands confirmed what has been observed so far for the other samples, with greater shifts in the matte sample irradiated at 2940 nm (**Figure 4**).

Micro-Raman spectroscopy

Determination of safe measuring conditions

First, low ($10\times/0.25$) and high ($100\times/0.9$) magnification objective lenses were compared to assess their performances in the detection of laser-induced physicochemical modifications. The $100\times$ objective showed higher sensitivity to surface changes than $10\times$, and hence more appropriate in the present study.

Subsequently, optimal exposure parameters to carry out safe $\mu\text{-RS}$ acquisitions were determined by progressively increasing the laser power and monitoring the peak intensity of the main Raman bands of the pigments (see **Table 1-SM**) present in the oil paint films. The results are listed in **Table 3**. As can be seen, laser-irradiated samples showed higher sensitivity compared to non-irradiated ones, with CYLO, VRLO and PBLO being the most susceptible.

sample	safe power level (%)		Int. time (s)
	<i>non-irradiated</i>	<i>laser-irradiated</i>	
LWLO-G	25	25	60
LWLO-M	25	25	60
CYLO-G	100	1	60
CYLO-M	100	1	60
VRLO-G	25	1	30
VRLO-M	25	1	30
ZWLO-G	50	25	60
ZWLO-M	50	25	60
UBLO-G	50	10	3

UBLO-M	50	10	3
PBLO-G	1	1	60
PBLO-M	1	1	60

Table 5. Exposure conditions found in this study for conducting safe micro-Raman acquisitions of prepared oil paint films.

Assessment of laser-induced modifications

As shown in **Figure 5** and in **Figure 3-SM**, the significant changes noted in Raman spectra above F_{th} were an increase in background intensity, a reduction of the I_R signal resulting from the pigment's blackening, or both effects.

Figure 11. Mean (solid line) and standard deviation (shaded area) of μ -Raman spectra of matte (M) and glossy (G) oil-paint model samples irradiated at 213, 266 and 2940 nm at $1.25 \cdot F_{th}$. Matte paint film samples were characterized by higher Raman signal intensities as compared to glossy paint films. Laser irradiation decreased band intensities of the pigment and increased the backgrounds, markedly upon 2940 nm laser treatment (see red shaded areas).

For LWLO, either matte or glossy, a marked increase in the background intensity after laser irradiation at 2940 nm was observed. The intensity of the carbonate $\nu_1(\text{CO}_3^{2-})$ stretching mode at 1051 cm^{-1} remained almost unvaried. Background amplitude variations were also observed for the other paint films and were clearly more pronounced in ZWLO, PBLO and UBLO glossy samples after irradiation at 2940 nm. Contrarily, in CYLO matte samples, the signal at 353 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_2/\nu_4(\text{CrO}_4^{2-})$ chromate mode decreased mildly in intensity. This effect was instead appreciably marked in photothermally sensitive pigments, like vermilion red and Prussian blue. As shown in **Figure 5**, PBLO samples irradiated at 2940 nm showed an important decrease in the amplitude of $\nu(\text{CN})$ mode of the cyano group ($\approx 2150\text{ cm}^{-1}$). In VRLO samples the most intense peak at about 250 cm^{-1} ascribed to the HgS bending vibrations drastically decreased and completely disappeared in some spectra of samples irradiated at 2940 nm (see **Figure 3-SM**).

As mentioned in the 3.3.2 subsection, the $RBR=(I_R-I_B)/I_B$ parameter was selected to obtain quantitative data on the laser-induced alterations by averaging $RBR_{\text{before}}-RBR_{\text{after}}$ ($\pm\text{SD}$) over 16 measurements for each analyzed area. As illustrated in **Figure 6**, the mean difference of RBR before and after irradiation tends to increase with the laser type, the pigment composing the paint film and its PVC.

Figure 12. Laser-induced variations of Raman signal to background ratio (RBR) of matte and glossy oil paint films irradiated at 213, 266 and 2940 nm and corresponding fluences of $1.25F_{\text{th}}$. The Raman band of the pigment, which was selected for the calculation is indicated in each histogram.

Results show that laser-induced quantitative variations of the Raman signal to background ratio follow the order of wavelengths: $213 < 266 < 2940\text{ nm}$. As regard differences of detected alterations among the samples, variations followed the order $\text{VRLO} < \text{PBLO} < \text{CYLO} < \text{LWLO} < \text{UBLO} < \text{ZWLO}$.

Moreover, at the three tested laser wavelengths, $RBR_{\text{before}}-RBR_{\text{after}}$ variations in LWLO, VRLO and CYLO matte samples were significantly higher as compared to the glossy ones due

to the photosensitive nature of these pigments. Variations observed for the other samples (ZWLO, PBLO, UBLO) showed an opposite trend. Although these variations are less meaningful with respect to the former they reveal a repeatable trend with glossy series more affected than matte ones.

1.4.4 Results and Interpretation

Irradiation tests allowed to point out different micromorphological and discoloration effects which depended on the specific laser wavelength and pulse duration, the pigment and its PVC in the paint film. Considering F_{th} , a difference of about one or two orders of magnitude between tested MUV (213 and 266 nm, 15 ns) and MIR (2940 nm, 150 μ s) lasers was observed.

This difference was determined by the longer pulse duration of the latter and the consequent increase of heat dissipation and fluence needed to induce alteration effects.

Two different discolorations were distinguished by macroscopic and microscopic examinations: darkening and whitening/yellowing regardless of the threshold fluence of the unpigmented paint ($F_{th, LO}$). Paint films containing more photosensitive pigments (i.e. vermilion, lead white and chrome yellow) showed intense to moderate darkening, whereas those made of pigments with F_{th} comparable with $F_{th, LO}$ or higher, showed whitening (Prussian blue and synthetic ultramarine blue) and yellowing (zinc white) along with a matting effect and micromorphological modifications (i.e. bubbles and cratering effects). Thus, the type and amount of pigment in the paint film were found to play a significant role in the laser-induced discoloration effect. In fact, low-PVC (i.e. glossy) samples showed higher F_{th} than high-PVC (i.e. matt) ones, indicating that the absorption of laser light by the oil-binding medium protects the pigment particles from potential laser-induced effects. However, for photothermally sensitive pigments, discoloration induced by UV lasers could not be avoided due to their higher optical absorption. At 2940 nm, laser-induced modifications were mostly associated with thermal damage (i.e. bubbling, yellowing, charring) of the oil binder rather than with the pigment. The degree of discoloration (yellowing) was more apparent for white samples (LWLO and ZWLO) and, most importantly, it was more intense for low PVC films.

DR-FTIR and μ -Raman spectroscopy carried out on laser-processed areas using fluences slightly above the F_{th} ($1.25 \cdot F_{th}$) shed new light on the laser-interaction mechanisms allowing for a correlation of laser-induced surface modifications with damaged components of the paint films.

In detail, it was possible to discriminate whether the pigment or the oil binder or both were damaged. DR-FTIR showed high sensitivity to surface changes, particularly in high absorption regions, where bands are normally subject to frequency-dependent refractive index changes. In fact, changes in the surface scattering properties due to the laser treatment produced band shape effects, variation in the peak intensity, and shifts of $\nu(C-H)$ and $\nu(C=O)$ derivative-like bands, which allowed monitoring, with high surface sensitivity, laser-induced changes of the oil component. Significant shifts of $\nu(C=O)$ derivative-like bands were observed for PBLO, ZWLO and UBLO irradiated at 2940 nm, with more evident shifting in matte films due to the formation of a more diffusing surface texture. Basically, the surface roughness increased to such an extent that $\nu(C-H)$ and $\nu(C=O)$ spectral features passed from derivative-like to positive absorption bands, due to the higher contribution of the volume reflection.

Raman spectra showed variations of the signal-to-background ratio. In accordance with the literature, intensity reduction or total disappearance of the pigment peaks is ascribable to laser-induced degradation, as a result of photochemical, photomechanical and photothermal phenomena (i.e., phase transitions, recrystallization, or thermal decomposition) depending on the wavelength and pulse duration. The rising of the background was prominent after 2940 nm

irradiation and can be reasonably ascribed to an increase of photoluminescence arising from the oil binder as a sum of changes in the chemical (i.e. formation of compounds emitting in this region), physical (i.e. increase of roughness and specific surface) and optical properties (i.e. scattering increase). Raman signal is very weak, thereby, it can be overwhelmed by photoluminescent components. Moreover, previous investigations have shown that oil-diterpenic resin varnishes experienced similar Raman background increases upon laser irradiation, especially at 266 nm in light-aged samples. This interpretation is supported also by DR-FTIR, which exhibited severe peak shifts of derivative-like bands of the oil binder, and OM evidences of micromorphological changes.

Summarizing, LWLO and VRLO, with $F_{th} \leq F_{th, LO}$, showed visible ablation and discoloration of the pigment (darkening or yellowing), decreased RBR (most evident in the matte samples), and negligible FTIR changes in the organic component. Conversely, PBLO, UBLO, and ZWLO, with $F_{th} \geq F_{th, LO}$, showed ablation and discoloration (whitening or yellowing) and noticeable shifts of derivative-like FTIR bands of the organic component, as well as marked decrease of RBR (slightly more pronounced for glossy samples). This means that if the pigment has a high discoloration threshold, the oil binding medium will be affected more than the pigment, especially at low PVC.

DR-FTIR and μ -Raman quantification showed that the Er:YAG laser was relatively more harmful (at the damage threshold) with respect to MUV lasers, although no practicable selective operative margins could be found regardless of the applied laser system. Damage thresholds obtained in this work compared with those reported for the removal of aged varnishes suggest a very narrow safe fluence range and scarce self-termination. As an example, ablation threshold to thin down light-aged dammar varnishes is ≈ 100 mJ/cm² at 213 nm and ≈ 300 mJ/cm² at 266 nm. Regarding Er:YAG laser, satisfying results in terms of a gradual thinning of dammar varnish from an oil painting were reported for dry irradiation at 1.5 J/cm² even though, in practical applications, higher operative fluences are often needed.

1.4.5 Conclusions and perspectives

In this work we investigated laser induced alteration effects on oil-paint films using three wavelengths (213, 266, and 2940 nm, respectively), which were proposed in several literature works for thinning aged varnishes in conservation of painting. In particular, we focused on the detection and quantitative characterization of the undesired effects on unvarnished paint films, which were approached using Diffuse Reflectance FTIR and μ Raman spectroscopies. Through a specifically tailored analytical evaluation protocol, differentiation between damage to the oil binder and the pigment was achieved, showing that at the damage threshold, surface changes were more pronounced with Er:YAG (2940 nm) compared to UV Nd:YAG (213, 266 nm). Most importantly, the quantity of binding medium enveloping the surface of pigment particles could significantly impact the damage thresholds and associated safe ranges.

Finally, the analytical protocol developed may be very useful for practical applications of the above and other laser approaches to varnish thinning. It can allow for monitoring of the varnish removal processes and reveal any early alterations or precursors of extensive damage of the intentionally or unintentionally uncovered painted areas.

1.5 Laser cleaning of artificially soiled cotton fabric: Assessment of surface chemical effects

1.5.1 Context and concept

After reviewing existing literature, it is clear that the laser cleaning process for soiled cotton fabric is still a challenge that needs to be addressed. Based on this, we decided to revisit the experimentation of Q-Switched Nd:YAG laser systems. Our aim was to determine whether it is possible to remove soiling from cotton fabrics without altering the chemistry and structure of the fibres. Additionally, we sought to identify the appropriate application methodology and analytical assessment protocol to achieve this. In summary, our study aimed to establish the damage thresholds of new and artificially aged cotton fabrics when exposed to 1064 nm and 532 nm lasers, assess the efficacy of laser cleaning using artificially soiled cotton mock-ups, determine the optimal combination of conservation standard treatments, such as vacuum cleaning, to facilitate laser removal of soiling particulates, and most importantly, determine analytically whether yellow discolouration of laser-cleaned areas is dependent on the chemical alteration of cellulose fibres.

1.5.2 Material and methods

Sample preparation

Cotton fabric mock-ups were prepared to investigate the potentialities of using laser irradiation to remove unwanted material, such as dirt and grime, from the textile support. The technical data sheet of the cotton fabric, whose commercial name is "ghinea", chosen for this study, is plain weave, warps 19/cm, slight Z-twist; wefts 24/cm, slight Z-twist; N garments. The fabric was originally primed and was de-watered prior to the test treatments, i.e. soaked in hot water to remove the substances with which it is put on the market. Afterwards, a set of five mock-ups were designed and prepared as reported in Table 1.

Sample ID	Sizing	Soiling	Ageing	Pre-treatments
Ref-0	no	no	no	no
Ref-1	rice starch	no	no	no
Ref-2	rice starch	no	Artificial	no
AA-1	rice starch	Artificial	Artificial	no
AA-2	rice starch	Artificial	Artificial	vacuum cleaning
AA-3	rice starch	Artificial	Artificial	vacuum cleaning + moistening

Table 1 - Table summarising the details of the sample preparation process considering sizing treatment, application of artificial soiling, ageing and pre-treatment.

Considering the existing literature regarding the topic, the sizing treatment was carried out by immersion in a bath containing 3% (w/v %) of rice starch in demineralised water. Then, the tissue sample was left to soak for two hours, stretch out on a smooth surface, and dry overnight

at room temperature. The day after, the mock-up was seized again, this time with a flat brush, and then left to dry at room temperature overnight.

Afterwards, a thin layer of artificial soiling, prepared according to indications in 3.1.1 section, was applied to the cotton size model using the toothbrush method to recreate a dot texture.

The seized and soiled textile samples were then subjected to accelerated hydrothermal ageing following the ISO 5630-7:2014. The cotton mock-ups were left in a laboratory oven within a sealed vessel at $80\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $60.6\pm 2\%$ relative humidity (RH) in the absence of light for up to 13 days. A saturated solution of sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) was used to keep the relative humidity constant during ageing.

Last, as reported in Table 1, AA-2 and AA-3 mock-ups were subject to further treatment to assess whether standard vacuum cleaning can favour a more effective laser cleaning treatment. Before vacuuming, to recreate the creases and the surface texture of an actual garment, the mock-ups were folded several times and placed under weights (3kg) for a week. Afterwards, to slowly relax the folds of the fabric, one mock-up (i.e., AA-3) was placed in a humidity chamber sealed at $21\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity (RH) between 75% and 80% for a total of 3.5 hrs. It should be noted that in AA-3 sample the application of moisture treatment was executed with the intention of aiding the tissue in its ability to decrease instances of creasing, wrinkling, and planar deformation.

Artificial soiling preparation

The surfaces of art objects are covered with a complex mixture of particulate soils consisting of materials such as carbonaceous, organic, and inorganic substances. Therefore, based on the published literature in the field of conservation, a synthetic mixture mimicking the soil composition of objects stored under indoor museum conditions was used. It consisted of: 0.175 g carbon black (Zecchi Colori Belle Arti, Florence, Italy), 0.05 g iron oxide (Zecchi Colori Belle Arti, Florence, Italy), 0.95 g gelatine (Zecchi Colori Belle Arti, Florence, Italy), 0.95 g soluble starch (Zecchi Colori Belle Arti, Florence, Italy), 0.175 g silica (CTS Conservation, Florence, Italy), 1.525 g lime (CTS Conservation, Florence, Italy), 1.7 g kaolin (CTS Conservation, Florence, Italy), and 8 ml mineral oil (CTS Conservation, Florence, Italy). Cement and peat moss were removed from the recipe prepared for this study. The mixture after stirring up with a wooden tongue depressor for a minute was grey/black in appearance.

1.5.3 Monitoring protocol

Laser irradiation thresholds

A QS Nd:YAG (1064, 532 nm) laser (pulse duration of 9 ns) was selected for the present experimentation. The laser beam was delivered through an optical fibre, and its output was imaged onto the target using a lens ($f=40$ mm). In this configuration, the magnification factor and hence the spot size can be finely varied by suitably setting the lens-fibre tip and lens-target distances. Fluence values were obtained by dividing pulse energy by the measured spot areas (estimated from a photosensitive black paper - ZAP-IT laser alignment and burn paper). The laser beam diameter on the irradiated surface was about 1.6 mm for the 1064 nm laser wavelength and 1.4 mm for the 532 nm laser wavelength.

The criterion for defining the damage threshold used in this study was the minimal fluence leading to visible alteration (F_{th}) of the surface sample at 1064 and 532 nm laser wavelength. This was first conducted on unaged and aged-sized cotton fabric mock-ups. The damage threshold was determined upon laser irradiation under an optical microscope (OM) with a dedicated setup. Protective aluminium foil tape masks, previously pierced with a hole punch with a diameter of 3 mm, were placed onto the fabric samples. Each hole area was exposed to

a single shot, increasing the fluence levels from 0.3 J/cm² to 4 J/cm² at 1064 nm and from 0.3 J/cm² to 4.3 J/cm² at 532 nm with a repetition rate of 1 Hz. The damage threshold was established with the appearance of fibre damage, disruption or discolouration (yellowing) visible under OM.

Thus, the same approach was adopted to determine the threshold fluence ($F_{th, soil}$) for soiling removal to ensure that appropriate cleaning was possible at fluence values lower than $F_{th, cotton}$ of the fabric samples previously obtained.

Laser cleaning tests

The laser cleaning tests were performed through a motorised scanning procedure, of which more details can be found in. In this set-up, the mock-ups were mounted and scanned on a controlled x-y stage, allowing two pulses per spot area to be released on the tested surface with a 50% overlap with a repetition rate of 5 Hz.

An engraving machine cut an aluminium foil, creating rectangular areas of 7x8 mm to obtain a protective mask placed upon the fabric samples before the laser irradiation. For the laser treatment at both wavelengths, test areas were created with established fluence values, corresponding to $F_{th, soil}$ for soiling removal and $F/F_{th, soil}$ ratios of 1.75, 2.5 and 4, respectively, with F the incident fluence. Laser-irradiated areas were then analysed by FORS, colourimetric analysis, DR-FTIR, μ -Raman, and XRF spectroscopy to identify changes in surface properties, fiber composition, and yellowing following laser treatment.

Microscopies

Damage thresholds for the cotton fabric and removal threshold for the artificial soiling were observed with Brightfield Optical Microscopy (OM) using a Nikon Eclipse L150 (obj: 5 \times and 10 \times) (Tokyo, Japan) equipped with a Nikon D80 DSLR camera (Tokyo, Japan). Micromorphological changes in the irradiated laser areas were also investigated using a stereo microscope. The irradiated areas, exposed to increased fluence values, were observed in reflected light using an Olympus SZX7 stereo microscope that provided an 8 \times -56 \times total magnification and a field of view of 27.5-3.9 mm. The images acquired were processed with ImageJ free software.

Fibre Optic Reflectance Spectroscopy (FORS)

The fibre optic reflectance spectra on untreated and laser-treated areas were recorded using a SensLine AvaSpec-2048 XL (Avantes) spectrophotometer equipped with an AvaLight-HAL-S halogen light source. The detector and the light source were connected with a bifurcated fibre optic FCR-7UV400-2-ME probe. In this configuration, the light was sent and retrieved by the bifurcated fibre optic set at approximately 45° from the surface normal, thus excluding specular reflectance SCE mode (specular component excluded). The spectral detector range was 200–1100 nm (grating 300 lines/mm), but only the 360 nm to 800 nm range was considered in this study. The calibration was conducted using a 99% Spectralon® diffuse reflectance standard. The diameter of the investigated area on the sample was approximately 1 mm. Instrument settings were 11 ms of integration time and 15 scans. The analysis was performed using AvaSoft 8 software for Windows.

The L^* , a^* and b^* coordinates were acquired with a standard observer of 10 degrees and an A illuminant. Measurements were repeated three times at different locations to determine variability in each mock-up. Based on the $L^*a^*b^*$ values and the BS EN 15886 standard, the magnitude of the Total Colour Difference (ΔE^*_{ab}) was calculated as follows: $\Delta E^*_{ab} = [(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2]^{1/2}$ where L^* (lightness) ranges between 100 (brightest white)

and 0 (darkest black) and a^* and b^* (chromaticity coordinates) represent the green ($-a^*$) and red ($+a^*$) component and the blue ($-b^*$) and yellow ($+b^*$) component, respectively. ΔL^* , Δa^* and Δb^* values were related to the difference between the artificially soiled samples (AA-1, AA-2, and AA-3) and the equivalent aged-sized cotton fabric (Ref-2).

Diffuse reflectance-FTIR

Diffuse reflectance-FTIR (DR-FTIR) spectroscopy was conducted using a Cary 630 (Agilent Technologies, USA) FT-IR spectrometer equipped with a diffuse reflectance module. The wave-number range was set from 4000 to 700 cm^{-1} , and the spectra were acquired over 256 scans at 4 cm^{-1} resolution using the Agilent MicroLab software. A mat gold plate was used as a reference background spectrum. The mock-ups were placed on a metal holder and secured with a clamp. The acquisition area was approximately 2 mm in diameter, and three spectra were collected once in each non-irradiated and irradiated area for all the prepared mock-ups. The DR-FTIR data presented in this publication were first evaluated qualitatively, and further processed to identify laser-induced chemical changes associated with yellowing and possible crosslinking reactions. The processing methodology consisted of a few steps. Acquired DR-FTIR spectra were slightly smoothed using 4 points moving average with a rectangular function, followed by spectral truncation in the 2000-700 cm^{-1} region of interest to eliminate the contribution of unrelated variables/noise. After truncating the spectra, a scatter-corrective Standard Normal Variate (SNV) processing was applied, as it performed better among other tested methods, including standard normalisation, de-trending (baseline subtraction) and Multiplicative scatter Correction (MSC). The difference spectra between laser-treated areas and the untreated reference were then calculated, setting the scaling factor to 1 for all data presented. Spectral processing was performed with Spectragryph software [28] and OriginLab software.

i-Raman spectroscopy

The high spatial resolution of the *i*-Raman technique was exploited to investigate the molecular composition of the cotton yarns down to the micro-scale. *i*-Raman measurements were carried out using the Xplora spectrometer by Horiba Jobin-Yvon to gather information on possible molecular modification of celluloses after laser irradiation. The system is equipped with three lasers (532 nm, 633 nm, and 785 nm). Herein, Raman spectra were recorded using a near-infrared (785 nm) laser excitation wavelength for reducing luminescence interference. The near-infrared Raman laser source was focused onto the sample surface with a spot of 2 μm diameter using a 100 \times objective providing a power of 10mW. Spectra were acquired using 600 lines/mm grating in the range of 200 – 2000 cm^{-1} with an acquisition time of 100 seconds. Six spectra per laser-treated area were acquired by carefully selecting different cotton yarns in each tested area.

X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy XRF

A Surface Monitor 2.0 XRF spectrometer (Assing s.p.a) was used to determine the elemental content of the presence of artificial dust after laser radiation from the prepared fabric artefacts. The XRF unit consisted of an X-ray tube with a gold target and silicon drift detector (SDD) with a resolution of 165 eV (FWHM @5.9 keV). X-ray tube and detector were equipped with cylindrical collimators producing an analysed spot size diameter of about 2 mm. The operational parameters were 50 kV input voltage, 70 μA current and 240 sec of accumulation live time. No filters were used during the acquisition of the spectra, and the analysis was

conducted in the open air without helium purge. The data points presented were obtained by normalising the XRF spectra to the peak of the gold X-ray tube ($L\alpha$ 9.71 keV). Thus, peak areas were determined for Ca ($K\alpha$ 3.69 keV) and Fe ($K\alpha$ 6.40 keV). The data were acquired using the dedicated software and processed with OriginLab software.

1.5.4 Results and interpretation

Nd:YAG laser tests and microscope observations

Safe cleaning windows for laser exposure at 532 nm and 1064 nm were first established by measuring laser-induced damage thresholds on unsoiled cotton fabric. A focal spot size of approximately 1.4 mm at 532 nm and 1.6 mm at 1064 nm was used. Results, shown in Figure 1, indicated that the unaged (Ref-1) and aged (Ref-2) sized cotton fabric could be safely exposed at 532 nm at a fluence up to approximately 4.3 J/cm^2 (Fig. 1a-b and Fig. 1 c-d) and at 1064 nm laser at about 4 J/cm^2 (Fig. 1e-f and Fig. 1 g-h). No surface discolouration (yellowing) was observed using the selected parameters. These results are consistent with those found in a previous study conducted on pure and gelatine-sized cellulose (unsoiled) [29], where threshold fluences were found at 4.7 J/cm^2 for 532 nm and 4 J/cm^2 for 1064 nm. Furthermore, no long-term effects were observed below these thresholds.

Figure 1 – Optical micrograph of the non-irradiated and irradiated Ref-1 and Ref-2 mock-ups at a 4.3 J/cm^2 at 532 nm and 4 J/cm^2 at 1064 nm, respectively.

Further tests were conducted on the artificially soiled cotton fabrics (AA-1) to characterise the fluence threshold needed to remove the soiling. The examination under OM of the artificially soiled cotton fabrics after laser irradiation led to establishing the threshold fluences $F_{th, soil}$ required for soil removal were 0.4 J/cm^2 at 532 nm (Fig. 2a) and 0.5 J/cm^2 at 1064 nm (Fig. 2b).

Figure 2 – Optical micrograph of the non-irradiated (a and c) and irradiated AA-1 mock-ups at a 0.4 J/cm² at 532 nm (b) and 0.5 J/cm² at 1064 nm (d).

Cleaning tests were conducted on all mock-ups, taking into account the cotton damage threshold ($F_{th, cotton}$) and the lowest fluence threshold required to remove soiling ($F_{th, soil}$). For each wavelength/mock-up combination, a 7×8 mm² matrix was laser processed with varying fluence values. After laser irradiation, the complete test matrix underwent a visual assessment to check for roughness, visible damage, and cleaning effect.

Upon conducting a stereomicroscope investigation of the artificially soiled cotton fabrics after laser-irradiation, it was found that complete soil removal along with uniform cleaning could be achieved by using 1 J/cm² at 532 nm (2.5 $F_{th, soil}$) and 1.2 J/cm² at 1064 nm (2.5 $F_{th, soil}$). It was observed that this treatment did not cause any damage to the underlying fibres, as depicted in Figure 3. Even at the lowest fluence selected for this study of 0.4 and 0.5 J/cm², the stereomicrograph images displayed acceptable cleaning results with a slight residue of the soiling (figure not displayed). No fibre damage or disruption to the textile structure was observed at any of the fluence tested for both laser wavelengths selected in this study. One drawback of artificially soiled test fabrics was the slight discolouration (yellowing) observed at 1064 nm. At 532 nm, the fibres showed no damage, and the surface appeared less yellow and visibly closer to the appearance of the unsoiled reference (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Stereomicrographs of the tested areas (AA-1, AA-2 and AA-3) before and after irradiation with a satisfactory outcome. a-d-g) not irradiated area; b-e-h) 532 nm laser-scanned area at a fluence of 1 J/cm² (2.5 $F_{th, soil}$); e-f-i) 1064 nm laser-scanned area at 1.2 J/cm² (2.5 $F_{th, soil}$). The scale bar is 1 mm for all the images.

FORS and colourimetric analysis

Figure 4 shows the reflectance spectra acquired before and after laser irradiation at 532 and 1064 nm of cotton mock-ups in the range of 350 to 800 nm. As it is possible to observe, cellulose scatters most of the light throughout the visible spectrum while the absorption steadily increases in the UV region. In fact, the reflectance spectra for all acquired areas exhibited maximum absorption centered at about 394.71 nm. Except for minor variations in the reflectance percentage, the spectra were reproducible. The fluence range selected for this study (between $F_{th, soil}$ and $4F_{th, soil}$), using both laser wavelengths, has made it possible to assess slight reflectance changes in the spectra. It is worth mentioning that at 532 nm and $4F_{th, soil}$ an over-cleaning effect of the cotton substrate could occur since the reflectance profiles exceed those of the non-soiled reference sample (Ref-2). As already reported in the literature, laser irradiation at 532 nm of historical or slightly aged yellowish papers may lead to a substantial decrease in the degree of yellowing (namely bleaching), accompanied by further oxidation. This discolouration effect is not accompanied by significant spectral changes, although a chemical change could still occur because small amounts of carbonyls and other absorbing

substances (such as double bond unsaturation, oxygen-polymer charge transfer complexes, metallic impurities, etc.) may start photooxidative reactions in the substrate. However, the bleaching effect is generally observed at high laser fluences or at a high repetition rate (5-10 Hz) and can be avoided during cleaning operations by adjusting the irradiation parameters correctly.

Contrary to what was observed at 532 nm, sample areas irradiated at 1064 nm turned out yellower. This effect is appreciable in the 400-550 nm region, where the spectra, due to scattering effects, did not recover in reflectance as much as after the 532 nm treatment. Most important, the yellowing effect increases when the density of soil particulates increases. This can be clearly observed at 1064 nm in the AA-1 sample, where no pre-vacuuming treatment was applied.

Figure 4 – Reflectance spectra acquired by FORS, in the 350-800 nm range, of the different types of mock-ups and the relative comparison among the spectra obtained before and after the laser irradiation by increasing the fluence values between $F_{th, soil}$ and 4 times $F_{th, soil}$.

Figure 5 shows the slight discolouration (yellowing) detected on the cotton mock-ups after irradiating 1064 nm. This colour variation was also visually observed under stereo microscopy and was mainly due to the re-deposition of ablation products on the surface.

Figure 5 – Δb^* values and Total Colour Difference (ΔE^*_{ab}) for the mock-ups with artificial soiling. Data were obtained by the difference between colour values acquired on artificially soiled specimens (AA-1, AA-2, and AA-3) and the unsoiled-sized cotton fabric (Ref-2 - reference). The dashed line at $\Delta E=2$ specifies the threshold at which the eye can detect minimal colour differences [10]. For simplicity, F_{th} in the label refers to the removal threshold fluence of the soiling (i.e. $F_{th, soil}$).

As shown in Figure 5, the total colour difference values (ΔE^*_{ab}) showed an overall downward trend upon the cleaning treatment with both lasers' wavelengths (532 and 1064 nm) and increasing fluence values. The total colour difference (ΔE^*_{ab}) was found to be significantly higher in the mock-ups that were exposed to 1064 nm laser irradiation, as compared to those subjected to 532 nm. Furthermore, the comparison between laser and vacuum cleaning is remarkably evident, particularly in samples AA-2 and AA-3 irradiated at 532 nm. The ΔE^*_{ab} went from 8 of the vacuum-cleaned samples to between 2 and 4 after laser treatment. It is also worth noting that the AA-1 samples showed more variation in colour compared to the AA-2 and AA-3 samples. This suggests that the pre-vacuuming treatment can effectively minimise the laser-induced discolouration effect. The intensity of this effect is usually more pronounced as the degree of surface soiling increases.

DR-FTIR and μ -Raman

Chemically, FTIR spectroscopy is sensitive to the skeletal mode vibration of α -1,4 glycosidic linkages, while Raman spectroscopy is to skeletal vibrational modes of less polar bonds, such as C–C symmetric vibration and pyranoid ring vibration. Thus, Figure 6a shows the typical DR-FTIR spectra for cotton and rice starch and a sized cotton fabric mock-up (Ref-2). The latter in the 900-1200 cm^{-1} region is modified by the strong distorted C-O-C glycoside bond vibration of the starch. Similarly, the Ref-2 μ -Raman spectrum in Figure 6b shows changes due to the use of rice starch on cotton. In particular, the Raman band at 476 cm^{-1} is associated with the presence of starch, which is not evident in the spectrum of the Ref-0 sample. Moreover, the

relative intensity of the Raman bands of cellulose at 1335 and 1380 cm^{-1} are inverted in the spectrum of the Ref-2 compared to the one of the Ref-0 sample, due to the presence of starch. For this reason, to assess the differences between treatments, Raman bands of cellulose at 372 and 1088 cm^{-1} were used as they were not affected by the starch.

Figure 6 – DR-FTIR (a) and Raman (b) spectra of reference materials before laser irradiation. The grey boxes highlight the regions where bond vibrations in cotton and starch overlap. Bold labels refer to the main starch bands.

Band assignments for DR-FTIR and μ -Raman spectra are summarised in Table 1 according to the reference literature.

As a matter of fact, absorbance fluctuations signposted negligible laser-induced molecular modifications, even beyond fluences 4 times higher than $F_{\text{th, soil}}$ (Figure 7). In contrast to what was reported in the literature, neither destruction of chemical bonds nor formation by cross-linking reactions was observed. The difference spectra clearly showed no change in the band at 1645 cm^{-1} of the hydroxyl groups. Through the bands at 1430, 1375, 1317 and 893 cm^{-1} related to CH deformation and stretching of other minor vibrations (COC, CCO and CCH) in polysaccharides, no modifications to the cellulose structure and to the degree of crystallinity were appreciated. Subtle deviations were observable moving toward the 900-1200 cm^{-1} region, where fall important bands suggested for monitoring the splitting of the glycosidic bond (C–O–C asymmetric stretching) or the opening of the glucopyranose ring. However, the minor difference peaks observed in this region at 1168 and 1065 cm^{-1} were due to the unevenness of the starch sizing rather than to laser-modified cellulose. This was supported by recurrent shifts of the peak maxima at 1168 and 1065 cm^{-1} associated with starch at various locations in the size reference models (Ref-2). For soiled samples subject to pre-vacuuming treatment (AA-2 and AA-3), difference spectra appeared flatter in the starch-cellulose overlapping region, as the residual starch was partially extracted during suction processing. However, these changes were not observed in the unsized Ref-0 sample. Moreover, the DR-FTIR analysis found no association between yellowing and chemical changes in samples irradiated at 1064 nm.

Raman		DR-FTIR	
Raman shift [1/cm]	Tentative assignment [33–35,37]	Wavenumbers [1/cm]	Tentative assignment [36–40]
344	$\delta(\text{CCC})$, $\delta(\text{CCO})$, ring deformation (c)	893	$\nu(\text{COC})$, $\nu(\text{CCO})$ and $\nu(\text{CCH})$ from the polysaccharide components of cellulose (c)
372	$\delta(\text{CCC})$, $\delta(\text{COC})$ ring deformation (c)	1044-1065	$\nu(\text{COH})$ bond in cellulose (c) and starch (s)
436	$\delta(\text{CCC})$, $\delta(\text{CCO})$ ring deformation (c)	1092	$\nu(\text{ring})$, $\nu(\text{CC})$, $\nu(\text{CO})$ (c) (s)
475	Skeletal modes of pyranose ring (s)	1126	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COC})$ glycosidic ether band, indicative of polysaccharides in cellulose (c)
514	$\delta(\text{COC})$ glycosidic linkage/CCC ring deformation (c)	1179	$\nu(\text{CC})$ ring breathing, indicative of polysaccharides in cellulose (c)
		1168	$\nu(\text{CC})$, C-O-C glycoside bond (s)
1089	$\nu(\text{COC})$ glycosidic, ring breathing (c)	1237	CH_2OH (side chain) related mode (s) $\delta(\text{COH})$ in plane at C-6 (c)
1117	$\nu(\text{COC})$ glycosidic linkage, symmetric stretching, ring breathing, skeletal (c)	1317	$\delta(\text{CO})$ and $\delta(\text{CH})$ of the glucopyranose ring in cellulose polysaccharides (c)
1339	Twisting (CH_2), $\delta(\text{COH})$ (s)	1372	$\delta(\text{CH})$ glucopyranose ring (c)(s)
		1430	$\delta(\text{CH}_2)$ glucopyranose ring (c)(s)
1335	$\delta(\text{CH}_2)$ rocking and wagging (c)	1640-1645	vibration of absorbed water in cellulose (c) and starch (s)
1378	$\delta(\text{CH}_2)$, $\delta(\text{HCC})$, $\delta(\text{HCO})$, $\delta(\text{COH})$ (c) (s)	2901	$\nu(\text{CH})$ (c)
1462	$\delta(\text{CH}_2)$ scissors. Correlated to amorphous cellulose (c)(s)	3450	$\nu(\text{OH})$ (c)

Table 2 - Assignment of μ -Raman and DR-FTIR bands of cellulose in cotton fibre (c) with rice starch (s).

Figure 7 – DR-FTIR difference spectra of the different types of mock-ups showing absorbance variations upon 532 nm (green spectrum) and 1064 nm (red spectrum) laser irradiation. Fluence values correspond to F_{th} , $2.5 F_{th}$ and $4 F_{th}$ the removal threshold fluence of the soiling ($F_{th, soil}$). The DR-FTIR difference spectra presented were obtained with the following pre-processing treatment: 4 points moving-average smoothing, 2000-750 cm^{-1} truncation and SNV correction. Variations in the 900-1200 cm^{-1} region, in the stack highlighted by the grey box, are due to the inhomogeneity of the starch sizing.

Raman spectra were acquired on untreated and irradiated (532 and 1064 nm) samples. In particular, bands of cellulose at 372.03 cm^{-1} (skeletal modes of pyranose ring) and 1088.83 cm^{-1} (glycosidic linkage) were selected as references to address differences among the treatments. As far as is known, the degradation of cellulose is related to the decrease of DP following the splitting of the glycosidic bond. Therefore, an increase of the 1088/373 ratio toward the reference unsoiled sample after the laser treatment should not be considered as chemical damage but reasonably a positive result. On the contrary, a decrease of the 1088/373 intensity ratio as a consequence of soiling removal is assumed to be indicative of a laser-induced chemical modification.

In this respect, Figure 8 shows the mean values of the ratio between the intensity (background subtracted) of the Raman band at 1088 cm^{-1} and 372 cm^{-1} , respectively. The grey bar is the mean value of the cotton sample without soiling (Ref-0), taken as a reference for the soiled samples. Red bars are the mean values of the three classes of soiled samples before the laser treatments. Finally, the light blue and blue bars are the mean of samples irradiated with the 532 nm and 1064 nm laser excitation wavelength, respectively. In the AA-1 sample with the highest content of soiling, the ratio between the intensity of the Raman bands remained almost unaltered after laser treatments, meaning that no alteration of cellulose was induced. In contrast, following vacuum cleaning in laser-irradiated areas showed more prominent deviations, especially for 1064 nm tests. For instance, for AA-3 samples the apparent increase of the 1088/373 intensity ratios after irradiation at 1064 nm could be related to thermal decomposition due to a higher concentration of iron oxide in the soiling, as detected by XRF analysis (4.3 section). In this respect, it could be supposed the formation of inter- and intramolecular bonds. However, these deviations are hardly ascribable to specific laser-induced cellulose modifications since they are within the level of uncertainty of the measurement.

Figure 8; Mean values of the ratio between the intensity of the cellulose Raman band at 1088.83 cm^{-1} and 372.03 cm^{-1} , respectively. The grey bar is the mean value of the cotton sample without soiling (Ref-0), the red bars are the mean values of the three classes of samples (AA-1, AA-2, AA-3) before the laser treatments. Light blue and blue bars are the mean of samples irradiated with the 532 nm and 1064 nm laser excitation wavelength, respectively. For simplicity, F_{th} in the label refers to the removal threshold fluence of the soiling (i.e. $F_{th, soil}$).

XRF analysis

One distinctive observation in the XRF analysis was the substantial reduction of Fe and Ca elements to levels similar to the untreated cotton fabric (Ref-0) and aged-sized cotton fabric (Ref-2) after Nd:YAG irradiation at 532 and 1064 nm (Figure 9).

Figure 9 – XRF measurements: circles mark mean values, vertical bars mark max and min values, red symbols refer to samples not irradiated by laser, light blue and blue symbols refer to samples irradiated

with the 532 nm and 1064 nm laser excitation wavelength, respectively. For simplicity, F_{th} in the label refers to the removal threshold fluence of the soiling (i.e. $F_{th, soil}$).

In particular, in the AA-1 mock-ups, the laser interactions were more easily distinguished due to an overall downward trend upon using the two lasers. It is important to highlight that the AA-1 mock-up had a higher soil level than the other two types of samples (AA-2 and AA-3). As a result, for the AA-1 model, the return of the Fe and Ca elements to levels similar to Ref-0 and Ref-2 was not immediate. As with the 532 nm laser wavelength, the reduction of the Fe and Ca elements improved by increasing the fluence values. Conversely, the 1064 nm laser wavelength appeared more effective at low fluence.

1.5.5 Conclusions and perspectives

The results of the present study, based on the experimental findings, have shown that when laser parameters are carefully chosen (wavelength and fluence values), laser cleaning of soiled cotton fabric is a highly selective method well-suited to extremely fragile surfaces and microstructures, as they can be those of the aged textiles. Soiling can be removed from white woven cotton fabric without fibre disruption or chemical damage, which is not feasible using wet cleaning and solvent cleaning methods commonly employed by conservators.

Laser irradiation tests led to diverse results depending on laser wavelength. At 532 nm, discolouration of the cleaned cotton surface is only slight at very high fluences ($4F_{th, soil}$), whereas moderate yellowing upon 1064 nm treatment was observed even at low removal fluences. Considering all the spectral analyses carried out on the untreated and laser-treated areas, it was concluded that no significant deterioration occurred after the laser irradiation using both the fundamental wavelength and second harmonic of a QS Nd:YAG laser (1064, 532 nm). Noteworthy, results showed that vacuum cleaning prior to the laser treatment could favour a more effective cleaning. Therefore, the laser approach should be conceived as the finishing step in the cleaning process, as it allows the removal of dirt particles stuck to the fibres and a deeper degree of removal than standard methods. However, one must remember that the positive result strongly depends on the experimental parameters selected during the cleaning process. Finally, although further work is needed in order to directly assess the nature of the discolouration at 1064 nm, the absence of chemical damage to the fibres and the decreasing trend of the phenomenon at increasing fluences, suggests it could be due to incomplete cleaning i.e. to soiling residues trapped within the fibres.

1.6 In-depth structural and compositional assessment of aged terpenoid varnish layers by nonlinear optical microscopy

1.6.1 Context and concept

This project investigates the extent of degradation of the outermost layers of varnish coatings on paintings. Due to aging varnishes undergo complex and differentiated structural and chemical changes over time depending on their composition and conservation conditions. In this project, these degradation phenomena, dependent of the depth below the surface, have been investigated by the non-invasive technique of nonlinear optical microscopy (NLOM) in the modality of multiphoton excitation fluorescence (MPEF). The aim of the study was the determination of the thickness, with microscopic axial and lateral resolution, of the affected regions of pictorial terpenoid varnish layer samples, made of dammar, mastic, shellac and sandarac, subjected to various types and degrees of aging, artificial, natural and a combination of both. By combining NLOM-MPEF with single-photon laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) measurements it was possible to determine the degree of surface aging and investigate the correlations between the extent of degradation, the type and length of aging, the nature of the varnish and the initial thickness of the varnish layer.

This study is the result of the collaboration between two teams of the IPERION HS partnership from Instituto de Química Física Blas Cabrera (former Rocasolano), CSIC, Madrid, Spain and Istituto di Fisica Applicata “N. Carrara, CNR, Sesto Fiorentino, Italy. The common work has resulted in one publication (Marina Martínez-Weinbaum, Laura Maestro-Guijarro, Paula María Carmona-Quiroga, Salvatore Siano, Daniele Ciofini, M. Castillejo, M. Oujja, *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 62 (2023) 170-180, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2023.05.026>) and oral presentations in several meeting and conferences in the Heritage Science field.

1.6.2 Material and methods

Varnish samples

Solvent-based varnish samples investigated here were prepared 10 years ago as part of an extensive project to study photooxidative kinetics under accelerated lighting conditions of various types of painting varnishes. A batch of these samples with different degrees of aging and thickness was selected to obtain in-depth information about the affected region due to aging. Varnishes were formulated by dissolving 30% (by weight) of finely ground natural resin in the appropriate solvent, as reported in **Table 1**. To prepare single-layer films of various thicknesses, different amounts (0.8, 0.4, and 0.2 g) of each varnish formulation were taken with a graduated pipette from the vials and cast as evenly as possible onto glass slides. Afterwards, curing of casted varnish was formerly carried out on a leveled plane for one month, then ventilated at oven at 25 °C for 24 h in the absence of light, and vacuum dried for about 1 week until reaching a constant weight. A set of prepared samples was stored in darkness under controlled laboratory conditions (20-25 °C, 45-55% UR) whereas a further set was exposed to accelerated light-aging in a cw air-cooled Xenon test chamber (i.e. artificial aging). Aging conditions were B.S.T. (Black Standard Temperature) = 50 °C, cut-off of 290 nm, 50 mW/cm². After being artificially aged, the samples have been newly exposed together with the former set under the same laboratory conditions for about 10 years prior to being analyzed. To obtain different degrees of in-depth aging, varnish samples were exposed during various time intervals spanning from a minimum of 50 h up to 500 h. Aging was ended at 500 h of exposure since

most of the structural and chemical changes have been observed within the first 200 h of aging. The aging condition of each sample is reported in **Table 1**.

Sample (solvent)	Code	Dry weight (g)	Aging condition
Light shellac (ethanol)			
	Sh1	0.2270	10 years (n.a)
	Sh2	0.2204	52h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	Sh3	0.2036	102h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	Sh4	0.1021	500h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	Sh5	0.0614	10 years (n.a)
Dammar (white spirit)			
	D1	0.3526	10 years (n.a)
	D2	0.3178	160 h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	D3	0.3621	350 h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	D4	0.1902	350 h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	D5	0.0989	10 years (n.a)
Sandarac standard (ethanol)			
	S1	0.2146	10 years (n.a)
	S2	0.1900	52h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	S3	0.2174	102h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	S4	0.1020	500 h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	S5	0.0600	10 years (n.a)
Mastic chios (iso-propanol)			
	M1	0.2024	10 years (n.a)
	M2	0.2122	52h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	M3	0.2139	102h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	M4	0.1102	500h (a.a) + 10 years (n.a)
	M5	0.0717	10 years (n.a)

Table 1. List of selected varnish films applied on glass substrates. Artificial and natural aged samples are referred as a.a and n.a, respectively. Aging times of the dammar series (D) differ from those of other varnishes because they were part of a batch of samples prepared at a different time.

Figure 1. Examples of the single-layer varnish samples on glass slides analyzed in this study after artificial and 10 years of natural aging. The scale bar is 2 cm for all images. The labels are explained in **Tables 1** and **2**.

After each aging condition, weight losses were monitored by gravimetric measurements. The dry weight reported in **Table 1** refers to the weight residue at the corresponding aging time.

1.6.3 Monitoring protocol

The physicochemical aging effects on the varnish samples were assessed, in a non-invasive way, both on the surface and in-depth using laser induced fluorescence (LIF) and NLOM in the MPEF modality. The latter was also used to quantify the thickness of the degradation layer below the surface of the varnish films due to aging effects. Thicknesses of the layers determined by NLOM-MPEF were compared with those retrieved by optical microscopy (OM).

LIF measurements were carried out using laser excitation at 266 nm (4th harmonic of a Q-switched Nd:YAG laser, 6 ns pulses, 10 Hz repetition rate) and a 0.30 m spectrograph with a 300 lines/mm grating coupled to an intensified charged coupled detector. The temporal gate of the detector was operated at zero-time delay with respect to the arrival of the laser pulse to the surface of the sample and with a width of 3 μ s. The sample was illuminated by the laser at an incidence angle of 45° with pulses of around 0.1 mJ using a laser spot size of 1 x 2 mm².

An optical profilometer (Zeta-20) was used to measure in a non-contact mode the surface profiles, in order to get the varnish surface elevation Z as a function of the lateral coordinates X and Y over the glass substrate. The lateral distance probed in each measurement has not exceeded 1 mm.

In-depth non-invasive analysis of the varnish samples was performed with a nonlinear optical microscope developed at Instituto de Química Física Blas Cabrera (former Rocasolano). The excitation light source is a mode-locked Ti:Sapphire femtosecond laser emitting at 800 nm delivering 70 fs pulses at a repetition rate of 80 MHz. A variable neutral density filter was used to control the laser power reaching the sample. For the present measurements, the average power was in the range of 1.5-2 mW, values far below the damage threshold of the varnish samples. The laser beam was modulated using a chopper at a frequency of 130 Hz and conducted to the sample through the aperture of a microscope objective lens (NA 0.42) by using a dichroic beam splitter with high reflection at 800 nm. The laser focal plane was selected with motorized translation XYZ stages. The lateral and in-depth resolutions achieved are 1 and 2 μ m, respectively. The MPEF signals were collected in the backward direction through the

objective lens and a beam splitter (70/30) and measured using a photomultiplier tube connected to a lock-in amplifier. A bandpass filter (335-610 nm) was placed at the entrance of the photomultiplier to cut off the reflected laser light at 800 nm. The remaining 30% of the MPEF signal was sent to a CCD camera (for online visualization of the sample surface and the signal collection process). The thickness value of each varnish sample was obtained by averaging the values obtained in Z-scans carried out at four different points of each sample.

1.6.4 Interpretation of results

Laser Induced Fluorescence

LIF spectra collected on the aged varnishes of this study, displayed in **Figure 2**, consist of a broad feature in the 300-700 nm range with fluorescence maxima occurring at different emission wavelengths depending on the nature of the varnish.

The analysis and discussion of the different contribution of varnish fluorophores and products of aging/degradation processes for each varnish sample is given in detail in the publication that has resulted from this project. The obtained LIF results indicate a high stability against light aging of shellac and dammar varnishes as compared to sandarac and mastic. The first two varnishes show an almost gradual increase in the LIF intensity and red-shifting as a function of the artificial aging time in the range of 0 - 500 hours, however, the last two ones show different behaviors, the corresponding to the artificial aging time less than or equal to 102 hours with a slight increase in the LIF intensity and red shift and a very marked effect corresponding to 500 hours of aging. The modifications induced in the LIF spectra and the changes to the shape and position of the maximum of the fluorescence profiles indicate the participation of photo-ageing processes. Specifically, the increase in fluorescence intensity and the red-shifted bands are associated with presence and formation of new fluorophores (i.e. new C=C bonds) and can be linked with the production of oxidized and cross-linked products occurring during photo-induced polymerization.

Figure 2. LIF spectra of the varnish samples as a function of the aging time: a) shellac, b) dammar, c) sandarac and d) mastic. The numbers 1 (black), 2 (red), 3 (green), 4 (blue) and 5 (magenta) indicate the degree of aging of each varnish sample as indicated in **Table 1**.

Multiphoton Excitation Fluorescence

The wavelength of the femtosecond laser (800 nm) is adequate for providing in depth information of the varnish layers since these are transparent at this wavelength. According to LIF results above, it is expected that absorption of two- and/or three-photons of 800 nm by the varnish will result in emission of fluorescence in the spectral collection range (335-610 nm).

The thicknesses of the varnish layers were measured by determining the dependence of the MPEF signal with the depth below the surface and compared with those obtained by OP.

Figure 3 shows the MPEF profiles from shellac samples subjected to different aging conditions. Differently from the typical top hat profile observed for fresh samples, the MPEF profiles display two differentiated zones, a maximum near to the surface, and a flat constant function deeper below. It is observed that the longer the aging time, the less extended the flat behavior is. This agrees well with what has been reported previously, i.e. that the degree of aging decreases with the distance from the surface due to the reduced probability of oxidation occurring in the inner layers of the film in comparison to the outer ones. The two regions of the profile are respectively attributed to the emission from the upper degraded layer and from the unaffected varnish layer underneath, where the thickness of each region could be determined by analyzing the MPFE profile. In turn, **Figure 3e**, Sh5 sample, with lower dry weight than sample Sh1 and expectedly thinner than the rest of shellac samples, shows a MPEF profile that is well represented by a function with a single maximum, indicating that the whole depth of the varnish layer is affected by aging. This result points to the influence of the initial varnish layer on the extent of deterioration induced by aging in agreement to previous studies.

Figure 3. MPEF in-depth profiles of shellac varnish samples subjected to different aging conditions. The grey stripes display the in-depth affected region obtained using a Lorentzian fit of this part of the MPEF profile. A top-hat fit of the total profile (dotted line) serves to determine the total thickness of the varnish layer. The indicated thickness values were corrected by the factor F (1.57) which considers the effective numerical aperture NA of the focusing objective lens (0.42) and the refractive index n of the analyzed material.

Dammar and sandarac show similar behavior as that described above for shellac, i.e., increase of thickness of the degraded layer with aging time and a thicker degraded layer for an initially thinner film. Despite this similarity, the extent of variations is different for each varnish. In turn, mastic do not seem to follow the trend described for the other three varnishes, as in this case the thickness of the degraded layer does not increase with artificial aging time.

Table 2 summarizes the results obtained and also compares the total thickness determined via MPEF with the values obtained by OP. It shows that longer times of exposure to artificial aging result in thicker degraded layers for shellac and dammar. In sandarac the thickness of the degraded layers remains almost constant in the range of exposure times, while in mastic the opposite trend is observed.

	Hours of artificial aging (+ 10 years of natural aging)	Thickness of total varnish by OP	Thickness of degraded varnish by MPEF	Thickness of total varnish by MPEF	Percentage of varnish thickness affected by degradation
Sh1	0	223 ± 15	20 ± 3	286 ± 2	7
Sh2	52	251 ± 5	20 ± 1	212 ± 2	9
Sh3	102	132 ± 3	28 ± 1	137 ± 3	20
Sh4	500	125 ± 3	39 ± 2	118 ± 1	33
Sh5	0	30 ± 1	38 ± 1	38 ± 1	100
D1	0	186 ± 6	29 ± 1	196 ± 7	15
D2	160	149 ± 3	32 ± 5	153 ± 9	21
D3	350	200 ± 2	33 ± 23	218 ± 14	15
D4	350	50 ± 1	43 ± 23	62 ± 13	69
D5	0	52 ± 4	57 ± 6	57 ± 6	100
S1	0	205 ± 24	43 ± 3	206 ± 10	21
S2	52	92 ± 19	33 ± 1	113 ± 3	29
S3	102	100 ± 12	44 ± 12	316 ± 5	14
S4	500	73 ± 2	38 ± 2	80 ± 7	47
S5	0	59 ± 2	35 ± 3	190 ± 15	18
M1	0	273 ± 1	47 ± 10	191 ± 39	24
M2	52	256 ± 9	45 ± 7	213 ± 29	21
M3	102	281 ± 2	42 ± 8	276 ± 4	15
M4	500	153 ± 2	29 ± 1	164 ± 2	18
M5	0	239 ± 2	38 ± 2	175 ± 28	22

Table 2. Average thickness values of artificial and natural aged varnish layers (in μm), as determined by OP and MPEF.

Results of **Table 2** also allow discussing the influence of the initial thickness of the varnish layer on the extent of degradation. Previous studies in dammar have shown that films thicker than 10 μm subjected to accelerated aging were less deteriorated than thinner films. This effect is clear for the naturally aged shellac and dammar samples of this study by means of the comparison between Sh1 and Sh5 and between D1 and D5. In these cases, the ratio of thickness

of the degraded layer vs total thickness increases from a value in the 7-15 %, for films in the 200 μm range, to a value of 100 % for films of 30-50 μm . This tendency is not observed for sandarac and mastic indicating the strong influence of the nature of the varnish in the involved processes.

1.6.5 Perspectives

In the present study, the extent of in-depth modifications induced on layers of the terpenoid varnishes shellac, dammar, sandarac and mastic, traditionally used in paintings, were investigated by nonlinear optical microscopy in the modality of multiphoton excitation fluorescence. Laser-induced fluorescence spectra, obtained upon laser excitation at 266 nm, yielded information about the surface structural and molecular composition and about the chemical changes derived from aging, and at the same time allowed the selection of the adequate MPEF measurement conditions.

We can conclude that the combination of the above techniques serves well to characterize superficial modifications and the extent of in-depth degradation and that the effects observed are strongly dependent of the nature of the varnish. For the four varnishes studied, the LIF results showed an increase of fluorescence intensity and a red shift of the maximum of the emission upon exposure to longer periods of artificial aging and for thinner layers, i.e., a longer aging time and an initially thinner layer leads to greater superficial degradation effects. In turn, the purely non-invasive NLOM-MPEF approach serves well to determine the initial thickness of varnish layers and the dependence of the degraded fraction with the aging time and with layer thickness. Specifically, it was possible to determine the thickness of the region below the varnish surface affected by aging by monitoring the increase of the MPEF signal and the change in the functional dependence with depth from the aged regions with regard to the non-aged ones. The NLOM-MPEF technique yielded values of initial thickness of the layers, that, except for some of the samples, showed good agreement with those retrieved by optical profilometry, thus validating the NLOM methodological approach and paving the way for future in-situ non-invasive stratigraphic investigations on heritage painting items. From this study we can extract some conclusions in relation to different behaviours observed for the four varnishes. Shellac and dammar show a higher stability against aging in comparison with sandarac and mastic due to their lower penetration depths for UV wavelengths. The results presented allow to extraction of useful indications for the conservation and restoration of paintings, as varnish thicknesses equal to or greater than 60 microns ensure better protection of the underlying paint layers

1.7 Monitoring potential CW and pulsed laser-induced damage on paintings with VIS-NIR Reflectance spectroscopy

1.7.1 Context and concept

The advancement in mobile ‘non-invasive’ analytical techniques has been a major technological contribution to the adoption of scientific analysis in the characterization of artists’ materials and their possible degradation products, owing to the ease of application to historical cultural assets *in situ*. Mobile instruments, such as portable Raman spectroscopy instruments, make use of intense VIS-NIR laser radiations. Despite it is known that intense radiations can increase the probability of damage on cultural heritage materials, research effort is still needed to better understand the radiation-matter interaction and identify the critical parameters. But most of all, due to the extremely high heterogeneity of artists’ materials, research effort should primarily aim at developing on-line monitoring methods to prevent damage and to better design strategies to reduce the risk associated with the use of such instruments.

Previous involvement of the team in the topic of radiation damage is represented by an extensive work in collaboration with FORTH (Liang et al., 2017) for the assessment of potential damages on paintings induced by lasers used in two imaging modalities: Optical Coherence Tomography and Non Linear Microscopy.

During the development of the in-house long range Raman spectroscopy system (3-15m) specifically designed for the analysis of architectural interiors by the ISAAC group at Nottingham Trent University (Li et al., 2019), an extensive survey over a range of common pigments was performed to assess the safety of the developed Raman system compared to other laser sources commonly used for Raman spectroscopy, both pulsed and continuous wave (CW) and both 532 nm and 785 nm. Fiber Optic Reflectance Spectroscopy (FORS) was deployed to carry out the monitoring before and straight after the laser irradiation on naturally aged (15 year old) paint mock-ups. Due to limited data on the damage threshold comparisons for CW and pulsed lasers on relevant materials, to better understand laser-induced degradation effects on common pigments and paints, laser irradiation experiments were designed using three types of laser sources to test the differences between pulsed and CW lasers at the same wavelength of 532 nm and between CW lasers at different wavelengths at 532 nm and 780 nm. Since larger laser spot sizes are employed in remote standoff Raman systems than those of micro-Raman systems typically used in cultural heritage research, the effects of spot size were also investigated in addition to that of intensity and fluence.

1.7.2 Monitoring protocol

All experiments were conducted at a distance of 4 m between the laser used and the test panel. The laser beam irradiates the vertically placed sample at normal incidence, while a retroreflective probe is aligned at 45° angle to the laser beam to collect reflectance spectra before and after the laser irradiation with an elliptical spot of 0.45 mm by 0.75 mm within the irradiated area of the sample. A low power tungsten halogen light (Mikropack DH-2000) was used as the illumination source for reflectance spectroscopy. The reflectance calibration was

performed against a Labsphere Spectralon white standard. Reflectance spectra were collected by a spectrometer (Ocean Optics HR2000) with an integration time of 200 ms, averaged for 10 times, amounting to 2 s for each measurement. To ensure stable light output, the tungsten halogen light was warmed up for 30 min before taking measurements. The stability of the illumination source was tested prior to the experiments by continuously monitoring the reflectance changes of the white standard until it stabilises, which usually takes 30 min. Reflectance spectra were recorded successively (every 2 s) for each sample before laser irradiation and again straight after the irradiation a consecutive series of reflectance spectra were collected over a period of 6 seconds to 5 minutes. Difference in reflectance spectra (ΔR) in the visible range (400–900 nm) for all the samples were monitored by subtracting the reflectance spectrum before the laser irradiation from the spectra collected after the irradiation.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the experimental setup for measuring laser-induced degradation effect in the paint samples (form Li et al., 2022).

1.7.3 Interpretation of results

The results of this extensive monitoring survey of various common pigments resulted in a publication (Li et al., 2022). Our combined setup of Raman and reflectance spectroscopy allows simultaneous interrogation of degradation effects at the same area to evaluate to what extent Raman spectroscopy can be used to effectively monitor laser induced degradation. We proved that due to the orders of magnitudes (ca. 10^6) lower Raman scattering efficiency compared to diffuse scattering measured by reflectance spectroscopy, in several cases subtle damages were not followed by any Raman spectral changes. It is also worth noting that for most of the irradiation tests, no visual changes were observable on the surface. Colour changes ΔE_{00} calculated from the reflectance spectra before and after laser irradiation, assuming CIE standard D65 illumination and the 1931 standard 2 degrees observer, it was found to be well below 1 and therefore not noticeable even under a microscope in almost all the cases. The only exception was in the case of realgar where the 532 nm CW laser caused a permanent change corresponding to a colour change ΔE_{00} of 1.3.

CW vs pulsed laser for safe Raman

In this study, the ns-pulsed laser with pulse duration of ~ 5 ns delivers at least 5 orders of magnitude higher intensity in one pulse than the CW laser, while the CW laser delivers 2–4

orders of magnitude more energy in 10-1800 s irradiation time than a single ns-pulse. CW lasers can have a measurement advantage of 6–8 orders of magnitude in efficiency for safe operation below the damage threshold, when compared with a typical ns-pulsed laser operating at a repetition rate of 1–100 Hz and pulse duration of ~ 5 ns, if the damage threshold in laser intensity (power per unit area) are at the same level for CW and pulsed lasers. However, this assumption is not true as we found that the intensity threshold for degradation is much higher for pulsed laser than CW laser. This is most likely because the heat generated in a pulse can be dissipated between the pulses.

532 nm vs 780 nm CW lasers

The difference in laser induced damage between 532 and 780 nm CW lasers was investigated, and it was found that the damage threshold for 780 nm is greater than 532 nm for all paints examined (azurite, red lead, realgar, vermilion and verdigris). Either no alteration or less alteration (e.g., reversible rather than permanent alteration) was observed when using 780 nm laser at the same or higher intensity and fluence than the 532 nm laser. This is perhaps not surprising for red lead, realgar and vermilion, since all have the typical ‘S’ shaped spectrum of semiconductors with point of inflection at >532 nm which means high absorption of light at 532 nm and low absorption at 780 nm. However, both azurite and verdigris have similar reflectance at the two wavelengths and neither have an absorption band at these wavelengths, but the shorter wavelength of 532 nm still has a lower damage threshold. It was found in one of our previous studies (Liang et al., 2017), materials that are transparent have the highest damage threshold and materials that are either highly absorbing or highly scattering have lower damage threshold. Absorption is not the only mechanism that determines the damage threshold.

Spot size effect

Laser-induced alteration threshold is found to be strongly dependent on the size of the irradiated area such that the threshold can be orders of magnitude higher for smaller spot size. We compared two sets of measurements on vermilion (light) oil paint with incident laser spot sizes of 0.88 mm and 0.04 mm and found that the intensity threshold for safe operation (i.e. no alteration including reversible ones) is at least 90 times higher for the smaller spot size than the larger one, which means that the system with the larger spot size is at most 5 times more efficient under safe operation below damage threshold compared with one using the smaller spot size, if we take the total laser energy incident at the sample to be proportional to the Raman signal and assuming the instrument efficiency to be the same for the two setups. With a larger spot size, more total energy will be delivered on the material which makes heat dissipation more difficult than that of a smaller area. Conventional wisdom of just considering intensity damage threshold is not sufficient, as that would have assumed that the thresholds are the same for both spot sizes and therefore the one with the larger spot would be able to safely gather ~ 480 times more Raman photons. Raman damage threshold in intensity and fluence need to be evaluated for different spot sizes.

1.7.4 Protocol limitations and advances

The use of fiber-based technique can potentially affect the stability of the measurement, that is why particular care must be done to assess the stability of the measurements with several control tests during the experiments. Being a point analysis, no spatial information is obtained. However, this FORS monitoring method represents an extremely useful, affordable, quick, in-situ monitoring well suited for *in situ* monitoring.

1.7.5 Perspectives

Raman spectroscopy did not detect laser-induced alteration that are easily detectable by reflectance spectroscopy. On the 13 common pigments surveyed, no alteration was detected in azurite, verdigris, Prussian blue, cochineal, lead white, and ultramarine, while reversible alteration was detected in red lead, realgar, vermilion, chrome yellow and indigo. This latter group have relatively high Raman scattering efficiency and typical integration time needed in Raman spectroscopy is much less than 60 s.

The choice of a CW laser for remote standoff Raman spectroscopy in cultural heritage applications was justified based on experimental determination of alteration thresholds of each material using a CW laser and a nanosecond pulsed laser at the same wavelength of 532 nm. Raman measurements using CW laser is always more efficient, that is shorter measurement time required for the same Raman signal collected, under safe operational limits.

In many irradiations' tests, a reversible damage was detected with FORS and it needs further investigation. Based on the interesting results of this study, we have started to explore the beam damage monitoring using VIS-NIR hyperspectral imaging.

1.8 Time and spatially resolved VIS-NIR hyperspectral imaging as a novel monitoring tool for laser-based spectroscopy to mitigate radiation damage on paintings

1.8.1 Context and concept:

The methods to assess the occurrence of laser-induced alteration on paintings are limited and none of them can predict damage. In the context of Raman spectroscopy for the analysis of historical paintings, visual inspection and Raman spectral changes can offer useful guidance for the detection of certain laser-induced damages, but they can be blind to physical changes (e.g., partial melting of the surface) and inter and intra molecular scale damage below detection limit.

At ISPC-CNR previous work concerning the surface temperature monitoring was extensively carried out for the control of the pulsed laser effect during Yb:YAG pulsed laser cleaning of graffiti from stone surfaces (Suzuki et al., 2023). The monitoring was performed *operando* with a thermal imaging camera and the correlation to specific laser-induced effects was successful in shedding light on the cleaning mechanisms of a new fiber laser system for the cleaning of architectural stone materials.

Based on this experience acquired at ISPC-CNR with thermal imaging and the above-described developed method of VIS-NIR reflectance spectroscopy carried out at NTU (sub-task and the resulted publication Li et al., 2022) we developed a combined multimodal imaging method to correlate the VIS-NIR reflectance changes with the surface temperature. VIS-NIR reflectance spectroscopy performed in imaging modality enables higher stability of the measurement itself compared to the fiber optic technique and it enables the simultaneous recording of the surrounding area where the photons are not involved. Moreover, apart from the monitoring method development we also focused on the physical-chemical characterization of the damaged surfaces and the assessment of the damage penetration depth.

We investigated the continuous wave (CW) laser irradiation (with 532, 785 and 1064 nm lasers) on 15 years old oil paint mock-ups designed to simulate a naturally aged oil painting on panel. The selected pigments (vermilion, realgar and red lead), reported as unstable to laser irradiation, were mixed with linseed oil and applied on a preparation layer of chalk in rabbit skin glue on a plywood substrate, with a resulted paint thickness of ca. 200 μ m. The pigments were selected to have similar reflectance spectra: all three pigments absorb at 532 nm while they are all strong scatterers at 785 and 1064 nm. Moreover, the pigments show different light and thermal stability, which are key material parameters that influence the occurrence of radiation damage. Realgar (As_4S_4) represents one of the most light-sensitive²⁶ and thermally unstable pigments (up to 200 °C), while vermilion (\square -HgS) represents a relatively light-stable pigment with a low thermal stability (300 °C); red lead (Pb_3O_4) is considered a relatively light-stable pigment with a high thermal stability (up to 600°C).

1.8.2 Monitoring protocol

To monitor CW laser-induced damage on these aged oil painting mock-ups a multimodal imaging approach (**FIG.2**) was developed to understand the time and spatial evolution and

types of laser-induced surface alterations, through simultaneous monitoring using visible and near infrared (VIS-NIR) reflectance hyperspectral imaging (HSI) and thermal imaging during Raman spectroscopy. For VIS-NIR Reflectance spectroscopy, a grating-based hyperspectral imaging system, developed in-house at the ISAAC laboratory at Nottingham Trent University, was deployed. This line-scan grating-based imaging system enables simultaneous monitoring of the changes within the laser spot and the surrounding area with a spatial resolution of $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ at a distance of 3.2 m of an area $30 \mu\text{m} \times 15000 \mu\text{m}$. As most thermal related damages dissipate heat from the irradiated area, the simultaneous monitoring of the surrounding area makes it possible to evaluate the extent of the damage as a function of temperature away from the laser spot, where no photons are directly involved allowing differentiation of changes caused by heat alone compared to those that involved photons.

The resultant physical and chemical changes were examined in detail by optical coherence tomography to assess changed in the optical properties of the surface, and synchrotron based micro-X-ray powder diffraction to ascertain the possible crystal modification of the pigments.

Fig. 2 The set-up for monitoring laser induced alterations and a brief description of instrument specifications. The enlarged picture of the sample shows the probing area for each technique: thermal imaging (dark blue box), hyperspectral imaging (HSI) slit (white rectangle) and the laser irradiation spot for Raman spectroscopy (yellow solid circle).

1.8.3 Interpretation of results

The results of this multimodal monitoring of CW laser irradiation of oil paint mock-ups resulted in a recent publication (A. Suzuki et al., 2024). The HSI was found to be the most sensitive in detecting laser induced alternations compared to conventional methods. It is orders of magnitude more sensitive than Raman spectroscopy and even synchrotron-based micro-X-ray powder diffraction. In cases of thermally driven alterations, transient and reversible reflectance changes (**FIG.3**) were found to be the first indications of laser-induced

modifications and can therefore be used as precursors to prevent damage. The identification of laser-induced damage threshold (LIDT) is generally performed on mock-ups and is assessed by varying laser power for a given setup and is expressed in terms of the minimum laser intensity at which damage is observed. The identification of LIDT on mock-ups is intrinsically an unreliable method owing to the highly heterogeneous nature of artists' materials. When dealing with Raman spectroscopy for sensitive materials, such as heritage objects, a balance must be struck between efficiency in collecting Raman photons and safe limits to avoid damage. Thanks to the reversible reflectance changes (ΔR) appearing prior to thermally dominated permanent damage, we can use this prediction marker to objectively define the safety threshold.

Fig. 3. The reversible ΔR as prediction marker: the ΔR VIS-NIR changes (1 s light blue, 5 s orange, 10 s yellow, 60 s green, 300 s dark blue) and initial reflectance spectrum (in red) of vermilion oil mock-up irradiated with the 785 nm laser with a laser spot of 900 μm for 10 s at increasing laser power: (a) 2.8mW, (b) 40 mW; (c) 60 mW; (d) 100 mW.

The heat accumulation induced by increased laser intensity is well known, but here we demonstrated that it is necessary to consider the combined effect of the 3 parameters, power, spot size, and exposure time, to define safety thresholds. Through this, some not so commonly known effects were found. The laser induced damage threshold, expressed in intensity, considerably decreases when using a larger spot size, that means that it is less safe to use a larger spot size for the same laser intensity. Prolonging the irradiation time does not necessarily increase the extent of damage. While prolonged exposure caused a significant increase in the extent of damage in a case where photochemical effect dominated, it did not increase the extent of damage in cases where the thermal effect dominated.

The three selected pigments present similar absorption and scattering properties in the VIS-NIR regime (absorbing at 532 nm and highly scattering at 785 and 1064 nm) but demonstrated different responses to laser irradiation. Red lead paint mock-up proved to be very resistant to the three lasers (532, 785 and 1064 nm) investigated, with no permanent damage detected in the survey (maximum laser power 100 mW, spot size between 40 and 1000 μm , max duration 450 s). The vermilion oil paint mock-up appeared to be damaged mainly by thermal effects, with 532 nm laser causing the highest temperature rise. The vermilion oil paint was heated up less than the vermilion powder and resulted in less damage under the same irradiation conditions. In the most severely darkened case, a very thin layer of black meta-cinnabar was formed. To a higher or lower extent, a superficial layer of pararealgar and intermediate phases

were produced when realgar was irradiated with 532 nm laser. With the predominant thermal effect induced by the 785 nm and 1064 nm lasers, realgar exhibited a relative stability to temperature rises. Overall, when irradiating with 785 nm and 1064 nm laser, the resultant temperature rise is highest on the vermilion mock-up, followed by realgar and then red lead. The surface temperature rises due to both absorption and scattering, and the kinetics of cooling are mainly related to the heat capacity of the irradiated materials. The lowest reported heat capacity is the one of vermilion, followed by realgar and then red lead with the highest heat capacity. These results indicate that both light stability and thermal stability are important in determining how sensitive a pigment is to laser irradiation.

1.8.4 Protocol limitations and advances

This multimodal approach represents a valuable source of information when exploring the different effects of irradiation parameter and materials' characteristics. The very high sensitivity of the reflectance monitoring is intrinsic in the technique itself. We consider this set-up suitable for a thorough lab-based study and assessment of radiation damage on a variety of artists' materials.

1.8.5 Perspectives

The multimodal imaging set-up is valuable for understanding and studying different damage mechanisms and contributes to the development of a safe analytical protocol for Raman spectroscopy on paintings. Due to the high sensitivity of the VIS-NIR reflectance spectroscopy technique and the spatial information obtained by the imaging modality, the method provides a very useful way to control in real time the possible damages induced by conventional CW laser sources commonly used for Raman spectroscopy of cultural heritage materials. We believe that this method could be very useful also for the monitoring of other types of radiation, such as X-ray, for safe analysis of paintings.

1.9 Gas desorption measurement of paint layers under proton analytical beam

1.9.1 Context and concept

The long history of the analysis of heritage objects using ion beams (IBA), notably using PIXE, PIGE, RBS and NRA methods [Calligaro and Dran 2015] has revealed the very sensitive nature of several classes of materials [Bertrand et al. 2023] and shed light on the fundamental mechanisms of modifications [Zucchiatti A and Agullo-Lopez 2012]. Most affected materials are organic compounds, and radiation-sensitive pigments such as lead white (lead carbonate), binders and supports [Calligaro et. al 2015]. While the IBA of organic materials is of limited interest, that of lead white pigment ubiquitous in painted works before the 19th century has been the subject of numerous studies to determine its origin and manufacturing techniques (Gonzalez et al. 2017). Lead white was also found to be highly sensitive to the proton beam. Several phenomena arise when the proton beam fluence exceeds $1 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. In those conditions, the absorbed dose induced in lead white calculated using the SRIM simulation code (Ziegler et al. 2010) is 50 kGy at the sample surface, and 250 kGy at the Bragg peak located at the end of the proton path (Figure 1a). For comparison, the fluence employed in routine spot PIXE analysis is generally more than $10 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ (e.g. 1 nA, 100 secs, 1 mm^2). It is also interesting to note that the gamma-irradiation of painting and parchment for conservation treatments has shown to induce modifications for absorbed doses above 10 kGy (Ponta et al. 2017).

Figure 1. a) Comparison of absorbed dose in lead white induced by $1 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ of 3 MeV protons (red line) and 10^{15} X-ray/ cm^2 (17 keV and 2.3 keV) (blue line). b) swelling induced in lead white paint layer for $10 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ of 3-MeV protons.

Several effects have been highlighted in lead white paint layers: the development of dark marks ascribed to coloured centres due defects creation in the lead white crystals, the production of $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ radicals [Gourier et al. 2018] and the desorption of gases resulting from the breakdown of the lead carbonates and of the binder. The irradiation effects are of two types: primary effects, considered here, and secondary effects resulting from a medium- and long-term

evolution of materials by slow kinetic mechanisms, in particular due to the activity of free radicals. Some of these effects are fully or partially reversible (colour centres) and may disappear over time or under UV illumination. The gas release of paint materials [Calligaro et al. 2015], also noted in other studies on the effect of ions on papers [Zucchiatti and Martina 2019] and parchment [Csepregi et al. 2022] results in the swelling of the sample that can be noted under the microscope (Figure 1b). The quantitative measurement of gases released by the target is of high importance since it allows targeting two distinct objectives. First, gain a deeper knowledge on the modification mechanisms by comparing the number of molecular fragments induced per each proton and the calculations of simulation codes. Second, gas desorption measurement could probably provide a quick and sensitive monitor of beam-induced damage during experiments. Indeed, the detection of gas species escaping from the target and collected in the surrounding atmosphere is likely to be faster and more sensitive than the direct measurements of faint modifications induced in the original material by molecular methods such as FTIR for example.

This work was conducted by researchers from the CNRS UAR 3506 Lab-BC - Laboratoire de développement instrumental et de méthodologies innovantes pour les Biens Culturels (formerly CNRS Fédération de recherche FR 3506 New AGLAE) with the collaboration the painting group of the C2RMF and of the SATIE Systèmes et Applications des Technologies de l'Information et de l'Energie, Cergy-Paris Université, CNRS UMR 8029 Cergy University, France.

The samples are mock-up paint layers made of pure lead white components: cerussite PbCO_3 , hereafter noted C and hydrocerussite $2(\text{PbCO}_3)\cdot\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$, hereafter noted HC, specially synthesized [Gonzalez et al. 2019] and mixed with a lipid binder (boiled linseed oil, hereafter noted LO) or a protein binder (fresh egg yolk, hereafter noted EY) in a 90/10 proportion in weight. They paint mixtures were applied on fused quartz support with a 130 μm thickness using an Erichsen applicator. The thickness of 130 μm were chosen to stop the beam in the paint layer.

Figure 2. Left, lead white paint layer ingredients. Right, paint layer mock-ups on fused quartz slides

1.9.2 Monitoring protocol

The irradiation cell

The desorbed gases are captured in a specially designed cell with controlled atmosphere where the target is placed and exposed to the proton beam. The cell is sealed and made of metal and glass, with an 8- μm Kapton window through which the proton beam can reach the target surface. The cell has an internal volume (90 ml) minimized to enhance the concentration of residual gas and features a sample holder for samples having a microscope slide size (75 x 25 mm). After target introduction, the cell is flushed with a pure neutral gas (He or N₂) at atmospheric pressure. The cell is installed at the exit of the external beam line (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Left, irradiation cell placed in at the exit of the external beam line. Right, paint layer mock-ups placed in the cell showing dark marks after irradiation over a 3 x 3 mm² area.

The cell was dimensioned to fit in the sample cabin of a FTIR spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer Frontier) and the infrared beam of a is sent through two NaCl optical windows, with an optimized geometry to minimize the contribution of the CO₂ present in air. The line of interest is 2349 cm⁻¹ for CO₂, and 2114 cm⁻¹ and 2170 cm⁻¹ for CO.

Figure 4. Left, irradiation cell placed the cabinet of the FTIR spectrometer for the measurement of CO₂ and CO. Right, the cell installed in the laser for GENS-LIBS analysis of hydrogen.

The same cell allows carrying out the GENS-LIB analysis of hydrogen. The pulsed laser beam is sent through the glass of the cell onto a pure aluminium metal target to induce the LIBS emission of the trapped gases (GENS-LIBS). The emission of hydrogen (H α line, 656.28 nm)

is collected through the glass of the cell walls and conducted to a grating spectrometer a gated sensor to collect the LIBS spectrum.

An inlet allows the injection of controlled microvolumes (e.g. 200 μl to 2000 μl) of reference gases (CO_2 , CO and H_2) to calibrate the sensitivity of the setup.

Proton irradiation and monitoring

The proton beam fluence was controlled using the external beam monitoring based upon the PIXE signal emitted by the Si_3N_4 exit window, and previously calibrated using an electrometer Keythley 6514. The beam fluence was adjusted by scanning the selected beam dose across a $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ area. The applied fluences were 10, 20, 40 and 80 $\mu\text{C}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ of 3-MeV protons. For example, to obtain a 40 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ fluence, we irradiated a $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ area with 3.6 μC using a beam of 3 nA intensity during 20 min.

1.9.3 Interpretation of results

Measurement of CO_2 and CO by FTIR

The FTIR spectra were acquired applying 100 scans totalling 15 minutes. The CO_2 correction of the instrument was disabled and the blank spectra taken after careful purging. The absorption line intensity subsequent to injection of 200 μl of CO_2 was 0.25. After irradiation of pure pigment pellets with a fluence of 40 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, the intensity of the CO_2 absorption line was 0.017 for C and 0.008 for HC. A similar difference was observed on the paint layers, the absorption for HC+LO being 0.07 and C+LO around 0.03. Hence it can be estimated that the emission of CO_2 is about twice that of HC-containing targets than for C-containing targets, corresponding to about 16 μl for HC+LO and 8 μl C+LO. The corresponding volumes of CO_2 outgassed at 40 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ corresponds to ca. $1/1000^{\text{th}}$ in terms of concentration in the cell. This leaves a good margin of manoeuvre to progress since there exist security gas sensors able to reach ppm level. Another interesting result is that the measured number of CO_2 molecules produced per impinging protons amount to several thousands. Those numbers have to be compared to dynamic molecular models. The CO absorption signal is much weaker than that of CO_2 but was clearly identified.

Figure 5. Left, irradiation cell placed schematic. Right, FTIR spectra recorded for 40 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ proton fluence on C and HC targets and after injection of 200 μl of CO₂ gas.

Measurement of H-containing gas by GENs-LIBS

Lead white paint layers contains hydrogen: hydrocerussite $2(\text{PbCO}_3) \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$, and linseed oil as well as egg yolk used in the binding media. Linseed oil is composed of polyunsaturated fatty acids, particularly, linolenic acid ($\text{H}_3\text{C}-(\text{CH}_2)_4-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-(\text{CH}_2)_7-\text{COOH}$). These materials can decompose under proton beams into carbon, oxygen, and hydrogen atoms which can transform into a gaseous state, based on their chemical composition through radiolysis to species containing C, O and H.

The newly introduced GENs-LIBS utilizes the plume generated on the metal surface to excite these elements in gas and achieve accurate detection. When a laser pulse is directly focused into the gas, plasma generation occurs only when the laser intensity is above the breakdown threshold for gas ionization. Multiphoton ionization is the only remaining phenomenon in a gas, and it essentially depends on the ionization potential of the element in question and its density at the focusing surface. The difference in breakdown between gases is a function of the ionization potential. A UV laser is well adapted for this task due to its high photon energies. We have used a 1064-nm Nd: YAG laser operated at a 20 Hz repetition rate, pulse duration of 6 ns. A plano-convex lens with a 30-cm focal length was used to focus the laser beam onto the sample, which provided an interaction zone of approximately 120 μm in diameter on the aluminum plate. Twenty laser shots, each with a fluence of 88 J/cm^2 were used to ablate the aluminum plate at the same point (1 sec total). The plasma emission was directed by a plano-convex lens towards the entrance slit of a spectrometer, which featured a Czerny-Turner spectrograph (iHR320, HORIBA Scientific) coupled with an ICCD camera (DH340T-18F-E3, Andor Technology). An optical grating, with 300 lines per millimeter blazed at 500 nm, was employed to record the H α hydrogen line at 656.2 nm. The gas of the cell was also measured (helium line at 667.9 nm and nitrogen line at 744.2 and 746.8 nm).

Figure 6. Right, diagram of the cell containing the analyzed sample and a pure aluminum plate inserted inside. Left, picture of GENS-LIBS experimental setup

The hydrogen content was calibrated by injection of a controlled microvolume of hydrogen (1 ml and 2 ml) after the measurement of hydrogen desorption by the target.

Figure 7. Left, atomic emission lines from HC+LO before (dotted line) and after (solid line) irradiation with $40 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ in helium atmosphere. Right, calibration curve and 95% confidence band with the experiment data. The intensity of the hydrogen line was normalized to that of the helium line on the sample of HC pellet and HC+LO.

As shown in Figure 7, the quantity of hydrogen released in the cell could efficiently be measured for fluences of 20 and $40 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. At $40 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, the measured volume of hydrogen-bearing gas corresponds to about 1 ml of H_2 . However, a spurious signal of hydrogen possibly due to water deposited at the surface of the sample hampered the detection for proton fluences at $10 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and below. This limitation is going to be improved in the future. The new GENS-LIBS methodology was published (Bai et al, 2024).

1.9.4 Protocol limitations and advances

The protocol was developed to explore the gas desorption and define the level of sensitivity required to detect the beam induced modifications at an early stage. The desorption of CO₂ and hydrogen-bearing gases was efficiently measured for fluences above 10 μC/cm². The sensitivity of the FTIR method must be improved to identify smaller outgassing occurring at lower fluences (e.g. 1 μC/cm²). While the employed gas detection methods are quantitative and easily implemented, they are slow (especially FTIR) and cannot be carried out at the same place and at the same moment as the irradiation. The FTIR is sensitive to spurious CO₂, and require careful purging between measurements. The novel GENS-LIBS was developed offers a fast method (response in one second) but cannot differentiate among hydrogen-containing gas released (H₂, H₂O, CH₄...) and can be affected by the contribution of water trapped on surfaces and water vapour in the atmosphere. The novel GENS-LIBS technique will be improved and the molecular detection in the IR transposed in a dedicated experimental arrangement for specific gases using commercial gas leak sensors.

1.9.5 Perspectives

The gas desorption from paint layers might provide a valuable indicator of the modifications induced by the analytical proton beam in fragile paint materials. The advantage is that the detection could be implemented by analysing in real-time the atmosphere surrounding the beam impact to detect modifications at an early level. The different solutions for the detection of desorbed gas will be evaluated to design beam damage monitors that will be implemented in the new beam line of the AGLAE particle accelerator of the C2RMF developed in the framework of the Equipex+ ESPADON project (ANR 21-ESRE-00050).

1.10 Ion Beam Analysis of parchments

1.10.1 Context and concept:

Ion beam analysis plays an important role in cultural heritage (CH) studies as it offers a combination of simultaneous and complementary analytical techniques (PIXE/PIGE/RBS) and spatially resolved mapping functions. Despite being considered non-destructive, the potential risk of beam-induced modifications during analysis is increasingly discussed.

This work focuses on the impact of proton beams on parchment, present in our CH in form of unique historical manuscripts. Parchment is one of the organic, protein-based CH material believed to be the most susceptible to radiation-induced changes.

Parchment is basically composed of collagen type I. Collagen consists of amino acids sequences (mainly glycine-proline-X or glycine-X-hydroxyproline (X: another amino acid)). Three polypeptide chains are twisted and form triple-helix molecules, which then further arrange together to form fibrils (10-100 nm in diameter), fibres and finally the tissue (Kennedy & Wess, Restaurator 2003).

Sample studied were prepared at the Rathgen Forschungslabor (RF), SPK, Berlin. They consist of fresh parchment from calf skin provided by Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin (SBB), 150 – 370 μm thick. Paints of ultramarine blue pigment mixed with gum Arabic powder (Kremer Pigmente) were applied.

Figure 1. *The external micro-beam set-up used for the irradiations*

Figure 2. Photographs of samples taken just after irradiation. Scale bars are 1 mm. Red rectangles = irradiated areas.

Irradiations were performed at Institute for Nuclear Research (ATOMKI), Debrecen, Hungary with 2.3 MeV protons, 0.5 nA beam current, 100 x 100 μm^2 beam size, an irradiated area of 3.1 x 3.1 mm^2 and beam fluences of : 0.5, 1, 4, 10 C/cm^2 (Török et al., NIMB 2015).

1.10.2 Monitoring protocol

We studied the modifications after the irradiation. The analytical techniques used for characterization of changes are:

- Optical microscopy at RF Berlin using a digital microscope Keyence VHX-500FD, 100x to 700x magnification
- ESEM at RF Berlin, Quanta 200 from FEI, accelerator voltage 15 kV, spot size 6.0 or 7.0 nm, emission current 100 μA , 0.53-0.82 Torr, XFlash 4010 (Bruker AXS Inc)
- FTIR at BESSY II/HZB Berlin, IRIS beamline, Nicolet 8700 spectrometer coupled with a Nicolet Continuum Infrared microscope (ThermoFisher Scientific), 32x objective, High Pressure Diamond Optics
- FITR-ATR at ATOMKI; Bruker Alpha
- Bath test. At ATOMKI

A H_2O_2 solution was used to check the effect of an oxidizing agent on the discoloration. However, a gentle stroke with a cotton bud resulted in removing some material from the surface of samples irradiated with higher doses, which was obvious for painted samples. Immersion of the samples in the solution eliminated the additional mechanical interference of stroking. The immersion in liquid resulted in clearly visible marks for higher doses, 2 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and upwards, as shown in Figure 3. Furthermore, addition of H_2O_2 , which was of interest in relation with colour, was found to be not necessary, distilled water was sufficient to remove some of the irradiated collagen from the parchment pieces.

Figure 3. Parchment sample which underwent a short bath (5 minutes) in 3% H_2O_2 solution. Accumulated charge: 2, 3 (upper left and right spots), 4 and 5 (lower left and right spots) $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, current 1 nA). The parchment sample is illuminated from below. The photo was taken after drying.

OCT is a prototype high resolution portable SdOCT instrument built under EU FP7 CHARISMA Programme, Institute of Physics, Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics, Nicolaus Copernicus University, ul. Grudziądzka 5, 87-100 Toruń, Poland

The OCT technique was employed for a limited set of samples to semi quantitatively examine the modification of the samples caused by the irradiation. This technique could reveal the properties of the “crater” formed in the irradiated parchment samples, which suffered the short immersion in water, either with or without H₂O₂.

1.10.3 Interpretation of results

Optical micrographs and BSE-ESEM images of parchment cross-sections before irradiation and after irradiation with proton beam fluences of 1, 4 and 10 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ show the proton beam-induced modifications (Figure 4). The beam penetrated from the bottom side. The scale bars are 100 μm . The white dotted lines indicate the borders of the cross-sections. Red lines and arrows = zone in which changes were observed, dashed line in dark gray = areas with denatured gel-like structure, light blue circles = cavities, yellow dot-dash line = area displaying discoloration (Figure 2., Müller, Szikszai *et al.* Scientific Reports 2022).

Figure 4. Optical micrographs and BSE-ESEM images of parchment cross-sections before irradiation and after irradiation with proton beam fluences of 1, 4 and 10 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$

The results show that the parchment without paint forms holes with diameters: $< 10 - 20 \mu\text{m}$, $0 - 100 \mu\text{m}$ deep into the sample. There is a transformation to gel-like structure.

The parchment with blue pigment layer shows formation of blisters/holes direct under or within the paint layer, of holes ($10-20 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter), melting of collagen fibers from the surface to $50-80 \mu\text{m}$ deep into the sample and possibly diffusion of pigment grains deeper into the parchment?

The investigations showed considerable modifications detected up to $100 \mu\text{m}$ deep into the sample for beam fluences of $4 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and higher. The presence of ultramarine paint on the parchment surface appears to increase the harmful effects of proton radiation. The molecular structure stays principally preserved. Based on our results, a maximum radiation dose of $0.5 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ can be considered as ‘safe boundary’ for PIXE analysis of parchment under the applied conditions (Müller, Szikszai *et al.* Scientific Reports 2022 and Csepregi, Szikszai *et al.* Heritage Science 2022).

Attenuated Total Reflection Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) was employed semi-quantitatively at ATOMKI to characterize alterations of parchment collagen and, thus, to gain insight on the mechanism (see previous chapter as well as Csepregi, Szikszai *et al.* Heritage Science 2022). These measurements were performed on the intact (not sectioned) samples, on the surface in first contact with the beam and covered additional fluences compared to the range specified for the SEM observations. The FTIR-ATR results were corroborated by a second series of irradiation on goat parchment.

In addition, immersion in liquid (water or hydrogen-peroxide solution) proved to be a useful method to magnify the effect of ion beams on the parchment samples. For higher doses, the damage was obvious (Fig. 5), for lower doses digital microscopy and optical coherence tomography (Fig. 6) was employed.

Figure 5. After a 5-minute immersion in a 3% H_2O_2 solution; fluence: $5 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. The whole irradiated area is affected.

Figure 6 OCT cross-sectional image of a parchment area subjected to $1 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ proton fluence at 500 pA, and immersed in 3% H_2O_2 solution for 5 min. The image is strongly expanded in a vertical (in depth) direction and shows a window of $7 \text{ mm} \times 0.70 \text{ mm}$ size. (Csepregi, Szikszai et al. Heritage Science 2022)

The observations after the immersion test showed that fluences of $2 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and above was undoubtedly damaging, while $0.5 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ seemed to be safe for the test material used in our study. As for $1 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, a tiny hole developed. It must be remarked that although the most important parameter is the applied fluence, other circumstances such as the current might also influence the extent of changes of the material.

1.10.4 Protocol limitations and advances

- Influence of further pigments need to be studied.
- Irradiation conditions extend beyond the usual, albeit the higher fluences are useful to study the mechanisms.
- Other variables than fluence were only tentatively considered
- Further work on mock-ups is required.
- Ideally, irradiations should be monitoring in operando. However, as ions deposit the majority of their energies just before stopping (Fig. 7), i.e. below the surface, monitoring the changes with surface techniques underestimates the harm.
- The parchment samples were freshly made, artificial aging could be applied.
- The attempts to study the effects of ions inside the material without causing further harm have been unsuccessful, further efforts are needed

Figure 7. *Simulated energy loss of 2.3 MeV protons along their path in the parchment (blue) and their actual energy (red)*

1.10.5 Conclusions and Perspectives

Ion beam analysis is mostly applied to inorganic materials, and aptly so. Organic materials should be treated with extreme caution, especially thin organic materials, when a small spot of damage can develop into an actual hole in the sample. The efficiency of signal detection is of utmost importance to reduce the fluence required for a meaningful analytical signal. As in situ monitoring with surface techniques underestimates the harm caused by ions deeper in the material, these are mainly useful for mechanically quite robust samples when the main concern is aesthetic, such as changes in colour, not the integrity of the whole object. Therefore, experimental work on mock samples to estimate the possible harm below the surface is required. We used freshly prepared mock samples, artificial aging either before or after the irradiation is envisaged to better cover the possible range of sensitivity of parchment. As a body of historic parchment samples has already been measured in various laboratories around world, an inspection of the records of the experimental parameters can be useful to infer the assumable effects. For future analysis, a strict limit to fluence is advisable.

1.11 Post-irradiation survey on organic materials to establish chemical mechanisms induced under ionizing irradiation

1.11.1 Context and concept

There are plenty of cultural heritage objects created on organic base such as textiles, paper or parchment. For a long time, only the upper layers of these objects were investigated with the aim of getting information about the material composition of the paint or ink, which were used for the preparation of the artefact. However, the organic materials can also be important for the interpretation of the object itself. Furthermore, the base material may be harmed by the often non-destructive investigative techniques (PIXE, XRF, etc.) used to analyze the artefacts. Consequently, it is recommended to investigate the effects of ionizing radiation on organic materials considered as models for cultural heritage objects.

The investigations' goal was to attempt structural change elucidation to look into how various high purity organic chemical species were affected by ionizing radiation, predominantly proton beams. Several types of chemicals (e.g., sugars, amino acid, proteins) as building block models of complex organic matrices were irradiated at similar charge densities. Chemical modification of the distinct structural complexity levels was monitored by SDS-PAGE, liquid based separation methods, mass spectrometry in close collaboration with Horváth Csaba Memorial Laboratory of Bioseparation Sciences (Debrecen, Hungary), FTIR and Raman microscopy. In situ monitoring of discoloration was also performed - where applicable - during some of the irradiation campaigns. Throughout the investigation it became obvious, that the identification of radiation-induced structural changes in the mockup matrix is too laborious, necessitating isolation and simplification of individual representative organic compound types and their analysis from a complex cultural heritage item matrix. Therefore, the protein like structures (demonstrating “mid level” complexity) were investigated using analytical grade glycoprotein standards at 2 different sizes (Fetuin = ~ 50 kDa, RNase B = ~15 kDa). For both proteins noticeable band broadening started to appear from 1-2.5 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. The polysaccharide type of cultural heritage materials were considered as carbohydrates (N-glycans of the mentioned glycoproteins). For the N-glycans the apparent change was observed from ~2.5 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. The lowest level of complexity was represented by the irradiation of alanine molecules as amino acid monomers of important protein (e.g., fibroin) molecules. The post irradiation analysis showed alterations of the alanine molecules from 1 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. High level complexity cultural heritage analog material was modelled by irradiating calf and goat skin parchments. The irradiated high level complexity material was investigated using ATR-FTIR and Raman microscopy concluding that from 2 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ charge density, proton beam alters the amide I and II bands.

1.11.2 Monitoring protocol

Glycoprotein irradiation and monitoring

Ribonuclease B and Fetuin glycoproteins, procured from Sigma-Aldrich (St Louis, MO, USA), were dissolved in HPLC grade water at a concentration of 30 mg/mL before proton irradiation. The Fast Glycan Labeling and Analysis kit from SCIEX (Brea, CA, USA) was utilized during sample preparation. PNGase F endoglycosidase enzyme was sourced from New England Biolabs (Ipswich, MA, USA). Capillary electrophoresis with laser induced fluorescence

detection (CE-LIF) based separations were conducted using either 10 or 50 cm effective length (50 μm id) capillary columns in the PA 800 plus CE unit (SCIEX). The experimental approach was guided by our previously published study on the impact of simulated space radiation on the N-glycosylation of human Immunoglobulin G glycoprotein (10.1002/elps.201800151). Glycoprotein irradiations occurred in high vacuum using dry glycoprotein samples. Specifically, glycoprotein droplets (6 μL of 30 mg/mL) were desiccated on glass slides to form spots approximately 5 mm in diameter with a thickness of around 10 μm . These slides were then positioned perpendicular to the beam at the HUN-REN Institute for Nuclear Research (Debrecen, Hungary) within a high vacuum environment ($\sim 10^{-7}$ mbar) and subjected to a 2 MeV energy proton beam. Based on calculations, charge densities ranged from 0.1 to 30 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. Simulations indicated uniform energy loss throughout the sample depth, with protons penetrating through the dry glycoprotein and being absorbed approximately 48 μm deep into the glass plate. Irradiations were performed at both lower (0.5 nA beam current) and higher (40 nA beam current) doses, with careful design to ensure linear and constant energy loss of protons throughout the sample volume. Notably, the high-energy loss region of the proton path, known as the Bragg-peak, remained within the sample holder, thereby avoiding direct stopping within the samples. Following irradiation, the samples were transferred to the bioseparation lab and reconstituted in 6 μL of HPLC grade water prior to SDS-PAGE and subsequent glycan release and fluorophore labeling.

Alanine irradiation and monitoring

For the amino acid irradiation, 100 μm thick 1 mm diameter alanine (Avantor Sciences, Radnor, PA, USA) pastilles were prepared. During this irradiation campaign the alanine samples were placed in front of the extracted proton beam provided by the millibeam setup (10.1039/D2JA00291D) in such a way that the 2.67 MeV protons deliberately stopped and therefore deposited their full kinetic energy within the samples. Irradiations were performed at approximately 10 nA beam current. Once the irradiations were completed, the samples were transferred for CE-LIF analysis. Prior to separation a modified version of Creamer et al (10.1021/acs.analchem.6b04338) sample preparation and fluorescent labeling was performed. Additionally offline ESI-MS measurements of the irradiated samples were carried out.

Calf-skin parchment irradiation and monitoring

The first parchment irradiations, specifically on calf skin were carried out utilizing the external microprobe (10.1016/j.nimb.2015.09.062) of HUN-REN ATOMKI. A focused proton beam, with a diameter of 100 microns, had exited through a thin Si_3N_4 window from the vacuum chamber and systematically traversed over an area of approximately 0.1 cm^2 . The protons had an energy of 2.3 MeV upon contact with the parchment samples. The applied currents varied at 250 pA, 500 pA, and 1 nA, while the accumulated charges ranged from 25 to 1000 nC within a spot measuring approximately 3.1 mm \times 3.1 mm, corresponding to a charge density of 0.25–10 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. Each irradiated region was compared with an equivalent non-irradiated section on the respective parchment piece. Typically, each piece of parchment contained 3–4 irradiated spots. Further irradiation experiments on calf-skin parchment took place within the same vacuum chamber setup, maintaining a pressure of approximately 10^{-7} mbar during the experiments.

Goat-skin parchment irradiation and monitoring

To increase robustness of the measurements in the case of goat skin mockup parchment samples, two special sample holder concepts were developed to provide A.) „same spot” type FTIR analyses of the parchments to evaluate the radiation induced changes compared to the specific sample’s own reference state prior to irradiation as shown in Figure 1A. In these cases,

the proton beam incident was perpendicular to the sample surface. The beam size was approximately 2 mm x 2 mm. In the other concept *B.*) the samples were arranged in a multi-sheet, "sandwich" manner. Sandwich samples were positioned in front of the in-air extracted proton beam to achieve a particle incidence that was tangential to the sample surface. This layout is shown in Figure 1B. Handmade goat skin parchment from KareDeri (Istanbul, Turkey) was used with a thickness of 440-480 μm for the measurements as targets. The energy of the protons was 3.6 MeV at contact with the parchment samples. The changes induced by radiation were expressed as the deposited charge per unit area for each sample (0.125, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 10 and 20 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$). FTIR measurements were carried out with a diamond-headed Bruker Alpha type, attenuated total reflection Fourier transform infrared spectrometer equipped with a DLaTGS detector (4 cm^{-1} resolution). Data were collected before and after the irradiation and were analyzed using Opus 7.5 software. Raman measurements were performed on a Renishaw InVia Raman microscope (Wotton-under-Edge, United Kingdom) in the 1100–2000 Raman shift/ cm^{-1} range using 785 nm CW laser.

Video analysis of irradiation induced color change was possible through the use of the millibeam setup (10.1039/D2JA00291D). Image analysis to determine the dynamics of the color change during irradiations was carried out using ImageJ software (doi:10.1038/nmeth.2089). In situ monitoring of the visible spectrum of the target during IBA or X-ray based analytical measurements can be accomplished even by simple video microscopy as demonstrated in Figure 4.

Figure 1A: Sample holder to provide „same spot” type FTIR analyses of the parchments; 1B: Multi-sheet, "sandwich" type sample holder

1.11.3 Interpretation of results

Glycoprotein irradiation and monitoring

SDS-PAGE analysis showed only increased smearing skewed towards the smaller size band range as a function of charge density only hinting on the fragmentation of the initial glycoprotein molecules both in the cases of fetuin and RNaseB. However, the released, labeled and separated N-glycans showed noticeable decrease in the charge-to-size ratio of the irradiated samples indicating the appearance and increase of N-glycans consisting of fewer sugar monomers as a function of administered dose, but only from 1 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and above.

Amino acid irradiation and monitoring

Pacific Blue labeling of amino acids involves forming stable amide bonds with amino groups ($-\text{NH}_2$) of the amino acids and the Pacific Blue dye molecules, resulting in the covalent attachment of the fluorescent dye to the amino acid. Since the separations showed the appearance of stable radicals in a dose dependent manner, the fragments are produced through the interaction of the proton beam with alanine molecules involving probable decarboxylation reactions. The irradiated alanine molecules all showed consecutive dose dependent (1, 2, 4 and 20 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) appearance of radicals starting from 1 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. Moreover offline, unlabeled ESI-MS analysis showed several fragments showing up between 30-89 m/z values supporting the results obtained by CE-LIF separation of the irradiated alanine samples.

Calf-skin parchment irradiation and monitoring

Parchment, primarily composed of type I collagen, is a protein-based material. At the molecular level, collagen consists of three polypeptide chains that assemble into a trimeric structure. These chains intertwine to form a triple helix. Collagen degradation is typically characterized by three main processes elucidated in literature: denaturation or gelatinization, involving the unfolding of the triple helix; hydrolysis and oxidation of the polypeptide chains, which can result in bond cleavage and collagen molecule breakdown. In the context of collagen, critical absorption and Raman bands include amide I, II, III, A, and B. The amide I band corresponds to the stretching vibration of $\text{C}=\text{O}$, with some contribution from CN stretching. Amide II is primarily associated with NH bending and CN stretching. Peak areas were determined by integrating absorbance values within specific wavenumber ranges: 1480 to 1580 cm^{-1} for amide II and 1580 to 1700 cm^{-1} for amide I. The maximum intensity of the amide I band was observed at approximately 1632 cm^{-1} , while the maximum intensity of the amide II band was around 1538 cm^{-1} . Analysis of the FTIR-ATR spectra revealed an increase in the distance between the absorbance peaks of amide I and amide II for samples subjected to collected charges of 5 and 10 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ across all three currents, and also for those with 3-4 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ at the lowest current (250 pA). The amide II peak shifted from the range of 1534–1540 cm^{-1} to 1522 cm^{-1} , indicating a transition from a more ordered to a more disordered structural state. These observations align with existing literature on the effects of mixed light-thermal aging on collagen-based materials like parchment or leather. Notably, there appears to be a slight reduction in the contribution of the amide II peak in irradiated samples compared to non-irradiated ones, possibly attributed to structural scission of the amide group or loss of collagen's triple helical or secondary structure. These chemical or structural alterations result in decreased intermolecular crosslinking, potentially weakening the material. Definitive changes in the FTIR spectra were observed particularly at high doses, such as 5 and 10 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$.

Goat-skin parchment irradiation and monitoring

During the continuation of our work on parchment, we still focused on the bands of amide I and II, as these are the most discussed bands in the context of cultural heritage studies (Figure 2). Our results show good correlation with our previous measurements, namely the 4-20 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ dose range alters the amide I and II bands the most similarly, despite using goatskin parchment this time. Extended with the sandwich type arrangement, strong correlation can be found with previous (Calf-skin) FTIR data on the intensity and the wavenumber shifts of amide bands.

Figure 2: FTIR spectra of the bands of amide I and II after irradiation with different charge densities

Figure 3: Raman spectra on the sandwich type sample arrangement measurements were performed along the longitudinal axis of the sample sheet surfaces starting from the edges

Video microscopy

The discoloration was primarily caused by the chemical effect of the ion beam on the organic material. During the excitation and ionization by the proton beam, organic radicals, double bonds and other conjugated bond systems are formed, as a result of which the substance absorbs light in the visible range as well. The material can relatively easily return to its original state through recombination or reaction with oxygen, causing the yellowish color to disappear. The yellowing was observed on the surface of the parchment during the irradiations, the dynamics of these events are shown in Figure 4. The relatively high intensity values represent the white parchment before irradiation. As the irradiation progressed, the color deconvolution optimized for the yellow signal indicated a well defined drop in signal intensity, thereby designating the “moment of discoloration”.

Figure 4: Monitoring of the surface yellowing

All the above performed measurements suggest less than an order of magnitude lower charge densities to be delivered to the samples in order to reach the sensitivity limit of the above listed techniques and cases. It implies the use of detector clusters in the case of IBA, to improve the solid angle parameters and therefore decrease the analytically required dose.

1.11.4 Protocol limitations and advances

Due to the insolubility of the collagen in water, developing an appropriate methodology to separate and identify irradiation-induced structural changes in that complex matrix can be difficult and time-consuming. So, we attempted to reduce the complexity to individual organic compounds which can represent simplified characteristic levels of the complex material. Glycoprotein standards served as protein-like structures, glycans represented the polysaccharide-type objects and amino acids indicated the lowest level of complexity. This approach (the separation of a complex matrix to distinct levels of structural maturity) could be further developed by utilizing analytical grade complex matrix standards if available.

SDS-PAGE was used to detect the alterations inside the molecular structure of the protein components of the glycoproteins, however, this technique has low resolution so it in essence can be used only for detecting the presence of the main molecules in question. Other protein identification methods should be developed, in our suggestion CE-SDS-MS based analysis, to have the highest possible separation resolution available, to be able to see the modifications occurring in the structure of the proteins and to streamline the whole measurement process.

CE-LIF was capable of detecting the glycan modifications and the appearing structures generated by the radiation, however for the proper identification of the novel glycans the procurement of standard materials would have been necessary. Since radiation produced standards might be hard to obtain, an online structural database of CE-LIF-MS based glycan (or saccharide) measurements should be constructed and employed in the future.

FTIR and Raman spectroscopy are highly surface sensitive techniques, hence investigating alterations impacting the deeper regions of the samples necessitated the use of other examination techniques such as OCT. However, OCT - just as the aforementioned techniques - has limited resolution. Nevertheless, FTIR proven to be useful in monitoring the changes occurring in the organic matrices.

Unfortunately, no significant change was observed between the Raman spectra recorded on the sandwich type sample arrangement along the longitudinal axis of the sample sheet surfaces starting from the edges (Figure 3). A more robust scanning type analysis is needed for the evaluation of the samples.

Please note, that during the mentioned studies the charge densities were similar but the absorbed doses were apparently not. This also implies the necessity to perform systemic studies where not only charge densities are in sync, but the administered doses are as well, even if simplification and modeling is very much needed and unavoidable at complexity levels, where unknown radicals are hunted for in such an analytically diverse molecular environment.

1.11.5 Perspectives

FTIR microscopy performed on mock-up cross sections could reveal in more detail the chemical changes happening along the path of decelerating protons. The combination of artificial aging and proton irradiation/X-ray would provide further information on the susceptibility of old historical organic artefacts to IBA/ionizing radiation-based techniques. Knowledge of the effects of proton beam can help develop guidelines for safe PIXE/XRF analysis of unique and sensitive organic compound containing objects such as historical manuscripts. Furthermore, such studies are essential for the better understanding of degradation phenomena and for the development of appropriate conservation measures in the future.

1.12 Assessing the impact of irradiation of various archaeological materials with neutrons

1.12.1 Context and concept

At the Budapest Neutron Centre, we analyze various types of archaeological material in order to obtain information about their chemical (elemental or isotopic) composition or about their structure.

To obtain information, spectroscopic data are collected following various reactions of neutrons with the atomic nuclei of the samples. One of the typical reactions is the radiative capture of neutrons, when a low energy neutron is captured by the target nucleus. As a result of the capture, in many instances, the produced nucleus is radioactive, i.e. it irradiates further type(s) of ionizing radiation, typically β or γ radiation. Two questions emerge, when we investigate the possible effects of these nuclear reactions.

- 1, Whether the resulted modification of the original sample's material is significant enough to show any prompt or late, visible or invisible changes in the sample's appearance (in their colour, in their consistence, etc.)
- 2, Whether the induced radioactivity of the samples reaches a level that might be harmful to the human health, and how quick is the induced radioactivity decays.

We have investigated both topics for some typical kind of archaeological materials and for some typical irradiation conditions at various instruments of the BNC used in HS studies. We have studied the effect of irradiations at the instruments of PGAA, SANS, RAD, NAA and also the effects of irradiation with 2.5 MeV proton beam at the Budapest PIXE facility.

The modification of the samples' materials has been studied using test samples made of unpainted and painted parchments, as pigments are considered ones of the most sensitive indicators for damages induced by various (electromagnetic or particle) irradiations. The irradiation conditions of the parchments are summarized in Table 1.

Following the irradiation, FTIR investigation of the samples was done at the Institute of Materials and Environmental Chemistry, Research Centre for Natural Sciences, Budapest. All samples were measured within 1 day after irradiation apart from NAA irradiated samples which show high level of radioactivity. The irradiation conditions are summarized in Table 1.

	PGAA*	RAD	NAA	SANS *	PIXE**
Beam:	$9.6 \cdot 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$3.4 \cdot 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$2.5.7 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$5 \cdot 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
	K. Zs., Sz.L.	K. Z.	G. K.	L. A.	K. I.
	P1 1 h	R1 10 min	N1 30 s	S1 10 min	X1 5 min
16 pcs	P2 3 h	R2 130 min	N2 300 s	S2 2 h	X2 10 min
	P3 24 h	R3 24 h	N3 10800 s		X3 30 min
	0 blank				
	P1 1 h	R1 10 min	N1 30 s	S1 10 min	X1 5 min
16 pcs	P2 3 h	R2 130 min	N2 300 s	S2 2 h	X2 10 min
	P3 24 h	R3 24 h	N3 10800 s		X3 30 min
	0 blank				
	P1 1 h	R1 10 min	N1 30 s	S1 10 min	X1 5 min
16 pcs	P2 3 h	R2 130 min	N2 300 s	S2 2 h	X2 10 min
	P3 24 h	R3 24 h	N3 10800 s		X3 30 min
	0 blank				
Altogether: 48 pcs					
* cold neutrons					
** 2.5-2.8 MeV protons					

Table 1. Irradiation of parchment test samples at experimental stations of the Budapest Neutron Centre

For performing FTIR spectra the attenuated total reflection (ATR) technique was used due to the lack of any sample preparation. The spectra were recorded on a Varian 2000 (Scimitar Series) FTIR spectrometer with mercury/cadmium/telluride (MCT) detector. A 'Golden Gate' ATR accessory (SPECAC) with a 45° diamond single reflection ATR element was used with an active surface area of 0.6 x 0.6 mm². 64 scans at a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ were averaged. The samples were placed on the top of the diamond ATR element and the contact was insured by a constant 60cNm pressure using a sapphire clamp. Before evaluation all spectra were ATR corrected using the Varian Resolution Pro 4.0 software.

1.12.2 Interpretation of results

As a result of the FTIR analysis, we can be summarized as the following:

Irradiated type I samples without paint:

No spectral changes were observed after PGAA, RAD, SANS and PIXE irradiations. We supposed that the applied doses do not damage the parchment material.

After NAA, however, visible damage of parchment occurs: after 30 s irradiation. The parchment became a little yellowish, however, no spectral changes can be observed.

Figure 1. Damage of samples after NAA irradiation

After 300 and 10800 s irradiation the parchment loses its flexibility and even fractured. Drastic changes could be observed also in the IR spectra suggesting a damage in the secondary (changes regarding the Amide I band) and tertiary (changes regarding the Amide II band) structure of parchment's proteins. **Irradiated type II samples with blue paint (ultramarine, gum arabic):**

Again, no spectral change was observed for all the irradiation methods with the exception of NAA. In spite of the blue painted parchment became more rigid and darkened after NAA for 30s, no changes in the ATR-FTIR spectra were witnessed. Higher exposition time, however, lead to alteration and damage of gum arabic layer as revealed by the reduction and shift of typical C-O-C bands of polysaccharides around 1010 cm^{-1} . Moreover, the painted layer starts to peel and the ATR-FTIR spectra being dominated by the Amide I and Amide II bands of the parchments base (1628 and 1532 cm^{-1} , respectively).

Irradiated type III samples with red paint (carmine, gum arabic):

No spectral changes were observed after PGAA, RAD, and SANS irradiations. After PIXE irradiation, some extremely small new shoulders/bands can be observed probably due to some minor decomposition products of the organic carmine paint. However, no direct sign of damage could be noticed.

After NAA irradiation, significant damage of red painted samples was observed, too. Similar to previous samples, no spectral changes could be seen after 30 sec NAA irradiation. After 300 seconds and 10800 seconds of irradiation, the ATR-FTIR spectra showed both signs of degradation of the gum arabic and peeling of the painted layer.

In summary, no visible and spectral features of damage could be observed after PGAA, RAD, and SANS irradiations. Some very small spectral shoulders/bands probably belonging to decomposition products of red organic paint (carmine) was observed after PIXE irradiation. NAA irradiation caused visible lesion on both the pure parchment and painted parchment samples. Spectral features indicate changes in protein structure of parchments material (leading to increase in rigidity) and of gum arabic of painted layers detectable after 300 sec of NAA treatment. After 10800 sec NAA, the peeling of the painted layer was observed which leads to the difference between parallel measurements. This results have been partly reported at D6.2 of IPERION CH.

Assessment of the induced radioactivity following the irradiation of some typical archaeological material

During the (n, γ) reaction, which is the fundamental nuclear reaction when slow neutrons interact with the target atomic nuclei, the amount of the induced radioactivity primarily determined by the thermal equivalent flux of the neutron beam (which is the characteristic of the experimental arrangement), the amount of the target nuclei (which depends on the composition of the sample), the neutron capture cross-sections of the irradiated nuclei and half-lives of the produced isotopes (which are nuclear constants).

$$A(t_c) = \Phi \cdot \sigma \cdot \frac{m \cdot \Theta \cdot N_A}{M} \cdot (1 - \exp(-\lambda t_i)) \cdot \exp(-\lambda t_c)$$

Where

A	is the activity of a given nuclide
Φ	is the thermal equivalent neutron flux
σ	is the neutron absorption cross-section
m	is the mass of an irradiated element
Θ	is the isotopic abundance
N_A	is the Avogadro-number
M	is the molar weight of an irradiated element
t_i	is the irradiation time
t_c	is the cooling time after the end of the irradiation

In practice, we have to pay attention to elements, which are present in a significant amount and/or with large cross section to produce induced radioactivity. On the other hand, because of the usual length of the neutron irradiation during measurements, those isotopes might represent the risk of activation, which have a half-life between some minutes and some days. Those, which have much longer half-life, will not be activated significantly, on the other hand, those which have much shorter half-life, will decay quickly.

In case of samples of our everyday practice, the risk of activation has been checked for the following elements: Na, Mg, Al, Mn, Co, Cu, Zn, Ag and Au. From these elements, Na, Mg, Al, Mn, Co and Cu could be constituents of glass (especially of natron-glass), rocks, ceramics, while Mn, Co, Cu, Zn, Ag and Au are typical constituents of various metal alloys, such as bronze, brass, silver and gold alloys.

The produced radioactive daughter isotopes, their half-lives and the energies of the emitted γ -radiation during the decay are summarized in Table 2.

Element	Radioactive isotopes	Half-life	Decay γ -energy
Sodium	^{24}Na	14.96 h	1368.63 keV
			2754.03 keV
Magnesium	^{27}Mg	9.46 min	843.74 keV
Aluminum	^{28}Al	2.24 min	1778.97 keV
Manganese	^{56}Mn	2.58 h	846.77 keV
			1810.77 keV
Cobalt	$^{60\text{m}}\text{Co}$	10.47 min	58.6 keV
Copper	^{64}Cu	12.7 h	1345.84 keV
	^{66}Cu	5.1 min	1039.23 keV
Zink	$^{69\text{m}}\text{Zn}$	13.76 h	438.63 keV
Silver	^{108}Ag	2.39 min	632.97 keV
	$^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$	249.8 day	657.76 keV
Gold	^{198}Au	2.69 day	411.80 keV

Table 2. List of the most commonly produced radioisotopes during different irradiation conditions of various archaeological materials (rocks, ceramics, glass and metals)

To estimate the expected induced radioactivity due to low energy (thermal) neutrons, one can use the following figure. Activity values after 1 hour irradiation can be read. The number of atoms of the irradiated isotopes is 10 mmol (6×10^{21} atoms) in a thermal equivalent neutron flux of $10^8 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. The curves refer to typical cross section values between 0.1 and 100 barns. Activity values for some interesting isotopes are presented. The activity values do not contain the activity produced during measurements due to irradiation with epithermal or higher energy neutrons. For such cases there is a well usable website (<https://webapps.frm2.tum.de/activation/>) one can visit to assess the activity of the induced radioactive isotopes after regular time periods and the time necessary to reach the clearance level.

Fig. 2. Calculation of induced radioactivity of some typical isotopes at the PGAA instrument of the Budapest Research Reactor, after 1 h irradiation (Kardilov et al., Neutron methods for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage, p. 318, Springer International Publishing Switzerland, 2017)

For a more exact assessment of the induced radioactivity and for the estimation of potential health risk when handling irradiated objects, calculations have been made using the Neutron Activation Analysis Prognosis Code 2003, v. 1.0 beta software. An average composition of the most frequent HS materials, such as glass, ceramics, obsidian and bronze, considered for the calculations. Typical irradiation times of 1h and 12h were chosen. Calculations have been conducted for PGAA, NAA and RAD stations at the BNC, taking into account thy typical thermal equivalent neutron fluxes at their sample positions. The initial data for the calculations are given in Table 3.

PGAA ($9.6 \cdot 10^7$): Obsidian, ceramics, glass, bronze, silver		SANS ($5 \cdot 10^7$): Obsidian, ceramics, glass, bronze, silver	
		<i>Irradiation time</i>	
<i>Cooling time</i>		1h	12h
1 min	Ceramics: Al-28	Ceramics: Al-28; Glass: Mn-56, Na-24	
1 h			
1 day	Bronze, silver: Cu-64		
3 days			
1 week			
		RAD ($3.4 \cdot 10^7$): Ceramics	
		<i>Irradiation time</i>	
<i>Cooling time</i>		4h	1h
3 days	Obsidian, ceramics: Na-24		12h
1 week		1 min	Mn-56
2 weeks		1 h	Mn-56
1 month		1 day	
3 months		1 week	
1 year			

Table 3. List of the significant radioactive isotopes in different irradiation conditions and the calculated necessary cooling times

According to our calculations, in case of irradiations of obsidian, ceramics or glass samples at the PGAA instrument for 1 h or even for 12 h, only Al-28, Mn-56 and Na-24 show significant induced radioactivity levels, which, however, decay to the safe level with half-lives of 2.24 min. 2.58 h and 14.96 h, respectively. In practice, following a few hours cooling, the object can be returned to the owner. Calculations are very similar for the SANS instrument, as the same neutron flux can be measured as at the PGAA instrument.

When irradiating bronze (Cu, Sn, As, Sb, Ag) or silver (Cu, Ag, Au) alloys for 12 h or longer at the PGAA or SANS instruments, only the Cu-64 isotope (12.7 h half-life) must be taken into account, as significant amount of induced radioactivity. However, after 3 days or longer cooling time, the level of the induced radioactivity decays well below the safety limits.

In case of irradiation obsidian or ceramics samples at the NAA, Na-24 produces significant radioactivity, which – due to the higher neutron flux – decays in longer period (typically in more days). One has to remember that in case of NAA, small subsamples are taken from the objects, which are usually not necessary to return to the owner.

1.12.3 Conclusions and Perspectives

Finally, in case of irradiation of a ceramics object at the RAD station, Mn-56 produces significant induced radioactivity, which decays in a few hours.

According to our calculations and health physics measurements, treatments of samples following the irradiation at PGAA or at SANS stations requires special attentions (not to touch directly and place it behind shielded storage), but after few days cooling, the objects can be freely moved to any public space, i.e. to museum exhibitions, as they do not represent any health risk.

On the other hand, irradiation at RAD or NAA instruments might induce higher level of radioactivity that imply longer cooling time (weeks or months), during which it is strictly forbidden to move the objects to public area from the safety deposits.

1.13 Non destructive characterization of historical glasses via Non linear Optical Microscopy (NLOM), MPFE modality, safe limits investigation

1.13.1 Context and concept

Historical glass-based objects undergo, since the time of their manufacture, different degradation phenomena that are related to their composition and the environment to which they were exposed. Three-dimensional (3D) structural and chemical characterization of the degradation layers is important to selecting the most adequate conservation strategies for glass objects. Optical microscopy (OM) is the most frequently used non-destructive method to examine the surface of historical glasses; however, the 3D structural assessment of alteration layers requires applying the destructive modality of this technique to conduct a cross-sectional study. In this project, we have applied a set of non-invasive photonic laser-based spectroscopies and nonlinear optical microscopy in the modality of multiphoton excitation fluorescence (NLOM-MPEF) for the structural and chemical characterization of artificial alteration layers on model medieval-like glasses. Laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) and FT-Raman spectroscopies were employed for the assessment of the molecular composition of the alteration layers, while MPEF allowed the non-invasive determination of the thickness of these layers. The results obtained by examining cross sections by OM that provided thickness values were compared with those retrieved with the above-mentioned photonic laser-based techniques. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that MPEF microscopy has been used for the assessment of the thickness of alteration layers on medieval-like glass. The good agreement found for the two sets of measurements exemplifies the possibility of carrying out the structural and chemical characterization of cultural heritage in a non-destructive way and without sample preparation.

This study is the result of the collaboration between the team of the IPERION HS partnership from Instituto de Química Física Blas Cabrera (former Rocasolano), CSIC, Madrid, Spain, and different Institutes belonging to CSIC in Madrid (Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio and Instituto de Estructura de la Materia). The common work has resulted in one publication (**Mohamed Oujja, Teresa Palomar, Marina Martínez-Weinbaum, Sagrario Martínez-Ramírez and Marta Castillejo, *The European Physical Journal Plus* 136 (2021) 859, <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-01834-w>**) and oral presentations in several meeting and conferences in the Heritage Science field.

1.13.2 Materials and methods

Medieval-like model glass samples and alteration processes

The study was undertaken on medieval-like model glasses subjected to various environmental and atmospheric conditions to generate alteration layers of different characteristics. A potash-lime silicate glass, with a composition similar to that of medieval glasses, was melted at 1400 °C for two hours, poured in a brass mould of rectangular cross-section, and annealed at 650 °C. The resulting glass ingot was cut into slices of around $10 \times 10 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ and then polished using emery paper and an aqueous suspension of cerium oxide to obtain optical-quality surfaces. Alteration of the glass slices was conducted by exposure to five different laboratory corrosion tests. **Fig. 1** shows images of the unaltered medieval-like glass sample and of the samples generated by the induced alteration processes.

For the sample labeled MAK, a Kesternich VCK-300 corrosion chamber (Metrotec) was used following the standard DIN 50018 (SO₂ corrosion). The glass sample was exposed to 6667

ppm of SO₂ at 40 °C and 100 % relative humidity (RH) for 8 hours, followed by exposure to 16 hours at environmental temperature, humidity, and atmosphere. The test was repeated for five cycles. The sample named MAR was immersed in 25.0 ml of synthetic river water at 60 °C for 155 days. Finally, three different accelerated aging burial tests were carried out using acidic, neutral, and basic natural soils. The samples MTA (acidic), MTB (basic), and MTN (neutral) were buried in methacrylate boxes with a starting volume of soil of 65×45×13 mm³ and 12.5 ml of distilled water. The burial tests were undertaken at 60 °C for 35 days. Every 5 days, 5.0 ml of distilled water was added to replace the evaporated water and maintain wet conditions.

Fig. 1. Images of unaltered medieval-like glass sample and of samples MAK, MAR, MTA, MTB and MTN resulting from exposure to different atmospheric and environmental conditions (see text). The measuring bar corresponds to 1 cm.

1.13.3 Monitoring protocol

The medieval-like model glasses were compositionally and structurally characterized by OM, LIF and FT-Raman spectroscopy, and by NLOM in the modality of MPEF.

A reflected light microscope Leica DM-LM with a Leica DFC 480 digital camera served for surface observation and thickness assessment in the cross-section of the samples.

LIF measurements were carried out using laser excitation at 266 nm (4th harmonic of a Q-switched Nd:YAG laser, 6 ns pulses, 10 Hz repetition rate) and a 0.30 m spectrograph with a 300 lines/mm grating coupled to an intensified charged coupled detector. The temporal gate of the detector was operated at zero-time delay with respect to the arrival of the laser pulse to the surface of the sample and with a width of 3 μ s. The sample was illuminated by the laser at an incidence angle of 45° with pulses of around 0.1 mJ using a laser spot size of 1 x 2 mm².

The Raman spectra were acquired with a Bruker FT-Raman MultiRam Spectrophotometer equipped with a cooled Ge detector. The excitation source consists of a continuous Nd:YAG laser emitting at 1064 nm. Controlled laser power output in the range of 200–300 mW was applied during measurements. The scattered light from an area of < 0.01 cm² was collected in the reflection geometry (180°). Each FT-Raman spectrum resulted from the accumulation of 200 scans with an exposure time and wavenumber resolution of 10 s and 4 cm⁻¹, respectively.

For MPEF measurements, we used a home-made non-linear optical microscope, described in detail elsewhere, based on a mode-locked Ti:Sapphire femtosecond laser source. Briefly, the femtosecond laser emitting at 800 nm with an average power of 640 mW, pulse duration of 75 fs and a repetition rate of 80 MHz, was modulated by a chopper at a frequency of 130 Hz. The laser beam was conducted to the artificially altered glass samples through the aperture of a microscope objective lens (M Plan Apo HL 50X, Mitutoyo, NA 0.42) by using a dichroic beam splitter (FF750-SDi02-25x36, Semrock) with high reflection at 800 nm. The sample under study was placed on a motorized translation XYZ stage (with components Standa 8MVT100-25-1 for XY and Standa 8MTF for Z) that served to place the sample in the focal plane of the laser beam with lateral and axial resolutions of 1 and 2 μm , respectively. The MPEF signals generated from the volume of the sample situated in the focal plane of the objective lens were collected in the reflection mode after transmission through a beam splitter (70/30) and a cut-off filter, to reflect the remaining excitation laser light (short pass filter; 335-610 nm, Thorlabs FGB37S), and were measured with a photomultiplier tube (PMT, 9783B, ET Enterprises) connected to a lock-in amplifier (SR810 DSP, Stanford Research Systems) to ensure high amplification and signal-to-noise ratio. A LabVIEW interface served for control of the scanning and data acquisition procedures. The remaining 30% of the MPEF signal, after directing the remaining 70% to the PMT, was sent to a CCD camera (Thorlabs DCC1645C) for online visualization of the sample surface. During MPEF measurements the photon dose applied to the surface of the samples was 80×106 pulses/point.

The thickness value of the glass alteration layers was obtained by recording MPEF Z-scan profiles in six different points of the sample surface. The full width at half maximum (FWHM) resulting from a Lorentzian function fitting of the profiles were then averaged and corrected by the apparent depth correction factor $F = \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - \text{NA}^2}}{n - \sqrt{n^2 - \text{NA}^2}}$ where NA is the numerical aperture of the focusing objective lens (0.42) and n the refractive index of the analyzed material.

1.13.4 Results

Optical microscopy

The surface and stratigraphy of the medieval like-glass samples were studied by OM (**Fig. 2**). The MAK sample, resulting from exposure to a SO_2 enriched atmosphere, shows a structure of five layers, in correspondence with the five alteration cycles applied (**Fig. 2 a**). Each layer has a thickness of 6 to 9 μm with white crystals detected between layers that are probably due to the formation of sulphates. These crystals are generated in fissures of the altered layer due to the reaction of the environmental SO_2 , dissolved in the adsorbed humidity, with the alkaline and alkaline earths lixiviated from the glass core. Their growth favours the detachment of the most external layers giving rise to a quite heterogeneous crust (**Fig. 2 b**).

The MAR sample, generated by immersion in synthetic river water, displays a homogeneous surface with fissures and groups of circular pits (**Fig. 2 d**). The pits have different sizes as a function of the degree of alteration, with depths between 25 and 55 μm (**Fig. 2c**). The altered layer has a single-layer homogenous profile, probably because the glass slice was permanently immersed in the aquatic environment. Circular fissures were observed around the pits while the rest of the alteration layer shows a heterogeneous cracked surface as a result of the stresses between the altered and unaltered glass. In the area without pits, a homogeneous alteration layer of $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ is observed.

The samples degraded in burial environments (MTA, MTB and MTN) showed fissured alteration layers (**Fig. 2 f, h, j**) with a brownish hue. The sample MTA, buried in acidic soil, displays a multi-layer structure of seven degradation layers, each 10-25 μm thick (**Fig. 2 e**),

where most external ones appear partially detached as a consequence of their manipulation. Sandy material was observed between the most external layers.

The MTB sample, buried in basic soil, presented a thin alteration crust as a result of the degradation and loss of most external layers (**Fig. 2 h**). The multi-layered structure was less defined than in the MTA sample; however, at high magnification, layers of 5-10 μm thickness become evident (**Fig. 2 g**).

Finally, the sample MTN shows a homogenous alteration layer as a consequence of the neutral pH of the soil in which it was buried (**Fig. 2 j**). Some irregularities were observed in the alteration front, probably as a consequence of inclusions or bubbles that could affect the hydration of the glass. The alteration layer in this sample displays a thick single-layer structure (**Fig. 2 i**).

The average values of the alteration layers in the MAK, MAR, MTA, MTB and MTN were measured in 10 different locations along the cross-section of the samples and estimated in 58, 46, 97, 30 and 75 μm , respectively.

Fig. 2 Optical microscopy images of the surface (left column) and cross-section (right column) of degradation layers on model medieval-like glass samples: a, b) MAK; c, d) MAR; e, f) MTA; g, h) MTB and i, j) MTN.

FT-Raman Spectroscopy

The FT-Raman spectra of the medieval-like glasses are shown in **Fig. 3**. **Fig. 3a** corresponds to the spectrum of the unaltered glass, where bands located in the wavenumber ranges of 500-700 and 750-1250 cm^{-1} are assigned to the bending and stretching modes of Si-O bonds,

respectively, typically appearing in 20th century stained ($K_2O + CaO$) silicate glasses. The structure of a silicate glass can be described in terms of the Q_n notation, where n expresses the number of bonding oxygen (BO) atoms per tetrahedron: a tetrahedron fully linked into the network via four BO is labelled as a Q_4 unit, whereas an isolated tetrahedron with no BO corresponds to a Q_0 unit. The quantity of each of the five possible Q_n is used to describe the local structure and connectivity of the glass network. The stretching bands (in the range $750-1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$) can be assigned in terms of Q_n to Q_0 (isolated SiO_4 between 750 and 850 cm^{-1}), Q_1 ($900-950\text{ cm}^{-1}$), Q_2 ($990-1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$), Q_3 (1100 cm^{-1}) and Q_4 ($1150-1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The bands around 650 cm^{-1} correspond to the Si-O-Si bending massif modes for medieval-like glass. The above spectral features are generically indicated by the label MG in the FT-Raman spectra.

The spectrum of the MAK sample, subjected to SO_2 atmosphere (**Fig. 3b**), displays, together with the bands of the unaltered glass body, a doublet band with maxima at 1005 and 980 cm^{-1} , which together with the signals at 649 , 620 , 605 , 489 , 477 , 448 , 436 and 170 cm^{-1} allows the identification of calcium and potassium sulphate in the form of syngenite ($K_2Ca(SO_4)_2 \cdot H_2O$). Concerning the MAR sample, treated by immersion in synthetic river water (**Fig. 3c**), bands at 1085 and 289 cm^{-1} reveal the presence of calcium carbonate in the form of calcite.

Finally, **Fig. 3 d-f** shows the FT-Raman spectra of MTA, MTB and MTN samples. Bands that were observed in the wavenumber range of $1200-2000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to the vibrations of organic compounds present in the burial surrounding media where the samples were treated. Besides, in addition to the FT-Raman bands observed in the case of the unaltered glass, various bands at lower wavenumbers (491 , 402 , 286 and 220 cm^{-1}) appeared in the spectra of MTA and MTB samples; these are attributed to a mixture of the iron (III) oxide chromophore (hematite, Fe_2O_3), clay and silica.

Fig. 3 FT-Raman spectra of unaltered medieval-like glass a) and degradation layers: b) MAK; c) MAR; d) MTA; e) MTB and f) MTN. MG, S, Cc, H and OC mean unaltered glass (see text)

glass, calcium sulphate, calcite (calcium carbonate), hematite (Fe_2O_3) and organic compounds, respectively.

Laser Induced Fluorescence Spectroscopy

LIF spectra are displayed in **Fig. 4**, and they consist of a broad feature in the 300-800 nm region, although the different samples display special characteristics that can be associated with their composition. In the region around 300-450 nm, a band with a shoulder at short wavelengths (330-360 nm) can be assigned to oxygen deficiency centres (ODC) from the glass network. Centered in the region around 520 nm, an additional contribution is observed that is attributed to the Ca^{2+} ion chromophore present in the glass lattice and burial media. The contribution of the feature associated with the Ca^{2+} chromophore is substantial in the spectra of MAK and MAR samples (**Fig. 4 b, c**). This is in correspondence with the significance of calcium sulphate and calcium carbonate bands, respectively, as revealed by FT-Raman spectra.

Fig. 4 LIF spectra of the unaltered medieval-like glass a) and different degraded samples: b) MAK; c) MAR; d) MTA; e) MTB and f) MTN. ODC and OC refer to oxygen deficiency centres and organic compounds, respectively. Each LIF spectrum resulted from the accumulation of 10 individual ones upon laser excitation at 266 nm and using spectral resolution of 5 nm.

The spectra of samples MTA, MTB and MTN, while following the general trend of MAK and MAR spectra, display specific additional features. For MTA, contributions in the spectral regions of 520 and 610 nm are assigned to bands of the organic compounds, in addition to Ca^{2+} contribution, and of Mn^{2+} chromophore, respectively (**Fig. 4d**). On the other hand, the sample MTB (**Fig. 4e**) shows an increase of intensity for the band at 360 nm, attributed to $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ chromophores, which is due to the presence of iron oxides in the alteration layer. Finally, the spectrum of sample MTN (**Fig. 4f**) is similar to that of MTA with slight intensity variations in the regions around 450, 520 and 610 nm. The band at 520 nm shows lower intensity in this

sample in correspondence with the low intensity of organic compounds bands observed by FT-Raman.

Notwithstanding the information LIF spectra yield about the composition of the alteration layers, it is important to note that, upon laser excitation at 266 nm, all samples analysed generate a broad emission in the spectral range that is used for the collection of MPEF signals (335-610 nm). This ensures that the MPEF collected from the glass samples corresponds to fluorescence emissions of the constituents of the analysed layers.

Multiphoton Excitation Fluorescence

To determine the thickness of the glass alteration layers via MPEF Z-scan profiles under safe irradiation conditions, it is necessary to determine the suitable femtosecond average laser powers to ensure that the irradiated regions of the samples are not modified or damaged during measurements. To determine the adequate, safe operating laser powers, we used the procedure consisting in monitoring the variation of the intensity of the MPEF signal upon repetitive irradiation, as changes in intensity are a signature of possible structural or photochemical alteration of the irradiated area of the sample. To determine the onset laser power for modification or damage, the acquisition of MPEF signals is carried out by irradiating a certain point of the sample at a given laser power, then moving to a fresh area at increasing laser power and repeating the process until changes of intensity of the MPEF signals are detected. The safe power limits are dependent of the irradiation mode (laser repetition rate, photon dose) and on the compositional characteristics of the sample.

In this work, to identify the adequate laser power limits for each glass sample, we collected four MPEF Z-scan profiles in the same point at increasingly larger fixed laser powers in the range of 0.4-1.2 mW. **Fig. 5** displays a selection of the MPEF depth-scan profiles obtained in the various glass alteration layers. We observed different intensity trends according to the sample. The MPEF intensity increased upon repetitive irradiation cycles for MAK, MAR and MTB (**Fig. 5 a, c, g**) and decreased for MTA and MTN samples (**Fig. 5 e, i**). Applying the described procedure, safe average powers, where MPEF intensity is maintained upon the four cycles of irradiation, were estimated in 0.8, 0.6, 0.8, 0.8, and 0.65 mW for the samples MAK, MAR, MTA, MTB and MTN, respectively. MPEF Z-scan profiles applying these safe average powers are presented in **Fig. 5 b, d, f, h, j** where the stability of the signal becomes apparent.

Figure 6 shows the MPEF Z-scan profiles acquired by using the determined safe laser average powers on a random position of the samples. The thickness of the alteration layers on the medieval-like glasses were estimated, as indicated previously, by measuring the full width at half maximum (FWHM) resulting from a Lorentzian function fitting of the MPEF profile and corrected by the F factor which depends of the material refractive index. Refractive indices of medieval potash-lime stained glass samples were measured and found to be in the range from 1.54-1.56. We assume that the average value of the refractive indices of the different alteration layers could only slightly deviate from that of the body glass and have estimated a value for F of 1.61. **Table 1** compares the thickness of the various glass alteration layers as determined by MPEF and OM in the cross-section modality, where a generally good agreement between the two sets of measurements is shown. It is noticed that the comparison is not entirely satisfactory for the MTA sample, a fact that could be related to the multilayer, inhomogeneous structure of the alteration layer of this sample.

Figure 5. Left column: MPEF depth-scan profiles of samples: a) MAK, c) MAR; e) MTA; g) MTB and i) MTA at average laser powers of 0.9, 0.65, 0.9, 0.95 and 0.8 mW, respectively. As indicated by the arrows, the maximum fluorescence intensity at these laser powers tends to increase for MAK, MAR and MTB and to decrease for MTA and MTN samples as the number of axial scanning runs increases from 1 to 4. Right column: corresponding MPEF profiles using average laser powers of 0.8, 0.6, 0.8, 0.8, and 0.65 mW, considered suitable for safe analyses.

As seen in **Table 1**, the thicknesses of the glass alteration layers depend on the nature of the surrounding exposure or burial conditions. The good agreement with OM results proves that MPEF microscopy is efficient in assessing in a non-destructive way the variability in the thickness of the studied samples under safe measurement conditions.

Samples	OM	MPEF
MAK	58 ± 12	65 ± 18
MAR	46 ± 8	44 ± 12
MTA	97 ± 12	46 ± 10
MTB	30 ± 4	38 ± 8
MTN	75 ± 4	58 ± 16

Table 1. Comparison between average thicknesses (over a set of six different positions in each sample) and standard deviation (in μm) of the alteration layers of model medieval-like glass samples as measured by OM in cross section and non-invasively by MPEF microscopy using previously determined safe average laser powers.

Figure 6. Examples of MPEF Z-scan profiles determined using safe laser average powers on random positions of the samples: a) MAK; b) MAR; c) MTA; d) MTB and e) MTN. Fits with Lorentzian functions are indicated in red and the full width at half maximum values, after refractive index correction, in blue.

1.13.5 Conclusions and perspectives

The study presented in this manuscript has made use of the photonic laser-based spectroscopies of LIF and FT-Raman for the determination of the molecular composition of model medieval-like glass and of different alteration layers. These layers were generated by exposure to different laboratory corrosion tests and mimic various usually encountered degradation pathologies in historic glasses. The manuscript also presents the capacity of MPEF microscopy

to accurately determine in a non-invasive way the thickness of the glass degradation layers, an application of this technique never explored before. In the paragraphs below, we summarize the findings obtained by applying this photonic approach and compare them with those acquired by applying a more conventional, albeit destructive, characterization methodology based on OM.

LIF spectra allowed to identify oxygen deficiency centres from the glass network, by virtue of bands around 350 and 450 nm, and, by the emission in the 520 nm region, the presence of Ca^{2+} of compounds of the glass matrix and of the materials of the surrounding environments. LIF spectra of MTA and MTN samples revealed the presence of the Mn^{3+} , through assignment of a band at 610 nm, while in the case of the MTB, iron compounds are apparent by the intense feature around 360 nm.

While LIF provided indications of the composition of the glass and of the alteration layers, FT-Raman spectroscopy facilitated its mineralogical identification. In fact, the FT-Raman bands observed for the unaltered glass allow classifying it as a $\text{K}_2\text{O} + \text{CaO}$ potash-lime silicate. The spectra of MAK and MAR samples revealed the respective presence of calcium and potassium sulphates originated by the exposure to an SO_2 atmosphere and of calcium carbonate due to the effect of synthetic river water. Bands of organic compounds appear in the FT-Raman spectra of MTA, MTB and MTN sample, and of hematite in MTA and MTB samples, the compound which is responsible of their brown coloration.

As seen, the combination of LIF and FT-Raman spectroscopies provided a detailed chemical and mineralogical picture of the materials in the set of samples of this study. Apart from providing complete chemical information at the molecular level, the obvious benefit of applying laser spectroscopies is indeed its non-destructive character and their capacities for in situ analysis. The photonic approach proposed here is complemented with the non-invasive, accurate determination of thickness of the alteration layers via MPEF microscopy. Through the determination of adequate femtosecond laser powers that ensure safe measurement conditions, an accurate estimation of the thickness of glass degradation layers was possible via this technique, as confirmed through the comparison with OM results (**Table 1**).

Thus, the proposed methodology, which involves the application of photonic laser-based spectroscopies and non-linear laser microscopy, exemplify the possibility to carry out non-destructive compositional and structural characterization of heritage glass items without sample preparation. The implementation of this approach in the field of cultural heritage and its application to real case studies in museums or heritage building environments will come in hand with the ongoing advances in femtosecond laser technology and optical component arrangements that will facilitate the availability of robust, reliable and portable nonlinear optical microscopes integrating various NLO modalities.

1.14 X-ray techniques for the study of ancient bones and teeth

1.14.1 Context and concept:

Radiation damage has been an important research thematic of IPANEMA and of the PUMA beamline for more than ten years and this resulted in two publications identifying the practical advances in terms of detection, monitoring, interpretation and mitigation of beam damage]. Moreover, Gueriau et al. highlighted the photo-oxidation of the cerium rare-earth from Ce^{3+} to Ce^{4+} in a shrimp fossil over a time scale of minutes by measuring the modifications of X-ray absorption near-edge (XANES) spectra at the L_3 edge. More specifically, X-ray synchrotron radiation effects on cotton paper and Egyptian blue and green pigments have been investigated at the PUMA beamline [Gimat 2020 and Godet 2022] using either UV photoluminescence (PL) or electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy to monitor the effects after irradiation.

On the other hand, bones have been studied at IPANEMA in the framework of a long-term collaboration with the Lab-BC CNRS research unit at the Center for Research and Restoration of the French Museums (C2RMF) to analyze the trace elements in prehistoric mammoth ivory. Mammoth ivory and bone samples have been analyzed at the PUMA beamline and at the New AGLAE accelerator external microfocus beamline [Tranchant 2023]. No visible beam damage has been noticed on the archaeological samples at that time. However, in the literature beam damage on ancient teeth and bones have been reported such as teeth darkening [Richards 2012] and degradation of ancient DNA for bones [Sauer 2022]. As a result, we wanted to investigate in which conditions visible beam damage appear on ancient bones and teeth, how we can better highlight them and if we can monitor the damage during the irradiation and after the irradiation. We gathered a corpus of ancient teeth of five distinct mammals dating between 70 million and 10,000 years representing various taphonomies. In order to reproduce irradiations conditions similar to those occurring during microtomography and μ XAS experiments, samples have been prepared in two different ways. One part has been studied without sample preparation on their outer layer, which corresponds to microtomography experiments. The others have been polished or cut and polished to obtain flat specimens for μ XAS and elemental and speciation mapping. The work on cross-sections helped us to assess the effect of irradiation on different fossilized biological tissues (dentin, enamel). In addition to that, a reference sample (pure synthesized hydroxyapatite) has been prepared for comparison as hydroxyapatite is one of the major components of teeth.

1.14.2 Monitoring protocol

Teeth samples have been irradiated at the PUMA beamline using a beam with an energy ranging from 6 to 18 keV in order to perform XRF mappings and XAS measurements at Mn K-edge and Ce L-edge with a X-ray spot of 10 μ m size. No clear XAS spectrum modifications have been detected and no visible beam damage has been observed for all the irradiated samples even for samples that have been irradiated more than 70 hours with a beam flux of about 10^9 - 10^{10} photons/sec. However, we noticed a variation of the XEOL (X-ray excited optical luminescence) signal during the irradiation for some samples. XEOL is a complex phenomenon where X-rays absorbed by the material is converted to optical photons in the visible range [Pédroni 2005 and Rezende 2016]. During X-ray irradiation, some teeth samples emitted optical

light from the irradiated spot and this emission decreases during the time. As a result, we optimized the XEOL detection in order to follow and to quantify this decay.

The in-situ XEOL measurements have been carried out with an Hamamatsu Orca CMOS camera having 4 million 650-nm-wide pixels (2048x2048) and with a x10 objective. This camera makes it possible to observe the sample in-situ during the irradiation thanks to the geometry of the PUMA beamline. The sample is arranged in a 45°/45° geometry with respect to the incident beam and the X-ray fluorescence silicon drift detector (SDD). The camera is pointed perpendicular to the sample surface as it is shown in the figure 1. The set-up contains different emission filters from visible to near-IR, a dichroic mirror at 665 nm and also a UV-visible tunable LED source. This source allows to carry out in-situ luminescence measurements after the irradiation and especially to test the effect of concomitant UV illumination of the sample during X-ray irradiation on the decrease of the XEOL. UV illumination is indeed a solution used to attenuate or remove the teeth darkening after X-ray irradiation. Moreover, after irradiation it is possible to make UV based PL micro imaging of the samples.

Figure 1. experimental setup of the PUMA beamline.

We monitored the XEOL decay by taking a 1 second snapshot of the XEOL with the microscope every 15 seconds during 45 minutes of X-ray irradiation followed by 45 minutes of monitoring without X-ray irradiation and again 45 minutes of X-ray irradiation. We characterized the XEOL signal on a minute time scale as a function of the absorbed dose, the type of fossilized biological tissue (enamel, dentin), the incident energy, the filter used to detect the XEOL and the use of the concomitant UV illumination. The principle of the experiment is presented in the figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2: (a) Scheme of the detection of the XEOL decay on an ancient tooth sample without UV. Simultaneously the X-ray irradiation the fluorescence is measured with a silicon drift detector (SDD) and the XEOL signal is measured with the microscope. (b) Microscope images and XEOL signal intensity evolution during the experiment.

Figure 3. (a) Scheme of the detection of the XEOL decay on an ancient tooth sample with concomitant UV illumination. (b) Microscope images and XEOL signal intensity evolution during the experiment.

1.14.3 Interpretation of results

The XEOL signal was used as a probe to monitor the beam damage. It indicates the chemical modifications appearing in the material during the irradiation such as the local structure of the atom involved in the luminescence emissions [Rezende 2016]. Variations in the XEOL intensity and in the shape of its spectrum is thus a demonstration of the beam induced modifications. However, their interpretation in terms of chemical modifications is not easy because it is challenging to determine the chemical origin of the XEOL signal for an

heterogeneous material. We also need the XEOL spectrum to understand how it is decaying during the irradiation and how we can link this decay to chemical modifications. Since we did not have access to a spectrometer to investigate the XEOL, our study is based on the variation of the signal in different spectral bands defined by the filters used. We characterized the XEOL decay as a function of several parameters and showed how the XEOL signal is sensitive to them. Moreover, the monitoring without X-ray beam allows us to check the evolution of the beam induced modifications after irradiation. Here, we present results for only one sample, a 32-million-year-old *Mesohippus* tooth and for hydroxyapatite for reference.

We quantified the XEOL decay using a stretched exponential function ($I = ae^{-\left(\frac{t}{\tau}\right)^\beta} + c$) because we noticed that the XEOL intensity is decreasing faster than a simple exponential decay and the stretched exponential function can be interpreted as a continuous sum of simple exponential decays [Johnston, 2006]. As a result, we can calculate a mean “relaxation time” that we will name as “darkening time” in our case because the observed process is not a relaxation.

Absorbed dose

The dependence of the XEOL signal on the absorbed dose is difficult to estimate for a heterogeneous sample. For this reason we fitted the XEOL decay for each pixel on the 4000 most intense pixels of the first microscope image snapshot (see figure 4). This way we can investigate the variation of the XEOL amplitude of decay and darkening time as a function of the incident beam intensity due to its gaussian profile. The full width half maximum of the X-ray beam at PUMA is estimated to be about 10 μm wide and 5 μm high, while the pixel size of the microscope camera is 650 nm. Moreover, we can estimate that the property of the material does not vary strongly at this length scale in the same fossilized biological tissue (enamel). We can therefore approximate that the absorbed dose is proportional to the beam flux and we assume that the XEOL intensity of the first snapshot is similar to the mapping of the beam flux reaching the sample. As a result, mapping of the XEOL amplitude of decay and of the darkening time at this resolution shows the variation of the XEOL amplitude of decay and darkening time as a function of the absorbed dose. We used the data of the irradiation of the polished enamel of the *Mesohippus* tooth with a 12 keV beam during 45 minutes.

In figure 3 the mapping of the XEOL intensity of the first snapshot is presented with the mappings of the amplitude of the exponential fit and of the darkening time. A fit of one pixel is also shown as an illustration. At this stage we can clearly see that, keeping all the parameters constant (nature of irradiated tissue, beam energy, same filtering and without UV illumination), the higher is the absorbed dose, the higher will be the decrease of the XEOL amplitude and the faster will be the decay. A more quantitative analysis remains to be done by adding a mapping of the beam flux to link definitively the absorbed dose to the XEOL decay.

Figure 4. Mappings of the XEOL signal, amplitude of the fit and darkening time for the polished enamel of a *Mesohippus* tooth irradiated by a 12-keV beam during 45 minutes and plot of the evolution of the XEOL signal of a pixel with its corresponding fit in red.

Use of concomitant UV illumination

We monitored the decay of the XEOL emission of the *Mesohippus* tooth enamel for 45 minutes on two spots with and without concomitant UV illumination at 385 nm and with a red filter (650 nm). After a 45-minute X-ray beam cut we measured again a second decay of the XEOL on the same spot during another 45-minute irradiation. The results are presented in the figures 5 and 6. In this case we fit the average value of the 1000 most intense pixels in order to have a good trade-off between a good statistic and a description of the decay of the most irradiated area. We observe that the darkening time of the first decay is shorter without UV than with UV and that the intensity values of the second decay are much lower than expected (from the extension of the fit of the first decay) without UV (figure 5d) and are higher at the beginning with UV but decreases faster than without UV (figure 6d). This highlights that UV illumination has an impact on the mitigation of the XEOL decay and consequently on the beam damage during the irradiation and during the time without X-ray irradiation. Without UV illumination we observed that damage continues to progress even during the period without X-ray irradiation as shown by the figure 5d.

Figure 5. (a) First XEOL snapshot of the *Mesohippus* tooth enamel without UV illumination. (b) Binary mask corresponding to the 1000 most intense pixels from the figure 5a and applied to the full stack of images of 90-minutes irradiation. Plots of the first (c) and second (d) decays corresponding to the average value of the 1000 most intense pixels. For the second decay the red curve corresponds to the extension of the fit of the first decay.

Figure 6. (a) First XEOL snapshot of the *Mesohippus* tooth enamel with UV illumination. (b) Binary mask corresponding to the 1000 most intense pixels from the figure 5a and applied to the full stack of images of 90-minutes irradiation. Plots of the first (c) and second (d) decays corresponding to the average value of the 1000 most intense pixels. For the second decay the red curve corresponds to the extension of the fit of the first decay.

Effect of the fossilized biological tissue, the incident energy and the filter

We repeated the previous experiments to test the effects of different parameters on the XEOL first and second decay. In the table 1 we measured the darkening times for three different biological tissues and synthesized pure hydroxyapatite while keeping the beam incident energy

constant, with a red filter and no UV. The darkening times of the first decay show that the enamel of the outside layer (non-polished) tend to be more robust to X-ray irradiation than polished dentin and polished enamel, which seems to be the most sensitive part. However, the darkening times of the second decay show different behaviours which is difficult to analyse. The recombination process during the period without X-ray beam is different from a fossilized biological tissue to another, thus inducing different decays during the second irradiation. Pure hydroxyapatite presents the highest darkening times for both decays. As a result, XEOL decay in fossilized teeth cannot be directly compared with the hydroxyapatite indicating that the fossilized material is more complex.

Fossilized biological tissue	First decay darkening time (s.)	Second decay darkening time (s.)
Polished enamel	145	1297
Polished dentin	189	1097
Enamel outside layer	197	1213
Hydroxyapatite (reference)	294	1353

Table 1. Darkening times for different fossilized biological tissues of a *Mesohippus* tooth sample and for synthesized hydroxyapatite without UV illumination, using a red filter (650 nm, bandwidth of 60 nm) for the XEOL and for a 12-keV incident beam.

We also investigated the effect of the beam energy (table 2) on the XEOL decay for the polished *Mesohippus* tooth enamel. It turns out that at an energy of 12 keV the XEOL decreases faster for both decays than for other energies even though the beam flux at this energy is not the highest. It reveals that the probed damages are sensitive to the energy of the beam. The reason why the XEOL decays faster at this specific beam energy depends on the nature of the material and needs to be further investigated.

Beam flux (ph/s)	Beam energy (keV)	First decay darkening time (s.)	Second decay darkening time (s.)
9.6×10^9	9	258	1278
8.8×10^9	12	171	1227
7×10^9	15	282	1309
4×10^9	18	278	1245

Table 2. Darkening times of the polished *Mesohippus* tooth enamel with UV illumination and using a red filter (650 nm, bandwidth of 60 nm) for the XEOL.

Finally, we tested several filters for detecting the XEOL signal in the visible and near-IR range (table 3). XEOL emission was only observed with two filters (650 and 935 nm). For both decays, the red components of the XEOL signal decreases faster than the near-IR components. This is an interesting information that could be interpreted as a monitoring of the chemical modifications.

Filter	First decay darkening time (s.)	Second decay darkening time (s.)
650 nm (bandwidth: 60 nm)	213	1120
935 nm (bandwidth: 170 nm)	643	1382

Table 3. Darkening times of the polished *Mesohippus* tooth dentin with UV illumination and different filters.

1) Monitoring of the beam damage after irradiation

After irradiation, evolution with time of the observed changes induced by the beam using PL micro-imaging was monitored with an UV illumination of 385 nm and a red filter (650 nm). On the enamel of the *Mesohippus* tooth, PL imaging after cessation of irradiation showed the presence of non-emissive lines correlated with the X-ray irradiation (immediately and 6 months after irradiation; Figure 7); however, no changes were observed in other tissues.

Figure 7. (a) and (b) XRF mappings of Ca for the polished section of *Mesohippus* fossil tooth. (c) Photoluminescence images of *Mesohippus* fossil tooth enamel irradiated with a 18 keV X-ray beam for XRF mappings. The black lines corresponding to the XRF scans showed in figures 7a and 7b (40 and 20 μm step size) are still visible about 6 months after irradiation.

In conclusion, we improved the detection of the XEOL decay by adjusting the filter of the XEOL emission, the wavelength and the intensity of the UV concomitant illumination and the beam energy to highlight the XEOL in our sample. The use of microscope to visualize the XEOL emission or darkening during the X-ray irradiation of fossil teeth is a very useful tool to help for mitigation strategies. We observed that for all our measurements the use of concomitant UV illumination helped to slow down the decrease of the first XEOL decay and also had an impact on the recombination process during the period without X-ray irradiation.

1.14.4 Protocol limitations and advances

The limitations of the protocol refer first to the sample itself. Among the corpus of teeth we tested, we did not observe XEOL for some samples for a reason we ignore. No visible beam damage was observed with PL imaging for these samples neither, however this does not mean that no alteration occurred. Second, we measured variations of the XEOL over 45 minutes with a time resolution of 15 seconds. We evidenced that it is a good probe to monitor damage over a minute time scale but we did not test the sensitivity of the technique for shorter time scales. Concerning the PL imaging the material needs to have luminescent properties but it is not a sufficient condition to highlight beam damage. For example, we did not see non-emissive lines in the dentin part even if we clearly detected XEOL decay for this tissue. Consequently, XEOL detection and PL imaging is very material dependent to monitor beam damages.

1.14.5 Perspectives

In the long-term aspect, further work will aim (i) to determine how powerful the XEOL signal is as a tool to monitor the chemical changes and (ii) to clarify the type of chemical information to which it is sensitive. For these reasons we are currently working on measuring the XEOL on shorter time scales and with shorter acquisition times. The main challenge remains to synchronize the opening of the shutter of the beamline with the acquisition of the camera in order to measure of the XEOL immediately at the beginning of the irradiation. In addition, a newly acquired spectrometer is currently being installed at the PUMA beamline. It will enable us to collect XEOL spectra specific to chemical changes in addition to the video microscope allowing the multispectral imaging of the irradiated sample in real time.

A case study would be the measurement of the XEOL variations in teeth depending on the presence of preserved collagen and to determine how the XEOL will probe the degradation of collagen in real time. The choice of the techniques to characterize the samples before and after irradiation will be of high importance. For example, we want to use SHG imaging and ATR-FTIR spectroscopy in addition to PL imaging in order to detect preserved collagen before and after irradiation and to identify and quantify the altered collagen. X-ray beams are known to destroy collagen in teeth especially in the presence of the mineral phase [Sauer 2022].

Finally, we recommend to use several techniques to optimize the characterization of the samples before irradiation and detect the modifications appearing after irradiation. The choice of the characterizing techniques will help to optimize the strategies to mitigate the beam side effects. In the case of fossil teeth PL imaging technique is interesting to monitor the beam damage for the polished enamel after irradiation but not for the other fossilized biological tissue like dentin.

2 Concept and future development of the irradiation passport

Objects of art are increasingly exposed to ionizing radiation as analytical techniques using intense photon, electron and ion beams produced by particle accelerators, synchrotrons, microscopes and other sources, are increasingly being applied for their study. Paintings are scanned using X-ray methods, tiny samples taken from these paintings are radiated at synchrotrons and in laboratory environments. Modern analytical techniques use the interactions of photons, electrons and ions with materials to identify the materials in the object. But interaction means that there is a chance of visible or invisible alterations, either permanent or temporary. The consequences of radiation in terms of long-term effects are not fully known. Several recent studies have shown that interactions between pigments and binding media are likely to significantly influence material response under irradiation. Research is complicated by the fact that “pure” pigments are complex mixtures containing traces phases, substitution elements and structural defects. Their behaviour will deviate from that of standard chemicals. Exposure to radiation is of a cumulative nature, which means that previous exposure may change the sensitivity of objects or research samples.

Therefore, both art objects and research samples in the field of cultural heritage need an irradiation passport, recording the location, total exposure and circumstances of use of radiation. Without such a passport, objects may receive an overdose due to cumulation of irradiation, results of analyses may be misinterpreted, and research into the long-term effects of irradiation of objects of art is impossible. The Irradiation Passport for Art (IPA) project was financed by NICAS (Netherlands Institute for Conservation, Art and Science; [IRRADIATION PASSPORT FOR ART - NICAS \(nicas-research.nl\)](http://www.nicas-research.nl)), and was led by conservation scientists, a physical chemist and a conservator, with the support of an international team of experts in irradiation of art, in which important synchrotron-institutes and research institutes involved in research in cultural heritage are represented. The IPA project has developed a website (www.irradiation-passport.net) to record information on radiation exposure, all the relevant parameters that were used during a measurement and information on changes -if they occurred. A screenshot of the homepage of the website is shown in figure 1. There are four images visible: to explore objects, to find techniques, to perform an advanced search and in about information on the partners, the project and how to join can be found (Figure 2-5). In figure 4 the parameters for a SEM-EDX analysis are shown. Techniques and parameters can also be added later on when needed. The website is meant for conservation scientists and conservators, who can gain free access by subscribing. The website will not hold actual measurement data, this stays with the partner institute that has uploaded the parameters. Information on existing exposures is crucial for the selection of future areas of investigation and prevents double exposure. Finally, the website acts as a resource when a restoration treatment is planned as conservators can check if and where an object was irradiated.

Figure 1: screenshot of the homepage of the website of the irradiation passport.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the explore page

Figure 3: Screenshot of the techniques page

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Objects page with the measurement parameters used to analyse an object

Figure 5: Screenshot of the about page with the partners listed

The irradiation passport for art objects and research samples was evaluated in the IPERION HS projects by the partners. During discussions it became clear that the website could be used but several things have to be improved:

- The classification of the techniques
- Add a possibility to clearly show where the analysis was done (box or point)
- Are different parameters needed for the analysis of an object or a sample?

The passport could be integrated in the data management structure developed within WP5.4 and accordingly be included in the E-RIHS structure. Within the IPERION-HS (WP6.3 and WP5.4) and E-RIHS IP projects work has been carried out to define and build an E-RIHS knowledge base (<https://data.e-rihs.io/>), based on an open source system called Cordra (<https://www.cordra.org/>). Within the future E-RIHS ERIC this system will act as the primary store for all of the key metadata required to define E-RIHS Services, proposals, projects, people, equipment, methodologies, research activities, etc. The structure of the knowledge base is based on a series of open JSON schema documents (<https://github.com/E-RIHS/schema>) linked to standardised vocabulary terms (<https://vocab.e-rihs.io/>). This will allow all of the future work of E-RIHS to be linked together as searchable knowledge rather than as a list of related reports. This plan has been described in one of the IPERION-HS Deliverables (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849169>), but further documentation work is being carried out as the system is finalised and will be reported within E-RIHS IP.

As this system should describe all of the work, carried out under E-RIHS, it should be possible to list all of the techniques, which can result in radiation damage, that have been used to examine or analyse given heritage objects or samples. Also the planned metadata models, for recording specific research methodologies and activities, could also be used to provide the details required to create Irradiation Passports. The structure of this knowledge base and the related metadata schema are expected to evolve over time, which will allow it to fully meet the needs of the Irradiation Passports as they develop.

It could also be possible, though this work has not been carried out yet, to develop custom graphical user interfaces to organise and present the metadata stored within the E-RIHS knowledge base to meet the Irradiation Passports presentation requirements

Framaforms

Questionnaire on practices for analyses using particle, X-ray and laser beams irradiations

Thank you for taking the time to respond to this survey. It will take less than 5 minutes to complete. Our aim is to identify the types of metadata that are used during analysis with particle, X-ray and laser beams and to better understand the practices used to document the analytical procedures by the operators of analytical instruments. Our goal is also to establish better procedures to estimate the dose (energy divided by irradiated mass, unit Gray), which is the best suited quantity to describe modifications in irradiated materials. As the dose depends on the beam specifications, the material composition and the interaction between them, we would be grateful if you could respond to the following questions.

Please indicate what is the information available to you.

Elaborating common protocols to archive information on the past irradiations for each experiment undergone by an object or a sample is a complex task. It is however an instrumental step to establish the list of mandatory metadata allowing to reconstruct the “history of irradiations” of materials.

The first step of our work consisted in grasping the diversity of practices to record experimental procedures within the consortium of partners gathered in the task.

In order to identify practices used in the field for adjusting and recording analytical parameters an online questionnaire was sent to the consortium of the task to collect information on the methodologies used to record information by each partner and provide a first overview of the different protocols used. the analytical parameters and the unit used to describe irradiation procedures, information the materials analysed and the environmental conditions used during experiments. The questionnaire was divided in five sections:

1. Beam specifications
2. Specifications of materials analyzed
3. Environmental conditions of the experiment
4. Record of analysed areas
5. Archiving of metadata

The result of the questionnaire was informative on the diversity of protocols and habits used and highlight the need to foster exchanges to establish common procedures to record such experimental conditions. The results of the questionnaire will be a base to continue the work and further discuss which units for beam specificities can be used by the widest panel or partners. Another aspect is the record of the environmental conditions used for experiments, since we know that specific humidity conditions for example can allow mitigating the initiation of changes. It will also feed our reflexion on how to structure and archive metadata associated with experiments in order to trace the history of radiation of materials and contribute to the sub-task 3 on the irradiation passport.

In parallel two events organized under the umbrella of IAEA and relative to the topic of the tasks and in particular to the question of establishing an irradiation passport have been supported by IPERION-HS.

Between October 17th and 20th 2022, a group of experts, composed of Loïc Bertrand (ENS Paris-Saclay, FR), Thomas Calligaro (Ministère de la Culture, FR), Ineke Joosten (RCE, NL), Sebastian Schoeder (Synchrotron SOLEIL, FR), Aliz Simon (International Atomic Energy Agency, AU), Mathieu Thoury (CNRS, FR) and Sam Webb (SSRL Stanford, US) was gathered in Vienna in the headquarters of the IAEA in the context of a Consultancy Meeting dedicated to the development strategy towards safe analysis of heritage objects and materials. During five days, a group work was undertaken to draft the follow up of the first review paper published in 2015 in *Trends in Analytical Chemistry* on the topic of safe analyses of ancient materials. The resulting output was a publication, which was published in the journal *Trends in Analytical Chemistry* in July 2023, that aimed to propose an updated review of the state developments undertaken in the field and proposing conceptual framework to promote safer analyses.

On 13-17 November 2023, the first hands-on workshop "Safe Analysis of Heritage Objects and Materials Using Novel Accelerator-based Analytical Techniques", jointly organized by the IAEA, the CNRS and the Université Paris-Saclay at Paris and Paris-Saclay area. The workshop was attended by 38 participants and has provided them with a broad overview and state-of-the-art presentation of the latest developments and procedures to improve best practices.

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